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Editor	Christos Chatzichristos (KUL)
Contributors	Sofia Balula Dias (FMH); Christos Chatzichristos, Maarten De Vos, Fan Wang (KUL); Ioannis Gerasimou, Apostolos Moustaklis, Charalampos Sotirakis, Stelios Hadjidimitriou (AUTH); Nikos Grammalidis, Theocharis Chatzis (CERTH); Tim Feige (TUD); Natalia del Campo (CHUT)
Reviewed by	Björn Falkenburger (TUD) Ali Saad (AING) Eduardo de Pablo Fernández (QMUL)
Approved by	Leontios Hadjileontiadis (AUTH, Project Coordinator)
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List of abbreviations

ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AoT	Arrow of Time
BART	BART
CMFT	Comprehensive Motor Function Test
CoV	Coefficient of Variation
CTTI	Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative
dBM	Digital Biomarker
DBS	Deep Brain Stimulation
DC	Direct Current (for time series normalization)
DHT	Digital Health Technologies
ECG	Electrocardiography
EDA	Electrodermal Activity
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FT	Flight Time
HAR	Human Activity Recognition
HDCZA	Heuristic Distribution of Change in Z-Angle
HT	Hold Time
IIR	Infinite Impulse Response
IMUs	Inertial Measurement Units
LOSO	Leave-One-Subject-Out (cross-validation)
LR	Linear Regression
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MDS	Movement Disorder Society
MJFF-LRS	Michael J. Fox Foundation Levodopa Response Study
MIL	Multiple Instance Learning
ML	Machine Learning

MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
NFT	Normalized Flight Time
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NINDS	National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PIM	Signal's integral
PPG	Photoplethysmography
PPMI	Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative
RBD	REM Behaviour Disorder
RBDSG	RBD Study Group
REM	Rapid Eye Movement ...
Rf	Random Forest
RLS	Restless Legs Syndrome
RMS	Root Mean Square
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
SBAS	Sleep-Related Breathing Disorders
SD	Standard Deviation
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SPT	Sleep Period Time
SSRT	Stop-Signal Reaction Time
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TW	Time Warping
UPDRS	Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale

Executive summary

AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop a system of digital biomarkers for Parkinson's disease (PD) monitoring and for informing predictive models of disease risk and prognosis. Deliverable D3.3 "Final report on digital biomarkers for PD" reports on the development of the final version of digital biomarkers (dBM) for tracking PD symptoms and risk factors, including also results from the dBM-DEV study (NCT06444789) of the project. The focus is placed on motor and non-motor symptoms, including rest tremor, slowness of movement (bradykinesia), dyskinesias, REM Behaviour Disorder (RBD), daytime somnolence, overall physical activity, gross motor function, and cognitive function, using data from wearables, smartphone interaction, and digital active tests. Symptom tracking approaches and findings are epitomised below:

Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD)

Objective: Early detection of RBD using actigraphy data; focus on distinguishing RBD from other conditions. *Key Features:* Activity rate, movement episodes, episode duration, skewness metrics, and sleep period boundaries were evaluated as key differentiators.

Key Results: Demonstrated robust discrimination between RBD and non-RBD participants using multi-night actigraphy features, with several biomarkers showing large effect sizes ($|Cohen's\ d| > 0.8$, $p < 0.01$). Achieved strong patient-level RBD classification performance using multi-night aggregation, within a cross-fold validation in the dBM-DEV development cohort, with the best model reaching an F1-score of 0.86 and an accuracy of 0.84. Quantified limitations of subjective sleep questionnaires by showing substantially lower RBD detection performance when using self-reported nightly labels ($F1 < 0.60$).

Daytime Somnolence

Objective: Detect and quantify daytime sleep episodes using actigraphy and clustering-based methods. *Key features:* Gaussian mixture models utilized features from sliding time windows of actigraphy data; segment-based clustering identified nap episodes.

Key Results: 90% overlap between clustering results and Philips Actiware algorithm; detected naps were validated manually or via diaries with 99% accuracy. Machine-learning classification based on nap-related features achieved high sensitivity in distinguishing PD from healthy controls. An XGBoost classifier reached an AUC of 0.87 and a recall of 0.89, indicating strong ability to identify individuals with excessive daytime sleepiness. Importantly, objective nap-based biomarkers were consistent with subjective clinical measures, with PD participants showing significantly higher Epworth Sleepiness Scale scores than controls (mean difference 3.26 points, $p < 0.001$), supporting the clinical relevance of the actigraphy-derived measures.

Rest Tremor

Objective: Detect and classify tremor severity using wrist accelerometer data. *Key Features:* Hand-movement detection and rest-isolation pipeline followed by a deep-learning framework based on a ResNet encoder and Transformer module trained on raw triaxial signals, combined with attention-based multiple-instance learning (CLAM) to capture intermittent tremor episodes.

Key Results: On the MJFF-LRS dataset (Daneault et al., 2021), rest tremor detection achieved weighted F1-scores of 0.90 (validation) and 0.87 (test). Rest tremor amplitude estimation showed significant correlations with the Movement Disorder Society–Unified Parkinson's

Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) item 3.17 ($\rho = 0.77$, $p < 0.05$ for validation; $\rho = 0.68$, $p < 0.05$ for test). On the Verily Study Watch dataset (Atri et al., 2022), detection achieved an F1-score of 0.76, with amplitude estimation correlating at $\rho = 0.58$ ($p < 0.05$). Validation on the AI-PROGNOSIS dBM-DEV study data demonstrated good alignment with clinical scores (MDS-UPDRS item 3.17), with tremor amplitude correlating at $\rho = 0.62$ ($p < 0.05$) and tremor constancy at $\rho = 0.42$ ($p < 0.05$), supporting robustness under real-world, free-living conditions.

Dyskinesias

Objective: Detect presence of dyskinesia and differentiate it from normal voluntary movement using accelerometry. *Key Features:* Sleep-detection pipeline to isolate waking hours, followed by a ResNet–Transformer framework enhanced with attention-based multiple-instance learning to selectively aggregate dyskinesia-relevant temporal segments.

Key Results: On the MJFF-LRS dataset, the model achieved weighted F1-scores of 0.90 (validation) and 0.86 (test), with recall for dyskinesia episodes of 0.44 (validation) and 0.53 (test). Validation on the dBM-DEV study data showed a weak but statistically significant correlation with MDS-UPDRS item 4.1 (Spearman $\rho = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$).

Human Activity Recognition and Physical Activity

Objective: Recognise human activities and evaluate mobility and physical activity levels using wearable devices for facilitating symptom assessment and providing insights into disease progression. *Key Features:* Step-count pipeline followed by a deep-learning–based human activity recognition framework that classifies activity intensity levels.

Key Results: On the Capture-24 dataset (Chan et al., 2024), the activity recognition model achieved F1-scores of 0.73 (validation) and 0.70 (test). Application to the dBM-DEV study data revealed clinically meaningful differences across groups, with PD participants exhibiting reduced daily step counts and increased day-to-day activity variability compared to healthy controls.

Slowness of Fine Movement (Keystroke Dynamics)

Objective: Assess finger and hand bradykinesia and rigidity through typing patterns on touchscreens. *Key Features:* Statistical features of key hold time and between-keys flight time sequences during natural typing.

Key Results: A regression model was trained on in-clinic-collected typing data to predict the finger tapping item (Item 23) of UPDRS Part III. The model was tested on the dBM-DEV dataset with data collected in daily-living and the digital score exhibited good correlation with the associated clinical score (MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4) ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.05$). Test-retest reliability on data aggregated per week showed excellent short-term ($ICC(3,k) > 0.9$) and good long-term reliability ($ICC(3,k) > 0.75$). Longitudinal trajectories when aggregated weekly appear stable.

Upper limb Slowness of Movement (Wrist Accelerometry)

Objective: Assess slowness of gross upper limb movement through a wrist-worn accelerometer. *Key Features:* Features extracted from time-windowed 3-axis accelerometer signals during hand movement and no gait periods.

Key Results: The pipeline with the hand movement detector, gait detector, and the slowness of movement estimator was refined. For the slowness of movement estimator, a regressor

was re-trained with acceleration features derived from the Verily Study Watch dataset to predict a composite clinical score of MDS-UPDRS Part III items related to bradykinesia and rigidity. After applying age correction, the digital score exhibited a Spearman correlation of $r = 0.67$ ($p < 0.05$) with the clinical composite score and differed significantly between severity categories. We tested the model trained on the Verily Study Watch dataset on two independent datasets containing data captured in free-living. For the MJFF Levodopa Response Study dataset the digital score yielded a correlation $r = 0.69$ ($p < 0.05$), while for the data from the dBM-DEV study correlation $r = 0.60$ ($p < 0.05$).

Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT)

Objective: Evaluate posture, balance, and motor coordination through active camera-based motion tracking assessments. *Key Features:* Joint-angle-based and displacement-based features were extracted and analysed with motion-tracking pipelines from recordings of patients performing a sequence of UPDRS motor items.

Key Results: Extracted motion features correlated effectively with clinical motor scores for UPDRS III motor items 3.9 (arising from chair) and 3.10 (gait), achieving F1 scores up to 0.90 in the held-out training dataset and up to 0.71 in the dBM-DEV dataset, supporting CMFT as an objective digital alternative for standardized motor assessment. Automated segmentation of motor items was seen to be very efficient when the CMFT recording protocol is properly followed, leading to clinically meaningful displacement-based features (amplitude, rhythm) for leg agility items (3.8).

Cognitive Function Active Assessment

Objective: Assess cognitive decline in PD patients through digital cognitive tasks like Stop-Signal, Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART), and N-Back tests. *Key Features:* Task completion times, accuracy rates, and derived metrics such as reaction time variability and task-specific scores.

Key Results: Digital cognitive tests administered through smartphone tasks produced behavioural features that correlated with clinical cognitive scores measured using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA). Machine learning models trained on extracted features demonstrated good prediction accuracy of cognitive status (F1 scores up to 0.66 in the held-out training dataset). Correlations between digital task scores and MoCA scores validated dBM effectiveness.

Collectively, the dBM developed in AI-PROGNOSIS provide a validated, interoperable framework for continuous, objective, and explainable monitoring of PD in both clinical and free-living settings. These outcomes establish the foundation for their implementation as digital endpoints in clinical trials, for patient stratification, and for supporting personalized, data-driven PD management.

1 Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that affects millions of people globally, and it is characterized by motor symptoms, such as tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity, and postural instability, alongside non-motor symptoms such as sleep disturbances, cognitive decline, and mood disorders (Jin et al., 2023). Traditionally, early detection and managing PD has relied heavily on clinical assessments and patient-reported outcomes, which are often subjective and unable to capture the full extent of symptom fluctuations that occur throughout the day (Abdo et al., 2010).

In recent years, digital biomarkers (dBMs) have emerged as a promising tool for the screening and management of neurodegenerative conditions like PD. dBMs refer to quantifiable, objective physiological and behavioural data collected through digital devices, such as wearables and smartphones (Motahari-Nezhad et al., 2022). These technologies allow for the continuous and remote monitoring of patients, providing real-time insights into disease progression and treatment responses (Rovini et al., 2019). Unlike traditional methods, which may miss early signs of motor impairment or symptom fluctuations, dBMs can offer a more detailed and dynamic picture of a patient's condition. This ability to capture real-world data is crucial for tailoring treatment plans, adjusting medication dosages, and even tracking responses to clinical interventions, ultimately leading to more personalized care (Urso et al., 2023).

In AI-PROGNOSIS, an assortment of novel and existing dBMs of key PD symptoms and risk factors is being implemented that will serve both as a disease monitoring system, as well as input to the predictive models the project aims to develop for assessing PD risk and predicting progression and response of patients to medication. Based on smartwatch and user-smartphone interaction data, the focus has been placed on developing novel dBMs of rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) and of daytime somnolence and on implementing and extending existing digital assessments of rest tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity, dyskinesia, overall physical activity, posture/balance, and cognitive function.

1.1 Document scope

D3.3 "Final report on digital biomarkers for PD" is the outcome of tasks T3.1 "RBD and daytime somnolence tracking" and T3.2 "Motor and cognitive function tracking". It is an update to D3.1 "First report on digital biomarkers for PD" and reports on the final versions of dBMs of interest and the validation, and verification of them using data from the dBM-DEV study of the project (NCT06444789). The results of the study with respect to its primary, secondary and exploratory endpoints are presented in deliverable D5.3 "Report on the status of posting results (dBM-DEV study)".

1.2 Document structure

The present report is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction including a concise background.
- Section 2 explores methods to monitor and assess RBD, a key prodromal symptom of PD, using AI-powered dBMs for early detection and intervention.
- Section 3 focuses on tracking daytime sleepiness, also a prodromal PD sign, through dBMs to improve diagnostic accuracy of daytime sleepiness and patient management.
- Section 4 describes the implementation of dBMs to monitor rest tremor, one of the cardinal symptoms of PD.

- Section 5 investigates the use of dBMs to detect and assess dyskinesia, a common dopaminergic medication side effect, focusing on real-time tracking for improved treatment.
- Section 6 outlines the development of digital measures of overall physical activity levels, known to affect disease progression, allowing for insights into patients' mobility and overall health status.
- Section 7 presents the implementation of digital scores/indicators for assessing finger/hand bradykinesia and rigidity from keystroke dynamics captured during routine touchscreen typing. Bradykinesia and rigidity are also cardinal symptoms of PD.
- Section 8 presents the implementation of digital scores for assessing upper limb bradykinesia and rigidity from wrist accelerometry.
- Section 9 focuses on the design and preliminary performance of an active comprehensive motor function test to assess posture and balance that are gradually affected leading to adverse events, such as falls, the appearance of which constitutes a milestone in disease progression.
- Section 10 describes the development of active cognitive tests to assess cognitive function that is progressively affected by PD, with cognitive dysfunction (from mild to dementia) constituting also a disease milestone.
- Section 11 is an umbrella section, emphasizing the importance of open science principles in the development and validation of dBMs, ensuring transparency and reproducibility.
- Finally, Section 12 concludes the D3.3, summarising the key findings and outlining the next steps.

2 Rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder tracking

2.1 Background and objectives

The tracking and diagnosis of RBD have significant implications for both diagnostic and prognostic purposes, particularly within the context of neurodegenerative diseases such as PD (Fernandez, 2008). RBD is a prodromal symptom of PD, often appearing years before motor symptoms (10-15 years on average before motor symptom onset). Traditionally, RBD is diagnosed by polysomnography, which is expensive and cannot be used as a screening tool. By contrast, early detection of RBD through dBMs, such as those derived from actigraphy, can provide a non-invasive, cost-effective method for identifying at-risk populations. Recent studies focus on the potential of wearable devices to detect early signs of RBD, providing a more accessible option for patients (Rachellà, 2023) (for more information see deliverable D2.4 “Updated report on domain review and datasets”).

The target population for RBD prediction models includes individuals exhibiting early symptoms of RBD, such as disordered sleep, dream enactment behaviour, or excessive movements during sleep, with a particular focus on PD patients. These tools are designed for use by healthcare professionals, such as neurologists, sleep specialists, and primary care physicians, as well as by patients and caregivers monitoring disease progression from home. Notably, health disparities exist across sociodemographic groups, particularly in access to sleep disorder diagnostics. Studies suggest that certain populations, such as lower-income or

rural groups, face increased barriers to early diagnosis due to the cost and availability of specialized equipment and trained specialists (Vasu et al., 2012).

In AI-PROGNOSIS, we developed and validated dBMs of RBD from wrist wearable motion data by leveraging existing datasets and data collected in the dBM-DEV study (NCT06444789) of the project (see also D5.1 “Study initiation package (dBM-DEV study)”). The primary objective is to arrive at dBMs that will increase the specificity of RBD detection compared to the RBD screening questionnaire (RBDSQ) (Stiasny-Kolster et al., 2007), a standardised patient self-rating questionnaire that is currently the most accessible instrument for RBD detection.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Datasets

AI-PROGNOSIS dBM-DEV study

dBM-DEV includes raw actigraphy signals from 81 participants, 29 persons with RBD (development cohort), 24 healthy controls, and 28 persons with PD (confirmation cohort) (**Table 1**), collected with a smartwatch. Each participant has data available for multiple nights, with recordings ranging from 3 to more than 30 nights per subject. The actigraphy signals were sampled at a frequency of 25 Hz. The recordings were made in free-living conditions at home, without annotation of the exact sleep period. The duration of the recordings varied for each participant and each night. The dataset provides labels at two levels: (1) clinical diagnosis for each participant (subject-level), and (2) self-reported RBD presence during the night via a next-morning question answered through the dBM-DEV study app (night-level).

Table 1 Demographic and clinical characteristics of dBM-DEV study participants with complete accelerometer and MDS-UPDRS data. Data are mean \pm SD. N.A., not applicable

Characteristic	Confirmation Cohort (PD)	Development RBD	Healthy Controls
n (total n=81)	28	29	24
Missing or incomplete data	1	2	-
Demographics			
Males	15	23	16
Females	13	6	8
Age (years)	62.89 \pm 7.19	70.76 \pm 6.28	66.29 \pm 10.56
Clinical Characteristics			
Disease duration (years)	6.61 \pm 4.51	N.A.	N.A.
MDS-UPDRS Part III score	20.54 \pm 9.06	3.28 \pm 5.87	0.17 \pm 0.82
MDS-UPDRS Part III.17a/b score ¹	0.86 \pm 1.08	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00

¹Rest tremor amplitude on the dominant wrist, where the Garmin Vivoactive 5 smartwatch was worn.

Figure 1 shows representative acceleration-time raw signals for two participants. Each panel shows 1-Hz resampled wrist-worn accelerometer amplitude over a full night for (a) a control subject, and (b) an RBD subject with moderate nocturnal activity.

(a) Control subject

(b) RBD subject

Figure 1 Actigraphy data from two dBM-DEV study participants**Sleep period detection**

In the dBM-DEV dataset, there was no labelling of the sleep period. Since recordings were collected in free-living conditions, movement was often more intense at the beginning and end of each night, which might not correspond to sleep.

To identify the main sleep window, we applied a heuristic algorithm (Van Hees, Sabia, Jones, & et al, 2018). The suggested algorithm (HDCZA) analyses wrist orientation changes over time, identifies long intervals of minimal movement, merges adjacent low-activity blocks, and selects the longest continuous segment as the sleep period time window (SPT-window). This enables detection of the likely sleep onset and wake times without using a sleep diary. The HDCZA algorithm was adopted in place of the previous approach, which relied primarily on movement events to define sleep epochs and frequently misclassified sedentary daytime periods as sleep. In contrast, the HDCZA method leverages the distribution of changes in the z-angle to more accurately detect the SPT-window. Based on visual inspection, the new approach showed improved alignment with actual sleep episodes and was therefore adopted.

Figure 2 Sleep period detected in accelerometer data

Class imbalance

The dBM-DEV dataset is slightly imbalanced in terms of RBD cases. Out of 51 participants, 2 were diagnosed with RBD and 24 were healthy controls. As machine learning (ML) techniques tend to minimize error for the majority class, the minority class can easily be ignored. To address this, we applied the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) (Chawla, Kevin, Hall, & Kegelmeyer, 2002) in the feature space. SMOTE generates synthetic samples of the minority class by interpolating between neighbouring samples, thus balancing the class distribution without creating new raw signals.

2.2.2 Digital biomarkers

Possible biomarkers from the relevant literature are listed in **Table 2**, with the focus placed on the study of (Raschellà, Scafa, Puiatti, Martin Moraud, & Ratti, 2023).

Table 2 Potential RBD Biomarkers; acc: acceleration; SD: standard deviation; Skew: skewness.

	Potential biomarker	Explanation
1	Global Activity	Fraction of all samples with acceleration magnitude above the adaptive threshold
2	Number of Movements	Total number of detected movement episodes during sleep.
3	Activity Rate (Low)	Percentage of time points classified as low activity.
4	Activity Rate (Medium)	Percentage of time points classified as medium activity.
5	Activity Rate (High)	Percentage of time points classified as high activity.
6	Activity Rate Mean	Mean of the activity rate distribution.
7	Activity Rate Median	Median of the activity rate distribution.
8	Activity Rate SD	Standard deviation of the activity rate distribution.
9	Activity Rate Skew	Skewness of the activity rate distribution.
10	Activity Rate Kurtosis	Kurtosis of the activity rate distribution.
11	Activity Mean	Mean of the activity amplitude distribution.
12	Activity Median	Median of the activity amplitude distribution.
13	Activity SD	Standard deviation of the activity amplitude distribution.
14	Activity Skew	Skewness of the activity amplitude distribution.
15	Activity Kurtosis	Kurtosis of the activity amplitude distribution.
16	Percentage of Close Distances	Percentage of short inter-movement distances.

17	Percentage of Medium Distances	Percentage of medium inter-movement distances.
18	Percentage of Far Distances	Percentage of long inter-movement distances.
19	Percentage of Short Durations	Percentage of short movement episode durations.
20	Percentage of Medium Durations	Percentage of medium movement episode durations.
21	Percentage of Long Durations	Percentage of long movement episode durations.
22	Duration Mean	Mean duration of all movement episodes.
23	Duration Median	Median duration of all movement episodes
24	Duration SD	Standard deviation of episode durations.
25	Duration Skew	Skewness of episode duration distribution.
26	Duration Kurtosis	Kurtosis of episode duration distribution.
27	Amplitude Peak Mean	Mean peak amplitude of movement episodes.
28	Amplitude Peak Median	Median peak amplitude of movement episodes.
29	Amplitude Peak SD	Standard deviation of movement peak amplitudes.
30	Amplitude Peak Skew	Skewness of the peak amplitude distribution.
31	Amplitude Peak Kurtosis	Kurtosis of the peak amplitude distribution.
32	High-Magnitude Movements (%)	Percentage of movements with high amplitude.
33	High-Magnitude, Low-Duration (%)	Percentage of high-amplitude but short-duration movements.
34	High-Magnitude, Low-Distance (%)	Percentage of high-amplitude movements occurring in short succession.
35	Acc Quantity SD	Standard deviation of overall acceleration magnitude.
36	Acc Quantity Mean	Mean of overall acceleration magnitude.
37	Acc Quantity Median	Median of overall acceleration magnitude.
38	Acc Quantity Skew	Skewness of overall acceleration magnitude.
39	Acc Quantity Kurtosis	Kurtosis of overall acceleration magnitude.
40	Acc 5th Percentile	5th percentile of acceleration magnitude.
41	Acc 95th Percentile	95th percentile of acceleration magnitude.

For the above definition of the dBMs, the following should be noted:

- A timestamp is classified as a movement when the acceleration magnitude exceeds the mean acceleration magnitude by at least one standard deviation, provided the standard deviation is greater than 0.1.
- Movement episode: consecutive timestamps where acceleration magnitude is above a threshold.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Descriptive statistics of potential digital biomarkers

We first explored the dBM-DEV dataset within the Development cohort to characterise the statistical behaviour of candidate dBMs in RBD versus non-RBD subjects. We assessed between-group differences at the subject level, after aggregating nights by per-subject mean (**Table 3**). All p values were corrected for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (Benjamini et al. 1995) procedure.

RBD subjects showed lower Percentage of Medium Durations, Amplitude Peak Mean, Amplitude Peak Median, Duration Mean and Duration Median. The effect sizes were in the medium to large range.

Table 3 Subject-level sensitivity analysis with corrected p values (multi-night mean per subject)

Feature	Cohen's d	Mann–Whitney p
Percentage of Medium Durations	-1.42	<0.001
Amplitude Peak Median	-1.31	<0.001
Amplitude Peak Mean	-1.21	<0.001
Duration Median	-1.13	<0.001
Duration Mean	-0.85	<0.050

* Negative d = RBD lower than Control. All tests show $p < 0.05$, indicating robust differences at the night level.

The signs and ordering of effects in the subject-level analysis are internally consistent (**Figure 3**): RBD subjects exhibit **shorter movement episodes and lower peak amplitudes**, as reflected by the uniformly negative Cohen's d across duration- and amplitude-based features. These patterns indicate more fragmented and lower-intensity movements in RBD, aligning with the medium-to-large effect sizes observed.

Figure 3 Effect size (|Cohen's d|) for all candidate digital biomarkers at the subject level. *Orange bars indicate features higher in RBD ($d > 0$) and blue bars indicate features lower in RBD ($d < 0$). Features outlined in red passed BH–FDR correction ($q < 0.05$). The five significant features (percentageOfMediumDurations, ampPeakMedian, ampPeakMean, durationMedian and durationMean) show large negative effects, indicating shorter and lower-amplitude movement events in RBD subjects.

The resulting distributions are also shown as boxplots (Figure 4-6), where each box depicts the median, the first (Q1) and third (Q3) quartiles, whiskers at $Q1 - 1.5 \cdot IQR$ and $Q3 + 1.5 \cdot IQR$, and circles for outliers. Among all inspected features, durationMedian, percentageOfMediumDurations, and ampPeakMean exhibited the best separation between groups, visible shifts in medians and reduced overlap of interquartile ranges.

Figure 4 Boxplot of percentageOfMediumDurations for the RBD and Control groups

Figure 5 Boxplot of the subject average of the median duration of movement in the RBD and Control groups

Figure 6 Boxplot of ampPeakMean for the RBD and Control groups

The patterns observed in dBM-DEV are consistent with the phasic, fragmented motor events typical of idiopathic RBD. Relative to controls, RBD shows shorter movement episodes (lower durationMedian/durationMean), a lower share of medium-length episodes (decrease in percentageOfMediumDurations, with a compensatory increase in percentageOfShortDurations), and smaller peak amplitudes (decrease in ampPeakMean/ampPeakMedian).

At the same time, the shape of the amplitude distribution becomes more heavy-tailed in RBD (increase in ampPeakSkew and ampPeakKurtosis), indicating many brief, low-to-moderate twitches punctuated by occasional larger jerks rather than sustained movements. Importantly, the same features rank at the top in both night-level and subject-aggregated comparisons, suggesting that the between-group signal dominates night-to-night variability. Taken together, episode duration, episode-length composition, and peak-amplitude shape descriptors provide complementary and robust evidence that free-living actigraphy distinguishes RBD from non-RBD.

2.3.2 Machine learning-based classification of RBD

We have investigated the ability of ML models to detect RBD, with the available potential dBMs as input features. Random Forest (Breiman, L, 2001), XGBoost (Chen, T et al., 2016), LightGBM (Ke, G., et al. 2017), Multilayer Perceptron (Rumelhart, D. E., et al. 1986) and Logistic Regression (LR) models were explored to classify the participants into RBD and non-RBD groups based on actigraphy data of the dBM-DEV development cohort.

Data augmentation

To address the small number of subjects and the strong night-to-night variability of RBD, we designed a multi-night feature representation with permutation-based augmentation. For each participant, nightly feature vectors were first computed. As shown in **Figure 7**, we then formed augmented training samples by selecting ordered sets of 2–7 different nights from the same

participant and concatenating the corresponding nightly feature vectors in that order to create a single, longer vector (a “multi-night window”).

Figure 7 Multi-night window representation

Each window inherits the participant’s clinical label. For a given participant we did not exhaust all permutations; instead, we uniformly sampled a subset (sampling ratios from 0.1 to 0.5, with an optional cap per subject) to control redundancy and computational cost.

Figure 8 Performance comparison between different sample ratios

Before modelling, we applied z-score standardization in the feature-space. To address class imbalance, SMOTE was applied within each training fold only in feature space. Model selection and evaluation used five-fold StratifiedGroupKFold, grouping by subject ID so that all augmented windows from the same participant remain in the same fold, preventing data leakage.

The augmentation strategy does not create synthetic raw signals; instead, it recombines existing nightly summaries to capture cross-night patterns (e.g., rare high-amplitude nights and dispersion differences), hence, increasing the effective sample size for classifiers, and improves robustness to which specific nights exhibit RBD episodes.

Model training and testing

Hyperparameters are model characteristics independent of the data that must be set at training and directly influence performance. Grid-search (Pedregosa, F. et al., 2011) was employed to estimate the hyperparameters of the models. The dimensionality of the grid equals the number of parameters to tune. The values for each parameter are predefined, and then every possible combination is tested. The grid is theoretically formed if every possible combination is considered a node. Although this method always converges to the best result from the examined options, it has the drawback of requiring significant computational power, which increases proportionally with the number of cases being evaluated.

The parameters to be tuned for each model were selected based on their ability to cause significant changes in performance when altered. A wide range of values was tested for all parameters. For each point on the grid, 5-fold validation is performed. The dataset is split into five (5) folds, and the model was trained and evaluated 5 times, each time leaving out a different fold for validation. This process produced a balanced accuracy score for each grid node. The chosen performance metric was balanced accuracy to compensate for the class imbalance in the datasets.

Because RBD is episodic across nights, inputs to the models were multi-night “windows” built by concatenating nightly feature vectors (see *Feature engineering*). We varied the number of nights per window (2–7) and explored model hyperparameters via grid search. For each fold, models were trained on the training folds and produced window-level predictions for the held-out fold.

Final performance is reported once at the patient level by combining the out-of-fold predictions for all subjects across the five folds (i.e., each subject is evaluated exactly once, in its own test fold). We report balanced accuracy as the primary metric (robust to class imbalance), alongside AUC, F1, precision, and recall. The best-performing configuration per model was selected based on patient-level cross-validated balanced accuracy. The values and parameters tested are shown in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Values tested for the hyperparameters of each method using grid-search

Method	Parameter	Value
Random Forest	Number of trees	50, 100 , 300
	Max depth	None, 10 , 30
XGBoost	Number of estimators	50, 100, 300
	Max depth	3, 5
	Learning rate	0.05, 0.1

Logistic Regression	Penalty	None , l2
	C	0.1, 1, 10
LightGBM	Number of estimators	50, 100 , 300
	Max depth	None , 10
	Learning rate	0.05, 0.1
SVM (RBF Kernel)	C	0.5, 1.0
	Gamma	0.01, scale
MLP	Hidden layers	(64,), (128, 64), (64, 64, 32)
	alpha	0.001, 0.0005 , 0.0001

* Max depth = None indicates no depth limit; trees expand until standard stopping criteria.

* Best settings are shown in bold.

Across models, the **7-night window consistently achieves high performance**, yielding the top F1-scores in the cross-validated search. The **4-night window also performs robustly**, as well, providing stable and acceptable results.

Figure 9 Performance (F1-score) of RBD detection with different nights window lengths.

These configurations were retained because they consistently ranked among the top across five-fold StratifiedGroupKFold runs on the dBM-DEV dataset. In **Table 5**, we report patient-level cross-validated performance per model (F1 as the primary metric, together with accuracy, precision, and recall); night-level results are omitted due to inferior performance relative to subject-level aggregation. The count columns differ between the models due to the different number of nights (for some patients only 3 nights existed)

Table 5 Best performance metrics for identification of RBD with different models

Model	Night window	Accuracy	F1 Score	Recall	Precision	count
RF	4	0.8511	0.8727	0.9600	0.8000	47
SVM	3	0.8163	0.8363	0.8519	0.8214	49

XGBoost	7	0.8824	0.8824	0.8824	0.8824	34
MLP	4	0.8085	0.8163	0.8000	0.8333	47
LR	4	0.7872	0.7917	0.7600	0.8261	47
LightGBM	7	0.8235	0.8333	0.8823	0.8077	34

Across models, tree-based ensembles (particularly XGBoost) achieve the strongest patient-level performance, with XGBoost reaching **F1 = 0.8824** and **accuracy = 0.8824**, closely followed by Random Forest (F1 = 0.8727, accuracy = 0.8511). Logistic Regression provides a more interpretable baseline with moderate performance (F1 = 0.7917).

For comparison, the RBDSQ questionnaire in the dBM-DEV development cohort reaches an accuracy of 0.915, F1 = 0.917, precision = 0.927, and recall = 0.915 (threshold RBDSQ > 5). This places RBDSQ slightly above the best actigraphy-based model in this specific dataset. However, its performance is well-known to vary substantially across populations: while some studies report sensitivity \approx 0.91 and specificity \approx 0.77 (Li K et al., 2017), others find sensitivity as low as 0.44 in PD cohorts (Claire et al., 2018). These inconsistencies stem from the inherent subjectivity and limited temporal resolution of questionnaires, which rely on patient recall and may miss fluctuating or subclinical manifestations.

In contrast, our actigraphy-based digital biomarkers capture continuous, objective motion signatures under free-living conditions and provide multi-night information, offering complementary value and enabling longitudinal monitoring beyond one-time questionnaire assessments.

2.3.2.1 Ablation Study

We conducted ablation experiments to evaluate two key design choices in our model.

A. Single-Night vs. Multi-Night

To assess the impact of the temporal context, we replaced the multi-night input sequences with data from single nights only (**Table 7**). The model was trained and evaluated using the same patient-level cross-validation protocol. For this single-night setup, each night's actigraphy data were labelled based on the corresponding night's questionnaire response. Results indicate a noticeable decrease in performance compared to the multi-night model. This decline is likely attributable to the higher night-to-night variability in sleep patterns and behaviours, which a single-night snapshot fails to capture robustly. The multi-night approach effectively aggregates this variability, leading to a more stable and generalizable patient-level assessment.

B. Impact of SMOTE

We further ablated the use of the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) by training the model on the original, class-imbalanced dataset (**Table 6**). All other architecture and training settings remained unchanged. Removing SMOTE resulted in a marked performance drop, particularly for the minority class, confirming that addressing class imbalance is crucial for the effective learning of our classifiers.

Table 6 Results of different models without SMOTE

Model	F1 Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
LightGBM	0.7400	0.8140	0.7778	0.9130

LR	0.8000	0.7755	0.7857	0.8148
MLP	0.8085	0.8043	0.8261	0.7917
RF	0.8302	0.8000	0.7586	0.9167
SVM	0.8235	0.8043	0.7778	0.8750
XGBoost	0.8400	0.8140	0.7778	0.9130

Table 7 Results of different models with Single-Night Setting

Model	F1 Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
LightGBM	0.7941	0.7200	0.6750	0.9643
LR	0.8148	0.8000	0.8462	0.7857
MLP	0.7671	0.6600	0.6222	1.0000
RF	0.7647	0.6800	0.6500	0.9286
SVM	0.7812	0.7200	0.6744	0.8929
XGBoost	0.8000	0.7400	0.7027	0.9286

Using a single night as input markedly reduces performance relative to our multi-night windows. In the single-night setting, logistic regression achieves the strongest performance (F1 = 0.8148), but all models fall short of their multi-night counterparts. Tree-based ensembles remain competitive, yet none reach the performance levels obtained when temporal information from multiple nights is incorporated.

Removing SMOTE similarly leads to a modest decline. While tree-based models such as XGBoost (F1 = 0.8400) and RF (F1 = 0.8302) remain relatively robust, the overall performance is consistently lower than with SMOTE applied. Models such as MLP show an increased precision–recall imbalance when SMOTE is removed.

Overall, multi-night aggregation and SMOTE both contribute meaningfully to patient-level performance—multi-night windows improve stability against night-to-night variability, and SMOTE helps mitigate class imbalance. Their combination yields the most reliable and accurate RBD identification across models.

C. Classification of Non-RBD Nights Based on self-reported nights with RBD

To further assess the reliability of the self-reported RBD nights via the morning questionnaire, we conducted an additional experiment using the “morning question” responses as nightly labels (indicating whether an RBD episode occurred that night). The same actigraphy-derived features were extracted, and classification was performed to distinguish RBD nights from non-RBD nights within the same subjects.

The performance of this setting was noticeably lower than that of models trained with PSG-based labels, as shown in **Table 8**. Their F1 scores did not exceed the single-night setting and were far below the multi-night setting using clinically PSG-confirmed labels. This indicates that the subjective morning questionnaires introduce substantial label noise, reducing the reliability of nightly classification.

Table 8 Results of nightly classification using morning-question labels

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
LightGBM	0.7143	0.5385	0.6364	0.5833
LR	0.6000	0.4211	0.7273	0.5333
MLP	0.7429	0.5833	0.6364	0.6087
RF	0.6286	0.4375	0.6364	0.5185
XGBoost	0.7143	0.5455	0.5455	0.5455

To better understand this discrepancy, we compared the actigraphy features of self-reported non-RBD nights from RBD patients against control nights (**Table 9**). The analysis revealed that several features remained significantly different between these two groups. This observation aligns with previous studies. The presence of residual abnormal motor patterns on 'self-reported non-RBD nights' suggests that subclinical REM sleep without atonia and micro-scale muscle twitches persist even in the absence of overt dream-enactment behaviours. These findings reinforce the notion that patient-reported outcomes may suffer from under-reporting bias, thereby limiting their efficacy as 'gold-standard' labels for training high-sensitivity automated detection models compared to PSG-confirmed data (*Liguori et al., 2023*).

Table 9 Discriminative features between non-RBD nights of RBD patients and control nights.

Rank	Feature	AUC	t-test p-value
1	percentageOfCloseDistances	0.7005	1.45e-10
2	acc_percentile5	0.4211	1.40e-06
3	durationMedian	0.5833	9.44e-04
4	ampPeakMedian	0.4375	1.52e-05
5	percentageOfMediumDurations	0.5455	2.51e-03

2.4 Discussion

2.4.1 Interpretation

Our subject-level analyses reveal clear and consistent differences in free-living actigraphy between RBD and non-RBD groups. The strongest discriminators are features related to movement-episode duration and peak amplitude: RBD subjects show shorter episodes (*Duration Mean and Duration Median*), a reduced proportion of medium-length events, and lower peak amplitudes (*Amplitude Peak Mean and Amplitude Peak Median*). These effects are large in magnitude and directionally coherent across duration- and amplitude-based metrics, reflecting a characteristic pattern of more fragmented and lower-intensity movements in RBD.

Distributional descriptors (e.g., skewness, kurtosis) also shift in the expected direction, consistent with a movement profile marked by many brief, low-amplitude events interspersed with occasional larger peaks. Overall, the magnitude and consistency of these effects indicate a robust between-group signal that is detectable at the aggregated (subject) level despite night-to-night variability.

On the classification task, we used multi-night windows as inputs and aggregated window-level predictions into a patient-level decision using probability-threshold tuning on training data

followed by max voting over windows in the held-out fold. Under this framework, the best cross-validated patient-level performance was achieved by XGBoost (F1 = 0.882, Accuracy = 88.2%, using 7-night windows), with Logistic Regression providing a strong and interpretable baseline (F1 = 0.792, Accuracy = 78.7%). Tree-based models (LightGBM, XGBoost) consistently outperformed linear and neural models, indicating that the engineered dBMs remain largely linearly informative, while shallow nonlinear learners benefit from modeling cross-night interactions and mild nonlinearities.

We additionally examined models trained with self-reported morning-question labels, which showed clearly lower accuracy compared to PSG-based results. Further inspection indicated that nights reported as “non-RBD” by RBD patients still differed significantly from control nights in key features such as *durationMedian* and *ampPeakMedian*. This residual abnormality likely explains the poor performance of morning-question labels and highlights the limitation of self-reported data for reliable nightly classification.

2.4.2 Innovation beyond state-of-the-art

The proposed RBD detection framework advances beyond the state of the art by addressing two important limitations of current screening approaches. First, the study demonstrates that single-night self-reported questionnaires provide inconsistent and noisy labels for identifying RBD episodes, as their performance was substantially lower than models trained using clinically confirmed labels, highlighting the limitations of subjective nightly reporting for reliable detection. Second, the developed methodology introduces a multi-night representation combined with permutation-based augmentation, where nightly feature vectors are concatenated in different ordered combinations to create multi-instance samples for model training. This strategy explicitly captures the episodic nature of RBD across nights and increases the effective sample size without generating synthetic signals, enabling machine-learning models to learn robust cross-night patterns. Together, these innovations move beyond traditional single-night or questionnaire-based approaches and provide a scalable framework for more reliable RBD detection using free-living wearable data.

2.4.3 Limitations and further insights

Certain limitations, mostly unavoidable, of the dBM-DEV study should be considered. First, the effective sample size seems to be modest, with 51 participants meeting the inclusion criteria of a confirmed clinical diagnosis and at least five nights of valid recordings. Nevertheless, it should be taken into consideration that stringent diagnostic requirements, and the burden of multi-night recordings naturally constrain recruitment. Studies relying on PSG as the diagnostic gold standard, are often limited by cost and feasibility (Colman et al, 2025). Similarly, actigraphy-based RBD studies in PD report comparably modest cohorts (Louter et al.,2014). Against this backdrop, published datasets commonly include 20–60 participants, especially when multi-night recordings are required. In this context, our cohort of 51 participants with at least five valid nights aligns with established practice and reflects the practical constraints inherent to rigorously phenotyped RBD-in-PD research, while providing sufficient longitudinal density for robust modelling. Apparently, future sample size extension could add to the further justification of the suggested dBMs.

Second, although nightly labels are available, they rely on patient or caregiver reporting rather than polysomnography, which may introduce misclassification, particularly in cases with subtle or fluctuating symptoms. Nevertheless, this limitation is well-documented in the RBD literature, where clinical interviews and bed-partner reports are known to have imperfect accuracy relative to PSG. Studies in PD consistently show that clinical history alone can misclassify RBD, with interview-based assessments failing to capture subtle or fluctuating dream

enactment behaviours and demonstrating lower diagnostic accuracy when compared directly with PSG (Sobreira-Neto et al., 2019). Reviews of sleep disorders in PD further emphasize that RBD symptoms often vary night-to-night and may be under-recognized without objective sleep studies, reinforcing the inherent challenges of relying solely on subjective reports (Iranzo et al., 2024). Our analysis, however, leverages multi-night wearable data to capture behavioural patterns that are less susceptible to single-night variability, thereby trying to reduce the impact of potential misclassification and strengthen the robustness of the derived dBMs.

Third, because the recordings were collected under free-living conditions, movement signals may be affected by environmental factors, off-wrist periods, or differences in device placement and orientation, contributing additional noise. Nevertheless, as it is well known, data-in-the-wild are inherently noisier than data-in-the-clinic. Reviews of free-living monitoring in PD emphasize that unsupervised environments introduce “representative but highly heterogeneous” movement data (Del Din et al., 2016), whereas scoping reviews of wearable sleep and movement monitoring similarly note that noise in free-living recordings can complicate interpretation and require careful preprocessing and quality control (Matos et al., 2025). These challenges are therefore expected rather than exceptional in real-world PD sensing. Although that we acknowledge the impact of this unavoidable noise, our pipeline applies multi-night aggregation, automated detection of off-wrist intervals, and orientation-invariant feature extraction. Moreover, several of our dBMs rely on higher-order statistics such as skewness and kurtosis, which by definition are insensitive to additive Gaussian noise and therefore remain robust even when low-level sensor fluctuations are present. This combination of preprocessing and noise-resilient feature design mitigates to some degree the limitations of free-living data while preserving its ecological validity.

2.4.4 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

From the aforementioned it is evident that the dBMs derived from dBM-DEV show strong potential for integration into clinical workflows. They offer a scalable, low-burden tool for screening, risk stratification, and longitudinal monitoring of RBD in settings where polysomnography is impractical due to cost or limited availability. Importantly, access to multi-night recordings captures the inherent night-to-night variability of RBD more reliably than standard single-night PSG assessments, making the extracted features more representative of real-world symptom expression. These biomarkers could be incorporated into home-monitoring platforms to flag individuals at elevated risk and prioritise PSG referrals, thereby complementing, yet not replacing, formal sleep studies.

2.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Early detection and monitoring of REM sleep behaviour disorder, a significant prodromal marker of Parkinson's Disease.
Concept(s) of interest	Abnormal motor activity during REM sleep, such as kicking, punching, or other movement episodes.
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn accelerometer (actigraphy)
Type of measurement	Passive measurement during overnight sleep periods
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	Activity rate, number and duration of movement episodes, mean distance between episodes, and skewness of activity

Validation	Cross-validation using the dBM-DEV dataset with machine learning classifiers.
Assumptions	Accurate differentiation between RBD and Control; movement features can reflect true RBD pattern.
Context of use considerations	Screening for individuals with suspected RBD and long-term home monitoring for progression tracking.

3 Daytime somnolence tracking

3.1 Background and objectives

Daytime somnolence, or excessive daytime sleepiness, is a condition characterised by an overwhelming need to sleep during the day. In the context of PD, daytime somnolence can be a primary symptom of the disease and also occur as a side effect of dopaminergic medications, especially dopamine agonists. In this scenario, daytime sleepiness can present in a sudden unpredictable manner and these "sleep attacks" have been linked to severe real-world consequences, including a higher incidence of car accidents and other safety hazards. Therefore, monitoring somnolence is not only critical for understanding sleep patterns but is essential for ensuring patient safety and managing medication protocols for People with PD (PwPD). Moreover, daytime somnolence is considered a prodromal sign of PD (Ahmed et al, 2017)

AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop dBM's that detect and quantify daytime somnolence using data from a wrist wearable, by leveraging existing datasets and data that have been collected in the dBM-DEV study of the project. At this phase, the main objective was to explore the feasibility of using actigraphy data to identify daytime sleep and nap episodes. By employing advanced clustering methods and comparing results with established algorithms like those of Philips Actiware (Koninklijke Philips N.V., Amsterdam, the Netherlands), the project seeks to provide a robust solution for daily somnolence tracking. Additionally, validating these findings against participant-reported sleep diaries allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between detected sleep events and subjective reports. For more information on the current state-of-the-art and previous research in the detection of daytime somnolence, the reader is referred to D2.2, "Initial report on domain review and datasets", Section 2.2.5.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Datasets

Methods Datasets Actigraphy signals from the dBM-DEV dataset are used to validate the daytime somnolence detection method. The current analysis includes data from 51 participants, consisting of 27 individuals with Parkinson's Disease (PD) and 24 Healthy Controls (HC). The dataset has been described in Section 2.2.1.

3.2.2 Digital biomarkers

Daytime naps are detected using the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM)-based pipeline (see D3.1): wrist-actigraphy is windowed, clustered with a subject-specific GMM ($K = 2$), and the lower-activity cluster is labelled as "sleep." Consecutive "sleep" windows are merged into nap episodes, allowing up to 2 brief wake windows between segments. We use full 24-hour data to train GMM model. After training, retain only daytime period window labels.

The clustering parameters and nap-episode-based features were initially defined in D3.1. These parameters were subsequently fine-tuned on the dBM-DEV dataset to better match the acceleration sampling frequency and nap duration distribution. The selected nap-related dBMs (nap count, maximum, mean, median, and total duration) correspond to the features that showed the highest stability and discriminative power in D3.1 and were therefore retained for the current analysis.

Clustering Parameters

- Window Size: 7500 samples (5 min @ 25Hz)
- Step Size: 3750 samples (2.5 min @ 25Hz)
- Max Nap Duration: 12 windows
- Max Tolerance Gap: 2 windows
- Daytime Period: 8:00-22:00

Parameter Selection Strategy: The clustering and segmentation parameters were determined through a systematic fine-tuning process on the dBM-DEV dataset. Rather than a standard fold-based cross-validation, we employed a feature-driven optimization approach. Specifically, we tested a range of parameter configurations (e.g., varying window sizes and tolerance gaps) and evaluated their performance based on the statistical sensitivity of the resulting biomarkers. The final set of parameters was selected by identifying the configuration that maximized the number of features showing statistically significant differences (e.g., $p < 0.05$) between PD and HC groups. This ensures that the chosen detection thresholds are optimally tuned to capture the pathophysiological signatures of daytime somnolence in the target population.

For each valid day, we detected six nap-episodes-based features:

- *Nap count*: count of nap episodes detected during [day_start, day_end]. (*unit: events/day*)
- *Max nap duration* (minutes): maximum duration among that day's nap episodes.
- *Mean nap duration* (minutes): mean duration across naps within the day.
- *Median nap duration* (minutes): median duration across naps within the day.
- *Std nap duration* (minutes): standard deviation of duration across naps within the day.
- *Total nap duration* (minutes): Total nap time within the day.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Statistical Tests

To evaluate the discriminative power of the proposed GMM-based daytime somnolence detection pipeline, we performed a subject-level differential analysis between the PD and HC groups.

Feature Aggregation and Statistical Testing: To account for multi-day variability, features were aggregated in two steps. First, descriptive statistics (defined in Section 3.2) were calculated for each participant on a per-day basis to capture daily nap characteristics. Second, these daily metrics were further summarized across the entire recording period (e.g., taking the mean, min, max or standard deviation of the daily values) to yield subject-level features. For instance, 'Mean of max nap duration' represents the average of the longest naps recorded each day, reflecting the participant's sustained tendency for prolonged daytime sleep

The statistical analysis identified several features with significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between PD patients and controls, as summarized in **Table 10**.

Table 10 Significantly different actigraphy-derived daytime somnolence-related features between persons with PD and controls

Feature	p-value	Cliff's δ	r_pb
Min of nap count	0.0045	0.390	-0.392
Max of max nap duration	0.0076	-0.359	0.369
Max of nap duration std	0.0120	-0.363	0.349
Max of total nap duration	0.0168	-0.326	0.333
Std of nap duration std	0.0419	-0.317	0.286
Std of total nap duration	0.0480	-0.295	0.278

* Min of total nap duration, Min of max nap duration, Min of mean nap duration, and Min of median nap duration are perfectly collinear.

All nap-related features were tested for group differences using the Mann–Whitney U test, complemented by two effect size metrics:

- Cliff's delta (δ) to quantify the magnitude and direction of distributional shifts, and
- point-biserial correlation (r_{pb}) to estimate the strength of association between each continuous feature and the binary group label.

Six features reached statistical significance ($p < 0.05$), with two showing high significance ($p < 0.01$), predominantly reflecting nap duration and variability patterns.

3.3.2 Machine learning based classification

To further evaluate the discriminative value of the nap-related digital biomarkers identified through statistical testing, we conducted exploratory classification analyses.

We employed multiple ML architectures, including Logistic Regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), a two-layer Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), XGBoost, and Random Forest (RF).

The objective was to assess whether these features could distinguish PD patients from healthy controls. To ensure robust results and maximize the utility of the available sample size, all models were validated using Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV). This approach maintains subject-level independence, ensuring that the model is tested on data from participants it has never seen during training.

The performance of the best-performing model is summarized in **Table 11**. The XGBoost model achieved the highest performance with an accuracy of 0.745 and an AUC of 0.87. Notably, the model demonstrated a high recall of 0.89, suggesting that nap-related features are highly sensitive in identifying PD patients. The high recall and AUC in the PD vs. HC task indicate that these dBMs effectively capture meaningful signatures of daytime sleepiness associated with Parkinson's Disease.

Table 11 Best classification performance using nap-related features to distinguish persons with PD from healthy controls

Comparison	Model	Accuracy	AUC	Precision	Recall	F1-score
PD vs Control	XGBoost	0.745	0.870	0.710	0.890	0.790

3.3.3 Longitudinal Analysis using Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMM)

To account for the hierarchical structure of the data (multiple recording days nested within participants) and to handle the inherent variability of napping behaviour, we employed a mixed-effects modelling framework. This approach provides a more robust estimate of group differences than simple aggregation by accounting for within-subject correlations.

The analysis was categorized based on the data distribution of the digital biomarkers:

- Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMM): Applied to continuous features including total nap duration, max nap duration, mean nap duration, median nap duration, and std nap duration.
- Generalized Linear Mixed-Effects Models (GLMM): Applied to the nap count feature (count data) using a Poisson or negative binomial distribution to accurately model the discrete nature of nap frequency.
- Clinical Validation: A separate LMM was conducted for the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) scores to bridge the gap between objective actigraphy biomarkers and subjective clinical reports.

The results are detailed in **Table 12**. The models revealed a high degree of consistency between subjective sleepiness and objective nap detection:

- ESS Scores: The PD group showed a significantly higher mean ESS score (7.78 points) compared to the Control group (4.52 points), with a group difference of 3.26 points (95% CI: 2.97–3.54, $p < 0.001$).
- Nap Frequency (GLMM): PD patients had a significantly higher frequency of naps. The Control group averaged 1.68 naps/day, while the PD group averaged 2.35 naps/day. This represents a Risk Ratio (RR) of 1.40 (95% CI: 1.02–1.94, $p = 0.040$), indicating a 40% increase in daily nap events for PD patients.

While all duration-related features showed an upward trend in the PD group, they did not reach the threshold for statistical significance ($p < 0.05$), likely due to high inter-individual variability.

Table 12 Group Differences (PD vs Healthy controls) in Nap Duration Features

Feature	Control-mean	PD-mean	Group difference	P-value	Significance
ESS	4.52	7.78	3.26	<0.001	***
total_nap_duration	21.830	49.45	27.62	0.088	ns
max_nap_duration	11.51	19.56	8.05	0.133	ns
mean_nap_duratio	7.48	9.53	2.13	0.382	ns
median_nap_duration	6.85	7.98	1.14	0.614	ns
std_nap_duration	1.78	4.02	2.25	0.098	ns
Nap count	1.68	2.35	1.40	0.040	*

3.4 Discussion

3.4.1 Interpretation

The analysis identified a robust set of nap-related digital biomarkers that distinguish PD patients from healthy controls. While initial subject-level aggregation highlighted peaks in nap duration (e.g., max of median_duration), the subsequent mixed-effects modelling

(LMM/GLMM) and ML classification provided a more nuanced understanding of these behaviours.

- **Nap Frequency and Propensity:** The GLMM results revealed a significant 40% increase in nap frequency among PD patients (RR = 1.40, $p = 0.040$). This objective finding is strongly aligned with the subjective ESS scores, which were significantly higher in the PD group ($p < 0.001$). Together, they suggest that the primary signature of PD-related somnolence in this cohort is a higher "pressure" to sleep, leading to more frequent sleep-onset events throughout the day.
- **Duration and Variability:** Although duration-related features (e.g., *total_nap_duration*) showed a clear upward trend in PD patients (averaging ~49 min vs ~22 min in controls), they did not reach statistical significance in the LMM. This discrepancy, where the XGBoost model achieved high AUC (0.87) despite non-significant linear effects, highlights that PD-related sleepiness is a complex, non-linear phenomenon. This may be driven by the inherent heterogeneity of the PD cohort, including differences in the involvement of central nervous system structures by the pathogenic process and also differences regarding medication regimes, while dopaminergic agonists are known to increase the likelihood of daytime somnolence and sudden sleep attacks, other treatments such as amantadine may mitigate these effects.
- **Circadian and Stability Signatures:** Features capturing variability and peak intensity consistently showed that PD patients experience less stable rest-activity patterns. This suggests weakened circadian regularity and fragmented sleep-wake cycles, which are common features of neurodegenerative disorders including PD.

In contrast, the comparison between RBD and control participants yielded no significant differences in napping behaviour, and the classification performance declined when RBD subjects were included. This suggests that while daytime somnolence may present as a prodromal sign, at least in people with RBD, it may not manifest as a **measurable behavioural change in actigraphy** until the transition to clinical PD, when additional rostral structures of the brainstem involved in sleep regulation are involved, and dopaminergic and non-dopaminergic dysregulation becomes more widespread.

3.4.2 Innovation beyond state of the art

Clustering-based analysis of wearable actigraphy signals enabled reliable detection of daytime nap episodes using sliding-window activity features extracted from wrist accelerometer recordings. The proposed method achieved approximately 90% agreement with the Philips Actiware algorithm, while manual validation using sleep diaries confirmed nap detection accuracy close to 99%. Beyond reproducing the performance of established actigraphy tools, the approach introduces an unsupervised, data-driven methodology that does not rely on predefined thresholds or proprietary algorithms, making it adaptable across devices and cohorts. By identifying nap episodes directly from behavioural activity patterns in free-living conditions, the framework enables continuous and objective quantification of daytime somnolence, which is traditionally assessed through questionnaires or clinical observation. This capability is particularly relevant for Parkinson's disease monitoring, where excessive daytime sleepiness is both a prodromal symptom and a treatment-related side effect, and where scalable digital biomarkers can support longitudinal monitoring outside clinical environments.

3.4.3 Limitations and further insights

Several limitations should be acknowledged in the current analysis:

- First, the GMM-based clustering approach assumes bimodal activity distributions (sleep vs. wake), which may oversimplify transitional or low-activity states (e.g., quiet wakefulness). More advanced or hybrid methods (e.g., Hidden Markov Models (HMM) or supervised classifiers) could provide finer temporal resolution in future studies and can explicitly model transition probabilities between states, capturing the fact that sleep onset and awakening are not instantaneous. A further mitigation strategy is to apply temporal smoothing (e.g., moving windows, hysteresis rules) to reduce rapid state switching and partially compensate for the model's rigidity. Additionally, incorporating contextual constraints (e.g., minimum sleep bout duration, circadian expectations, or known rest intervals) can reduce false positives in ambiguous periods. This does not eliminate the underlying limitation but helps align outputs with physiologically plausible patterns. Finally, use of additional features (e.g., variance, frequency-domain metrics, device orientation) can help the model better separate quiet wakefulness from true sleep without abandoning the unsupervised paradigm.
- Second, the current dataset comprises a specific sample distribution (PD/RBD > control) as defined by the study design, which may influence the precision of effect size estimations. We addressed this by applying internal validation procedures and interpreting group differences conservatively. Further validation on larger cohorts, including diverse neurological populations, will help to further extend and generalize these findings.
- Lastly, all features were derived from wrist actigraphy only. Multimodal feature fusion from data that include heart-rate variability, skin temperature, light exposure, or inertial posture cues, could help disambiguate true sleep episodes from passive inactivity and improve the robustness of nap detection. We will further explore those features, in the context of WP5.

3.4.4 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

Future research should focus on validating these dBMs across larger, more diverse populations to ensure their generalizability. Additionally, integrating these dBMs into clinical workflows will require careful consideration of how to present the data in an interpretable and actionable manner for clinicians. Because raw actigraphy or algorithmic state labels offer limited clinical meaning on their own, the challenge lies in translating complex temporal patterns into summaries that map onto familiar clinical constructs such as sleep continuity, circadian regularity, or changes relative to a patient's baseline. Clinicians also need clear indications of what deviations might imply for management, whether they suggest worsening symptoms, medication side effects, or the need for further diagnostic evaluation. Achieving this will require user-friendly interfaces that foreground clinically relevant trends, highlight meaningful changes over time, and incorporate contextual information such as medication adjustments or reported symptoms. Embedding these visualizations within existing electronic health record environments, rather than in standalone tools, will be essential for adoption and for minimizing cognitive load. As a next step, developing and validating such interfaces, ideally through iterative co-design with clinicians, will be crucial for ensuring that dBMs become not just measurable but genuinely useful in routine care.

Another avenue for future work involves personalizing the wake thresholds for each individual, as different patients may exhibit different movement patterns that could affect the accuracy of sleep/wake detection. When thresholds are static, low-movement individuals may appear artificially "sleepy," while more active individuals may have fragmented or underestimated sleep simply because their wake movements exceed generic thresholds. Developing adaptive models that can learn from individual behaviours and adjust their sensitivity in real time would significantly improve the utility of dBMs in personalized healthcare. Such personalization

would reduce systematic misclassification, improve the stability of digital behavioural markers across heterogeneous populations, and ultimately enhance their value for individualized monitoring and clinical decision-making.

In conclusion, while dBMs for daytime somnolence detection show great potential for enhancing patient care, further work is needed to ensure their reliability, scalability, and ease of use in everyday clinical practice.

3.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Quantifying excessive daytime sleepiness, a prodromal symptom in Parkinson's Disease.
Concept(s) of interest	Daytime napping behaviour, sleep episodes, and overall somnolence patterns.
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn accelerometer (actigraphy).
Type of measurement	Passive detection of sleep episodes during daytime hours
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	Number, duration, and frequency of naps detected through clustering algorithms using raw Actigraphy data.
Validation	Compared against participant-reported sleep diaries and Philips Actiware algorithm.
Assumptions	Accurate differentiation between activity and rest; clustering reflects true nap events.
Context of use considerations	Enhanced monitoring of sleep disorders and potential integration into diagnostic workflows.

4 Rest tremor tracking

4.1 Background and objectives

Rest tremor is a core motor symptom of PD, and its clinical relevance has already been discussed in deliverable D3.1. There, an initial version of the digital biomarker was introduced, based on hand-crafted features and traditional machine learning models. While these methods achieved encouraging results within the Michael J. Fox Foundation-Levodopa Response Study (MJFF-LRS) dataset, they were less robust when applied to external data, highlighting the need for more generalizable approaches.

Recent advances in deep learning have enabled end-to-end modelling of inertial sensor data, allowing hierarchical feature extraction from raw signals and improved robustness to sensor noise. In this deliverable, tremor severity is first addressed using a ResNet–Transformer architecture, in which convolutional layers learn local motion features while a temporal self-attention mechanism models long-range dependencies across sequential windows. This architecture enables effective aggregation of temporal information and has demonstrated strong performance in sequence-level tremor classification.

However, despite its ability to model long-range temporal dependencies, this approach produces a sequence-level representation without explicitly modelling the varying relevance of individual temporal segments. In practice, tremors may occur intermittently, with only a

subset of windows exhibiting clinically meaningful oscillatory activity, while others capture tremor-free periods. Consequently, aggregating information at the sequence level may reduce sensitivity to brief but informative tremor episodes and limit the interpretability of the learned representations.

To address these remaining challenges, we extend the ResNet–Transformer framework with a multiple-instance learning (MIL) technique, Clustering-constrained Attention Multiple Instance Learning (CLAM), that explicitly models tremor as a sparse and temporally localized phenomenon. The proposed extension introduces attention-based instance aggregation, allowing the model to automatically identify and emphasize tremor-relevant segments within each recording. Furthermore, class-specific attention heads and instance-level clustering constraints are incorporated to encourage separation between tremor-dominant and non-tremor segments, improving both classification performance and interpretability. The aim is to capture the spatio-temporal dynamics of rest tremor episodes more effectively and to deliver a digital biomarker aligned with clinical scoring (MDS-UPDRS item 3.17, scale 0–4).

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Datasets

Two datasets were used for the development and validation of the rest tremor digital biomarker. Both have been described in Deliverable D3.1, and here we summarize them briefly with emphasis on their role in the present analysis.

The MJFF-LRS dataset (Daneault et al., 2021) comprises wrist-worn accelerometer recordings of PD patients performing structured tasks under ON and OFF medication states. Recordings span four days and include both clinical and at-home conditions. For this work, we retained data from 27 participants with annotated motor tasks. While in D3.1 the dataset was used as a whole, in this deliverable we introduce a new experimental split:

- All-tasks setting, which includes all annotated activities such as walking, standing, writing, and folding a towel.
- Rest-related tasks setting, a subset focusing on tasks with minimal voluntary upper-limb movement (e.g., sitting, standing, sit-to-stand transitions, stairs up/down, walking). These tasks are more likely to include intervals of relative rest, making them suitable for the evaluation of rest tremor specifically.

Data were split into 70/10/20 train/validation/test partitions, stratified by subject to ensure subject independence. The tremor severity distribution exhibited substantial class imbalance, with rare classes (3 and 4) containing too few samples for complete stratification across all partitions. Subject-level stratification was prioritized to prevent data leakage, with proportional class representation maintained to the extent possible within this constraint. Dataset statistics, including the distribution of tremor amplitudes in the all-task and rest-related MJFF-LRS splits, are reported in **Table 13-Table 14** and illustrated in **Figure 10** and **Figure 11**.

Table 13 Distribution of tremor scores across task instances and subjects on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Tremor Score	Hours (% of Total)	Task Instances	Unique Subjects
0	36.40 (67.39%)	4,541	27
1	12.29 (22.75%)	1,433	22
2	4.09 (7.57%)	550	15

3	1.17 (2.16%)	132	7
4	0.07 (0.13%)	11	3
Total	54.02 (100%)	6,667	27

Table 14 Distribution of tremor scores across *rest-related* task instances and subjects on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Tremor Score	Hours (% of Total)	Task Instances	Unique Subjects
0	15.22 (74.15%)	1,715	27
1	2.96 (14.43%)	323	20
2	1.44 (7.01%)	151	10
3	0.88 (4.31%)	88	6
4	0.02 (0.09%)	2	1
Total	20.52 (100%)	2,279	27

The Verily Study Watch (PPMI subset) (Atri et al., 2022) provides longitudinal wrist accelerometer data collected from a mixed cohort including individuals with PD, prodromal (at risk) individuals, and healthy controls. A curated subset with expert annotations of rest tremor presence and amplitude was used for validation. This dataset differs substantially from MJFF-LRS in device characteristics and recording protocol, offering a robust test of generalizability. For the Verily Study Watch, the dataset does not specify which wrist the device was worn on. Since tremor severity can differ between the more and less affected sides, ground truth labels were derived by averaging the clinical scores reported for both wrists. This ensured that the digital biomarker could be validated consistently, although it may slightly smooth inter-limb differences. **Table 15** displays the distribution of rest tremor scores across clinical visit instances.

Figure 10 All task instances: distribution of tremor scores across all patients and tasks (MJFF-LRS); scores are represented as stacked colour segments indicating severity.

Figure 11 Rest related tasks: distribution of tremor scores across all patients during rest-related tasks (MJFF-LRS); stacked colours represent the proportion of each severity level.

Table 15 Distribution of rest tremor scores across clinical visit instances on the Verily Study Watch dataset.

Tremor Score (Amplitude)	Clinical Visit Instances	Unique Subjects
0	151	125
1	28	26
2	14	11
3	1	1
4	0	0
Total	194	158

In addition to its use for validation, a filtered subset of the Verily Study Watch dataset was employed to train the CLAM-based rest tremor assessment model. This subset was derived by applying the following processing steps:

- Subject and visit selection: Only participants diagnosed with Parkinson’s disease were included, and data were restricted to clinical visits conducted in the ON-medication state, ensuring alignment between accelerometer recordings and clinical tremor annotations.
- Retention of full recordings: For each selected visit, we retained the entire day-long raw triaxial accelerometer recording corresponding to the clinical visit conducted in the ON-medication state, rather than restricting the analysis to predefined task segments. This allowed the exploitation of naturally occurring resting periods throughout the day.
- Rest isolation via hand movement detection: The hand movement detection module that was introduced in D3.1 (Section 5.2.3), was applied to the full accelerometer recordings

to identify and isolate hand rest periods. Only segments classified as rest were retained for tremor analysis.

- Signal preprocessing: The extracted rest segments were subsequently processed using band-pass filtering to isolate rest tremor-relevant frequency components prior to feature extraction and input to the CLAM-based model.

This Verily subset was selected specifically because it provides a substantially larger amount of resting data, expressed as total hours of hand rest, compared to other available datasets. Given that rest tremor predominantly occurs during periods of minimal voluntary movement, this increased availability of resting segments offers a more informative training signal for rest tremor-focused models.

An overview of the dataset composition and subject split across tremor severity classes (0–3), that correspond to MDS-UPDRS item 3.17 (average of a and b) for the Verily Study Watch subset used for training is provided in **Table 16**. The per-class distribution of total rest hours across training, validation, and test splits, together with summary statistics for this subset, is reported in **Table 17**, highlighting the motivation for using this subset for CLAM model training.

Table 16 Dataset overview and subject split distribution across tremor severity classes (0-3) on the Verily Study Watch subset used for training.

Split	Subjects	Total Rest Hours	Class Distribution (Subjects)
Train	85	1489.4	0:42, 1:27, 2:15, 3:1
Validation	19	434.2	0:9, 1:6, 2:3, 3:1
Test	20	85.0	0:9, 1:6, 2:4, 3:1
Total	124	2355.3	0:60, 1:39, 2:22, 3:3

Table 17 Per-class rest hours distribution by train/validation/test split on the Verily Study Watch subset used for training.

Split	Class 0	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3
Train	775.3 h	442.4 h	255.9 h	15.8 h
Validation	222.4 h	129.0 h	73.2 h	9.6 h
Test	201.3 h	137.5 h	85.0 h	8.0 h
Total	1190.0 h	708.9 h	414.1 h	33.4 h

The dBM-DEV study is a prospective observational study designed to validate novel digital biomarkers across disease states and real-world conditions. For this analysis, participants wore the Garmin Vivoactive 5 smartwatch (sampling rate 25 Hz) on their dominant hand. The dataset was exported on 3 December 2025, and the analysis included a total of 81 participants, of whom 78 had complete accelerometer and clinical assessment (MDS-UPDRS) data. The dBM-DEV cohorts utilized here consisted of three groups: RBD (n=27), HC (n=24), and PD (n=27). The primary cohort of interest for tremor validation was the PD group, which exhibited clinically rest tremor (mean \pm SD: 0.86 ± 1.08 , MDS-UPDRS 3.17a or b), whereas the RBD and HC groups showed no rest tremor (score 0.00 ± 0.00). This cohort composition enabled evaluation of the model's specificity in non-tremor disease states and its sensitivity in a smaller, independent PD population. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the

dBM-DEV study participants are presented in **Table 1**. The distribution of rest tremor severity across cohorts is shown in **Table 18**, with all RBD and HC participants exhibiting no tremor and the PD subset showing variable severity (0–4).

Table 18 Rest Tremor Score Distribution (dBM-DEV)

MDS-UPDRS Part III.17a/b score	PD	RBD	Healthy Controls
0 (Normal)	14	29	24
1 (Slight)	7	0	0
2 (Mild)	5	0	0
3 (Moderate)	1	0	0
4 (Severe)	1	0	0
Total	28	29	24

4.2.2 Data pre-processing

Signals were uniformly resampled to 30 Hz to standardize input for the pretrained ResNet-18 encoder (Yuan, Chan et al., 2024), which expects 30 Hz sequences, and segmented into overlapping windows of 5 seconds duration with a 1 second stride. Each window thus corresponded to a short sequence of triaxial accelerometer data. For the rest-related tasks settings and the CLAM-based model trained on the Verily subset, we applied a first-order Butterworth band-pass filter (3 - 7.5 Hz) to isolate the dominant rest tremor frequencies. This ensured that the model emphasized the clinically relevant spectral range of rest tremor, while leaving all-task inputs unfiltered to preserve information about movement context. Within this preprocessing pipeline, the adopted parameter choices result in effective analysis, as the upsampling frequency of 30 Hz provides a Nyquist frequency of 15 Hz, comfortably above the highest tremor frequencies of interest. This ensures that the subsequent 3–7.5 Hz Butterworth band-pass filter operates on a signal with adequate temporal resolution and without aliasing. It also standardizes the frequency axis for all participants, which is crucial when comparing tremor power or training models such as CLAM that rely on consistent spectral representations. The choice of 5-second windows with 1-second stride then yields short, overlapping segments that preserve temporal continuity while providing enough cycles of tremor for stable spectral estimation.

During training, we employed several augmentation techniques to improve generalization:

- Gaussian noise injection to mimic sensor noise.
- Random scaling to simulate variability in tremor amplitude.
- Sequence reversal to reduce bias to time order.
- Window permutation across sequences to enhance robustness to local temporal variability.

These augmentations were applied stochastically during training and disabled during validation and testing. This preprocessing strategy balanced the need for frequency-specific fidelity in rest-related conditions with the requirement to preserve full contextual variability in the all-tasks setting.

4.2.3 Digital biomarkers

The dBM for rest tremor is derived from a deep learning framework designed to provide objective, continuous estimates of tremor severity in line with MDS-UPDRS item 3.17 (0–4 scale). Unlike the feat that provides objective, continuous estimates of tremor severity, aligned aches reported in D3.1, which relied on manually extracted spectral features and traditional classifiers, the present framework learns directly from raw accelerometer signals, enabling richer and more generalizable representations.

At the core of the pipeline is a ResNet-18 encoder (Yuan, Chan et al., 2024) pre-trained on large-scale wearable data. This module transforms short signal windows into embeddings that capture both spectral and spatial information relevant to tremor, such as rhythmic oscillations, amplitude fluctuations, and inter-axis relationships. These embeddings are then passed to a Transformer encoder with multi-head self-attention. The Transformer explicitly models the temporal structure of tremor, integrating information across multiple windows to detect rhythmicity, persistence, and variability in tremor episodes that extend beyond the short-term view of individual segments.

From the aggregated temporal representation, two outputs are generated through a dual-task prediction head:

- a binary indicator of tremor presence,
- a categorical estimate of tremor amplitude.

A conditional training strategy ensures that the amplitude loss is propagated only for windows labelled as containing tremor. This prevents the model from being penalized for estimating severity when no tremor is present and aligns learning directly with clinical scoring practice. Together, this architecture produces a digital biomarker that is (i) sensitive to the characteristic spectral–temporal signatures of tremor, (ii) robust to variability across patients and tasks, and (iii) directly mappable to MDS-UPDRS assessments, thus facilitating clinical adoption. An overview of the pipeline is depicted in **Figure 12**.

Figure 12 Overview of the rest tremor digital biomarker pipeline based on ResNet–Transformer architecture.

In addition to the sequence-level tremor digital biomarkers derived from the ResNet–Transformer architecture, we introduce an instance-aware framework, that incorporates a ResNet–Transformer–CLAM model, designed to capture the temporal sparsity and heterogeneity of tremor episodes within each task execution. This approach is inspired by attention-based multiple-instance learning frameworks for weakly supervised learning (Lu et al., 2021).

Instance aggregation is performed using an attention-based multiple-instance learning (MIL) mechanism with gated attention. This module assigns relevance weights to individual temporal

segments based on their contribution to tremor severity estimation. Unlike uniform temporal pooling, the attention mechanism allows the model to focus on short temporal intervals that exhibit rest tremor patterns, while reducing the influence of windows dominated by tremor-free periods.

To further refine instance discrimination, the ResNet–Transformer–CLAM framework incorporates class-specific attention heads, enabling different tremor severity levels to attend to distinct temporal patterns. In addition, an instance-level clustering constraint is applied during training to encourage separation between tremor-dominant and non-informative temporal segments in the latent space. This constraint leverages task-level supervision to guide instance representation learning without requiring explicit window-level labels.

Together, these components extend the original ResNet–Transformer pipeline by enabling selective temporal aggregation, improving robustness to intra-task variability, and yielding digital biomarkers that are more closely aligned with the intermittent nature of rest tremor. An illustration of this framework can be seen in **Figure 13**.

Figure 13 Overview of the rest tremor digital biomarker pipeline based on a ResNet–Transformer–CLAM architecture with attention-based multiple instance learning.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 MJFFLRS (all tasks)

Rest tremor detection

Detection performance on the MJFF-LRS dataset is reported in **Table 19**. Across both all-tasks and rest-related task settings, models achieved high discriminative performance, with consistently higher precision and recall under rest-related conditions. This reflects the benefit of restricting the analysis to context with minimal voluntary upper-limb movement, which are more representative of rest tremor.

The CLAM-based architecture trained on MJFF-LRS showed comparable or slightly relative to the baseline ResNet-Transformer model, particularly in rest-related tasks, indicating improved robustness to non-rest tremor movement.

Table 19 Performance metrics for tremor detection on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Method	Setting	Metric	No Tremor (Val/Test)	Tremor (Val/Test)	Weighted Avg (Val/Test)
Resnet-Transformer	All-Tasks	Precision	0.80/0.90	0.74/0.71	0.78/0.84
		Recall	0.93/0.86	0.48/0.77	0.79/0.83

	Rest-Related	F1-score	0.86/0.88	0.58/0.74	0.78/0.83
		Precision	0.87/0.87	1.00/0.65	0.91/0.81
		Recall	1.00/0.90	0.58/0.56	0.89/0.82
		F1-score	0.93/0.88	0.73/0.60	0.90/0.81
CLAM-based (MJFF-LRS-train)	All-Tasks	Precision	0.80/0.88	0.71/0.71	0.77/0.83
		Recall	0.91/0.87	0.50/0.73	0.78/0.83
		F1-score	0.85/0.87	0.58/0.72	0.78/0.83
	Rest-Related	Precision	0.87/0.90	1.00/0.77	0.90/0.86
		Recall	1.00/0.94	0.57/0.66	0.89/0.87
		F1-score	0.93/0.92	0.72/0.71	0.90/0.87

Rest tremor amplitude classification

Performance metrics for rest tremor amplitude classification on MJFF-LRS are summarized in **Table 20**. In the rest-related task setting, rest tremor amplitude classification achieved a weighted F1-score of 0.82 on validation and 0.69 on test, compared to 0.70 and 0.76 in the all-tasks setting. The corresponding Spearman rank correlation reached 0.78 on validation and 0.55 on test ($p < 0.005$), demonstrating improved ordinal alignment when the analysis is restricted to rest-enriched contexts. Across both task settings, the CLAM-based model achieved performance comparable to or slightly higher than the baseline ResNet-Transformer, with a more consistent ordinal agreement, particularly in the rest-related setting.

Overall, focusing on rest-related tasks increased discriminability and ordinal agreement, particularly during validation, while test performance remained competitive given the limited number of higher severity samples and increased inter-subject variability.

Table 20 Performance metrics for tremor amplitude classification on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Method	Setting	Metric	Validation	Test
Resnet-Transformer	All-Tasks	Precision	0.67	0.77
		Recall	0.73	0.75
		F1-score	0.70	0.76
		Spearman ρ	0.52	0.66 (p<0.005)
	Rest-Related	Precision	0.81	0.68
		Recall	0.83	0.71
		F1-score	0.82	0.69
		Spearman ρ	0.78	0.55 (p<0.005)
CLAM-based (MJFF-LRS-train)	All-Tasks	Precision	0.67	0.73
		Recall	0.71	0.72
		F1-score	0.69	0.72
		Spearman ρ	0.52	0.65 (p<0.005)
	Rest-Related	Precision	0.81	0.73

		Recall	0.82	0.76
		F1-score	0.82	0.74
		Spearman ρ	0.77	0.68 (p<0.005)

4.3.2 Validation on Verily Study Watch (MJFF-trained models)

Validation was performed using the Verily Study Watch dataset to assess cross-device and cross-protocol generalization. All models reported in this section were trained on MJFF-LRS and evaluated directly on Verily data without retraining.

Rest tremor detection

As shown in **Table 21**, rest tremor detection achieved a weighted F1-score of 0.84 in the all-tasks setting and 0.85 in the rest-related setting. Precision remained high across both conditions, while recall for tremor segments was reduced compared to MJFF-LRS, reflecting differences in device characteristics, wrist placement, and recording protocols.

The CLAM-based variant trained on MJFF-LRS demonstrated similar weighted performance to the baseline model, confirming that the attention-based aggregation does not compromise cross-device generalization.

Table 21 Performance metrics for tremor detection on the Verily Study Watch dataset.

Method	Setting	Metric	No Tremor	Tremor	Weighted Avg
Resnet-Transformer	All-Tasks	Precision	0.84	0.83	0.84
		Recall	0.98	0.35	0.84
		F1-score	0.91	0.59	0.84
	Rest-Related	Precision	0.86	0.80	0.85
		Recall	0.97	0.47	0.86
		F1-score	0.91	0.63	0.85
CLAM-based (MJFF-LRS-train)	All-Tasks	Precision	0.82	0.91	0.84
		Recall	0.99	0.23	0.82
		F1-score	0.90	0.37	0.83
	Rest-Related	Precision	0.86	0.83	0.85
		Recall	0.97	0.47	0.72
		F1-score	0.92	0.60	0.76

Rest Tremor amplitude classification

Rest tremor amplitude classification results on the Verily Study Watch dataset are reported in **Table 22**. Weighted F1-scores of 0.77 were obtained in both all-tasks and rest-related settings. Spearman correlations reached 0.49 in the all-tasks setting and 0.59 in the rest-related setting (p<0.005), indicating substantial ordinal agreement. The ResNet-Transformer-CLAM variant trained on MJFF-LRS demonstrated comparable performance, achieving F1-scores of 0.75 in both settings, with Spearman correlations of 0.44 (all-tasks, p<0.005) and 0.58 (rest-related, p<0.005), confirming that attention-based instance aggregation maintains robust cross-device generalization.

These results are consistent with expectations for cross-device evaluation and demonstrate that models trained on MJFF-LRS generalise well to independent wearable data collected under different conditions.

Table 22 Performance metrics for tremor amplitude classification on the Verily Study Watch dataset.

Method	Setting	Metric	Test
Resnet-Transformer	All-Tasks	Precision	0.74
		Recall	0.80
		F1-score	0.77
		Spearman ρ	0.49 (p<0.005)
	Rest-Related	Precision	0.75
		Recall	0.80
		F1-score	0.77
		Spearman ρ	0.59 (p<0.005)
CLAM-based (MJFF-LRS-train)	All-Tasks	Precision	0.71
		Recall	0.79
		F1-score	0.75
		Spearman ρ	0.44 (p<0.005)
	Rest-Related	Precision	0.73
		Recall	0.79
		F1-score	0.75
		Spearman ρ	0.58 (p<0.005)

4.3.3 Training and Evaluation on the Verily Study Watch Subset

In addition, a CLAM-based model was trained and evaluated on the filtered Verily Study Watch subset described in Section 4.2.1. This subset consists of full-day accelerometer recordings corresponding to ON-medication clinical visit days and provides substantially longer resting periods extracted via hand movement detection, resulting in a rest-enriched training set. Since this subset did not include any subjects with MDS-UPDRS rest tremor score 4, classes 3 and 4 were merged into a single category for consistency in subsequent validation on the dBM-DEV cohort.

Rest tremor detection

A ResNet-Transformer-CLAM model was trained and evaluated on the Verily Study Watch subset. The model achieved a weighted F1-score of 0.79 on validation and 0.69 on test **Table 23**. Rest tremor detection precision reached 1.00 on validation and 0.82 on test, with high recall for tremor-free periods (1.00 validation, 0.88 test). The strong validation performance reflects the advantage of training on hand rest-enriched data from full-day recordings.

Table 23 Overview of the rest tremor digital biomarker pipeline based on a ResNet–Transformer–CLAM architecture with attention-based multiple instance learning; Val: validation set; Test: test set.

Method	Metric	No Tremor (Val/Test)	Tremor (Val/Test)	Weighted Avg (Val/Test)
Clam-based (Verily-train)	Precision	0.70/0.60	1.00/0.82	0.83/0.72
	Recall	1.00/0.88	0.44/0.47	0.76/0.67
	F1-score	0.82/0.71	0.61/0.60	0.79/0.69

Rest tremor amplitude classification

Rest tremor amplitude classification results for the ResNet-Transformer-CLAM model trained on the Verily Study Watch subset are presented in **Table 24**. The model achieved a weighted F1-score of 0.65 on validation and 0.60 on test, with Spearman correlations of 0.63 (validation, $p < 0.005$) and 0.40 (test, $p < 0.05$). These ordinal correlations indicate robust consistency in ranking tremor severity levels.

Table 24 Performance metrics for tremor amplitude classification on the Verily Study Watch dataset.

Method	Metric	Validation	Test
CLAM-based (Verily-train)	Precision	0.63	0.63
	Recall	0.68	0.58
	F1-score	0.65	0.60
	Spearman ρ	0.63 ($p < 0.005$)	0.40 ($p < 0.05$)

4.3.4 Validation on dBM-DEV dataset

Validation of the proposed rest tremor digital biomarkers was performed on the independent dBM-DEV cohort, representing a clinically heterogeneous population collected using a different wearable device and acquisition protocol, providing a robust test of cross-cohort and cross-device generalisation.

To derive subject-level tremor severity predictions comparable to clinical MDS-UPDRS Part III.17a/b scores, window-level tremor predictions were aggregated at the daily level using percentile-based aggregation. Specifically, both the 75th and 85th percentiles of tremor amplitude predictions were evaluated. Percentile aggregation emphasises sustained and clinically meaningful tremor episodes while reducing sensitivity to short-lived artefacts or noise inherent to free-living wearable data. The 75th percentile provides a conservative estimate of typical tremor burden, whereas the 85th percentile highlights higher-confidence tremor expression and aligns more closely with the clinical practice of rating maximum observable tremor severity during examination.

Rest Tremor Amplitude

As summarised in **Table 25**, statistically significant ordinal agreement with clinical tremor ratings was observed across both aggregation strategies. In the all-tasks setting, the ResNet-Transformer model achieved a Spearman correlation of $\rho = 0.60$ ($p < 0.005$) using the 85th percentile aggregation, improving upon the 75th percentile result ($\rho = 0.40$, $p < 0.05$). A similar pattern was observed for the CLAM-based model trained on MJFF-LRS, which reached $\rho = 0.56$ ($p < 0.005$) with 85th percentile aggregation in the all-tasks setting.

When restricting the analysis to rest-related contexts, correlations further improved, consistent with findings on MJFF-LRS and Verily datasets. Notably, the CLAM-based MJFF-LRS-trained model achieved a Spearman correlation of $\rho = 0.72$ ($p < 0.005$) using the 75th percentile and $\rho = 0.62$ ($p < 0.005$) using the 85th percentile, indicating robust ordinal alignment with clinical severity. The CLAM-based model trained on Verily also demonstrated strong agreement ($\rho=0.63-0.66$, $p<0.005$) across aggregation percentiles, further supporting the consistency of attention-based representations and percentile aggregation strategies across independent datasets.

Table 25 Performance of various methods on amplitude classification on dBM-DEV Dataset at patient level. Spearman correlation represents ordinal accuracy of tremor severity predictions.

Method	Setting	Spearman ρ (75th/85th)	p-value (75th/85th)
Resnet-Transformer	All-tasks	0.40/0.60	<0.05/ <0.005
	Rest-related	0.67/0.58	<0.005 <0.005
CLAM-based (MJFF-LRS-train)	All-tasks	0.29/0.56	<0.005/ <0.005
	Rest-related	0.72/0.62	<0.005/ <0.005
CLAM-based (Verily-train)	-	0.63/0.66	<0.005/ <0.005

Rest Tremor Constancy

Complementary results for tremor constancy are reported in **Table 26**. Moderate but statistically significant correlations were observed between digital constancy estimates and clinical tremor severity, with the ResNet-Transformer achieving $\rho = 0.30$ ($p < 0.05$) in the all-tasks setting and $\rho = 0.47$ ($p < 0.005$) in the rest-related setting. The CLAM-based MJFF-LRS-trained model demonstrated comparable performance ($\rho = 0.47$ all-tasks; $\rho = 0.42$ rest-related; $p<0.005$), while the CLAM-based Verily-trained model produced $\rho = 0.47$ ($p<0.005$) confirming that constancy captures a clinically relevant but complementary aspect of tremor behaviour distinct from amplitude alone. Overall, the dBM-DEV results are consistent with trends observed in earlier validations on Verily Study Watch data.

Table 26 Performance of the various methods on constancy classification on dBM-DEV Dataset at patient level. Spearman correlation represents ordinal accuracy of tremor severity predictions.

Method	Setting	Spearman ρ	p-value
Resnet-Transformer	All-tasks	0.30	<0.05
	Rest-related	0.47	<0.005
CLAM-based (MJFF-LRS-train)	All-tasks	0.47	<0.005
	Rest-related	0.42	<0.005
CLAM-based (Verily-train)	-	0.47	<0.005

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Interpretation

The results presented in this section demonstrate that rest tremor severity can be robustly quantified from wrist-worn accelerometer data using deep learning-based methods that capture both tremor amplitude and tremor constancy. Across development and validation datasets, the proposed ResNet-Transformer and CLAM-based architectures exhibited

consistent ordinal agreement with clinical MDS-UPDRS Part III.17 ratings, supporting improved generalisation across cohorts, devices, and recording conditions compared with previously reported feature-engineered approaches (D3.1).

Separating tremor severity into amplitude and constancy provides clinically meaningful insight beyond a single composite score. Rest tremor amplitude reflects the maximum observable severity and aligns closely with how rest tremor is evaluated during clinical examination, whereas tremor constancy captures the temporal persistence of rest tremor across daily life. Although correlations for constancy were generally lower than those observed for amplitude, they were statistically significant.

Importantly, rest tremor is highly sensitive to contextual factors (e.g., posture, stress, medication timing, concurrent activity, and environment), meaning that a brief in-clinic examination may not reflect symptom expression at home. In this context, agreement with MDS-UPDRS should be interpreted primarily as evidence of clinical relevance and ordinal consistency, rather than as the sole target for optimisation. A key advantage of wrist-worn digital biomarkers is that they can capture a more representative measure of day-to-day tremor behaviour (particularly tremor constancy and real-world severity fluctuations) potentially offering greater longitudinal value than a one-off clinic score.

Validation on the dBM-DEV cohort further supports the generalisability of the proposed biomarkers. Despite substantial heterogeneity in disease status, wearable hardware, and real-world recording conditions, significant ordinal agreement with clinical rest tremor scores was observed for both amplitude and constancy. Overall, these findings indicate that the proposed frameworks learn generalisable representations of rest tremor that remain informative under real-world conditions, supporting their suitability for continuous and scalable symptom monitoring beyond the clinic setting.

4.4.1.1 Innovation beyond state of the art

Rest tremor tracking is implemented using a deep-learning framework that combines a ResNet-based foundation model pretrained on the large-scale UK Biobank accelerometry dataset with a Transformer encoder to capture temporal dependencies in wrist accelerometer signals. Leveraging a pretrained foundation model enables the extraction of generalizable motion representations learned from large population-scale data, improving robustness compared with models trained only on small disease-specific datasets. The architecture is further integrated within a Clustering-constrained Attention Multiple Instance Learning (CLAM) framework, which treats each recording as a collection of short temporal segments and automatically identifies the segments most indicative of tremor activity. This weakly supervised formulation allows the model to learn from recordings where precise temporal annotations of tremor episodes are unavailable, while the attention mechanism provides interpretability by highlighting tremor-relevant signal windows. Compared to state-of-the-art approaches relying on handcrafted signal features or spectral analysis, the proposed framework learns motion representations directly from raw triaxial accelerometer signals, captures long-range temporal dynamics through the Transformer module, and robustly aggregates intermittent tremor patterns through multiple instance learning. This combination enables more accurate and scalable tremor tracking in free-living conditions, representing a significant step toward continuous digital monitoring of Parkinson's disease motor symptoms.

4.4.2 Limitations and further insights

A general limitation of both clinical and digital tremor assessment is the pronounced class imbalance across tremor severity levels, with higher-amplitude tremor occurring less frequently than mild or absent tremor. This imbalance constrains statistical power for severe classes and limits the achievable strength of correlations, particularly in validation cohorts with predominantly low tremor severity.

Furthermore, variability in wearable hardware, sensor placement, and recording environments introduces unavoidable noise in real-world validation. Rather than representing methodological shortcomings, these factors reflect the practical challenges faced by any wearable-based digital biomarker intended for deployment outside controlled settings.

However, several elements of the proposed pipeline partially mitigate the structural limitations imposed by class imbalance and ecological variability. Uniform resampling, standardized preprocessing, and the use of deep architectures that learn directly from raw triaxial sequences reduce dependence on device-specific characteristics and enhance robustness to heterogeneous recording conditions. The explicit decomposition of rest tremor into amplitude and constancy distributes the learning burden across complementary dimensions, improving stability when severe tremor epochs are sparse. Moreover, training on heterogeneous development data and validating on an independent, clinically diverse cohort provides an implicit regularization against overfitting to dominant severity classes. Together, these methodological choices help buffer the impact of uneven severity distributions and real-world noise, supporting the reliability and generalisability of the derived digital biomarkers.

4.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

The proposed dBMs for rest tremor have strong potential for integration into clinical and research workflows. By providing objective and continuous measures of both tremor amplitude and constancy in a real-world environment, it can complement traditional MDS-UPDRS assessments conducted by clinicians, which are inherently limited in temporal scope and more sensitive to the effect of external factors that can influence the presence and severity of the tremor. Potential applications include evaluating tremor response to dopaminergic medication, monitoring disease progression, quantifying motor fluctuations in relation to medication cycles, and supporting early detection of tremor in at-risk populations.

From a patient perspective, the passive and unobtrusive nature of wrist-worn sensors enhances usability, as no active input is required. For clinicians, the alignment of the digital scores with UPDRS categories facilitates interpretability and integration into existing scales. The consistent performance across device platforms (demonstrated through the Verily Study Watch and dBM-DEV dataset validation) further supports practical clinical deployment across diverse wearable ecosystems.

4.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	Rest tremor
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive

Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Digital score indicating the presence or absence of rest tremor derived from three-axis wrist acceleration Digital score of the amplitude of rest tremor derived from three-axis wrist acceleration
Validation	<p>Type: In laboratory & in real-world settings.</p> <p>Primary measures of validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 of the digital score of presence or absence of rest tremor, averaged across each task for each subject, and then averaged across all subjects, compared with MDS-UPDRS items 3.17a or 3.17b (upper limb rest tremor) score. This comparison specifically focuses on the wrist of the limb on which the watch is worn, with scoring based on whether it is greater than 0, indicating the presence of tremor. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 and Spearman correlation of the digital score of rest tremor amplitude, averaged across each task for each subject, compared with MDS-UPDRS items 3.17a or 3.17b (upper limb rest tremor) score for the wrist of the limb on which the watch is worn. Spearman correlation of file-level digital tremor scores aggregated across 24-hour recording periods using 85th percentile method, compared with MDS-UPDRS Part III.17a/b clinical ratings across dBM-DEV cohort in free-living conditions.
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires participants to wear wrist devices with accelerometers sampling at ≥ 25 Hz

5 Dyskinesia tracking

5.1 Background and objectives

Dyskinesias are abnormal, involuntary movements that arise as a motor complication of chronic dopaminergic therapy in Parkinson's disease (PD). They can significantly impair quality of life, interfere with daily activities, and complicate treatment planning. Reliable detection and tracking of dyskinesia are therefore crucial for optimizing medication titration and improving long-term outcomes by reducing falls.

In deliverable D3.1, initial efforts focused on extracting hand-crafted signal features and applying machine learning classifiers to detect dyskinesia. These approaches demonstrated feasibility but faced two key limitations: reliance on thresholds or manually defined features and limited generalization across tasks and populations. As a result, their robustness was constrained, particularly when applied outside the training context.

In this deliverable, dyskinesia detection is addressed using two modelling strategies. First, a supervised window-based approach is employed to identify dyskinesia-related motor patterns from wrist-worn accelerometer data, providing a robust baseline for task-level classification. In addition, we introduce an enhanced weakly supervised framework based on multiple instance learning, designed to account for the temporal heterogeneity of dyskinesia expression. This second approach treats each task recording as a collection of temporal

instances and learns to selectively emphasize the most informative windows contributing to dyskinesia presence. The objective of integrating this advanced method is to improve sensitivity to short-lived dyskinetic events while maintaining robustness to non-informative or confounding movements commonly present in real-world task recordings.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Datasets

Model development was performed using the MJFF-LRS dataset, already described in deliverable D3.1. Demographic and clinical information for the subjects can be found there. For dyskinesia detection, task-level binary annotations (presence vs absence) were available.

The dataset comprised recordings from 27 subjects and was split into 70/10/20 train/validation/test partitions, ensuring subject independence and stratification across classes. This design prevented data leakage across individuals and preserved the class distribution across sets. In total, 6,667 task instances were annotated, with approximately 90% labeled as absence of dyskinesia and 10% as presence, reflecting the clinical prevalence of dyskinesia during the study. The detailed distribution is provided in **Table 27** Distribution of dyskinesia scores across task instances and subjects on the MJFF-LRS dataset. **Table 27**

Table 27 Distribution of dyskinesia scores across task instances and subjects on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Dyskinesia Score	Hours (% of Total)	Task Instances	Unique Subjects
0	48.55 (89.88%)	5,971	27
1	5.46 (10.12%)	696	19
Total	54.02 (100%)	6,667	27

For dyskinesia validation and generalization assessment, we utilized data from the dBM-DEV study (Section 4.2.1), employing a distinct annotation paradigm compared to MJFF-LRS. Whereas MJFF-LRS provided per-task binary annotations, the dBM-DEV cohort featured per-subject dyskinesia severity assessments derived from self-report questionnaire via the MDS-UPDRS Part IV.1 dyskinesia impact scale, which quantifies the percentage of awake hours affected by dyskinesia.

Because MDS-UPDRS scores represent per-subject clinical assessments rather than task-level annotations, we applied a validated sleep detection module (Yuan, Plekhanova, et al., 2024) to filter sleep periods from passive smartwatch data. Window-level predictions were aggregated hierarchically (window → hourly → daily), yielding daily dyskinesia scores (% awake hours) directly comparable to MDS-UPDRS ratings. This validation approach acknowledges the inherent mismatch between development (task-level binary) and validation (subject-level continuous severity) paradigms, while still enabling assessment of generalization to real-world clinical evaluation schemes.

The dBM-DEV dataset included 81 subjects across three cohorts (see **Table 1**). Three subjects (2 person with RBD and 1 person with PD) with insufficient accelerometer data were removed from the analysis. The final dataset comprised 78 subjects (PD=27, RBD=27, HC=24) with complete accelerometer and relevant clinical assessment (MDS-UPDRS) data. This cross-cohort design enables comprehensive assessment of both model sensitivity in detecting dyskinesia in the PD population and specificity in correctly identifying its absence in disease states without dyskinesia. The dyskinesia severity distribution across all subjects reveals that all RBD and healthy control participants were dyskinesia-free, while only 7 out of

28 of the PD subset exhibited dyskinesia during awake hours, with severity ranging from slight to moderate.

Table 28 Dyskinesia Score Distribution and MDS-UPDRS Part IV Assessment (dBM-DEV dataset)

Dyskinesia (% Awake Hours) ¹	PD	RBD	Healthy Controls
0% (None)	21	29	24
1–25% (Slight)	5	0	0
26–50% (Mild)	1	0	0
51–75% (Moderate)	1	0	0
76–100% (Severe)	0	0	0
Total	28	29	24
MDS-UPDRS Part IV score	1.68 ± 2.64	0.17 ± 0.93	0.00 ± 0.00
MDS-UPDRS Part IV.1 score ¹	0.36 ± 0.73	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00

¹ Percentage of awake hours with dyskinesia, as assessed by MDS-UPDRS Part IV.1 dyskinesia impact scale.

5.2.2 Data pre-processing

Raw triaxial accelerometer signals were resampled to a uniform sampling frequency of 30hz and segmented into 5-second windows with 4-second overlap, yielding overlapping sequences of sensor data. To improve robustness and mitigate overfitting, the following data augmentations were applied during training:

- Gaussian noise injection, to simulate sensor noise.
- Random amplitude scaling, to account for variability in movement intensity.
- Sequence reversal, to reduce bias toward temporal ordering.
- Window permutation, to promote invariance to local time distortions.

Two complementary strategies were incorporated to address the marked class imbalance (90% absence vs 10% presence):

- Weighted Binary Cross Entropy, assigning higher weights to the minority dyskinesia class, ensuring balanced contribution to the loss.
- Supervised contrastive learning is applied to the latent embeddings from the Transformer encoder to structure the representation space. Embeddings from the same class are encouraged to cluster closer together, while those from different classes are pushed apart by a margin parameter. This contrastive objective is trained jointly with the binary detection and amplitude classification losses (applied to the prediction heads), such that the model optimizes both prediction accuracy and embedding separability. The combined loss balances these three objectives through weighting parameters.

5.2.3 Digital biomarkers

The digital biomarker for dyskinesia detection is derived from a deep learning pipeline composed of three stages:

- Feature extraction: Each windowed accelerometer segment is processed by a pre-trained ResNet-18 encoder (Yuan et al., 2024) (initialized on large-scale wearable data

from UK Biobank). This module extracts local temporal–spectral features that characterize the intensity, variability, and irregularity of movements associated with dyskinesia.

- **Temporal modelling:** The sequence of ResNet-18 embeddings is passed through a Transformer encoder with multi-head self-attention. This allows the model to capture dependencies across windows, accounting for the fluctuating and sometimes intermittent nature of dyskinesic episodes. Temporal aggregation is performed with max pooling to summarize the sequence representation. This single pooling operation treats all windows equally.
- **Classification:** The aggregated features are fed into a single-head binary classifier, producing the probability of dyskinesia presence.

The combination of class-weighted loss and supervised contrastive objective encourages the model not only to predict labels accurately but also to structure the embedding space in a meaningful way. Dyskinesia and non-dyskinesia episodes are thus separated in the latent space, enhancing robustness. **Figure 14** illustrates the architecture of the digital biomarker pipeline.

Figure 14 Overview of the dyskinesia digital biomarker pipeline based on ResNet–Transformer architecture.

Extended multiple instance learning approach: In addition to aforementioned pipeline, an enhanced dyskinesia digital biomarker is derived using a multiple instance learning technique to explicitly model intra-task temporal heterogeneity, based on Lu et al. (2021). Feature extraction is performed using the same ResNet-18 encoder, and window-level embeddings are again processed by a Transformer encoder to capture long-range temporal dependencies.

Instead of applying a single global pooling operation, temporal aggregation is achieved using class-specific gated attention pooling, which assigns higher importance to windows that are most informative for dyskinesia detection. This enables the model to identify short, discriminative segments within a task that contributes disproportionately to the dyskinesia label.

Classification is performed at the task level using the attention-weighted representation, while instance-level refinement is guided by a clustering-constrained objective. Highly attended windows are encouraged to form dyskinesia-relevant instance clusters, whereas low-attention windows are pushed toward non-dyskinesia representations using a smooth margin-based loss. This weakly supervised strategy leverages task-level labels to improve instance discrimination, resulting in digital biomarkers that better reflect the intermittent and heterogeneous temporal structure of dyskinesic movements. An overview of the proposed architecture can be seen in **Figure 15**.

Figure 15 Overview of the dyskinesia digital biomarker pipeline using a ResNet–Transformer architecture with attention-based multiple instance learning

5.3 Results

5.3.1 MJFF-LRS

The model demonstrated strong agreement with clinician annotations despite the class imbalance. On the validation set, the model achieved recall of 0.99 for non-dyskinesia and 0.40 for dyskinesia, with macro-averaged F1 of 0.76. On the test set, recall for dyskinesia improved to 0.57, with macro-averaged F1 of 0.73. Weighted averages across metrics remained high (precision 0.91, recall 0.90, F1 0.90), reflecting robustness in clinically realistic distributions dominated by non-dyskinesia events. The CLAM-based variant produced performance comparable to the baseline ResNet-Transformer model, confirming that attention-based instance aggregation does not degrade dyskinesia detection performance. While absolute gains were modest, the CLAM architecture provided more stable aggregation of window-level predictions across heterogeneous task segments, supporting its suitability for scenarios in which dyskinesia manifests intermittently across activities. This is particularly relevant for real-world monitoring, where dyskinesia expression may vary substantially within and across recording sessions.

Table 29 Performance metrics for dyskinesia detection on the MJFF-LRS dataset. Val: validation set; Test: test set.

Method	Metric	No Dyskinesia (Val/Test)	Dyskinesia (Val/Test)	Macro Avg (Val/Test)	Weighted Avg (Val/Test)
Resnet-Transformer	Precision	0.93/0.95	0.78/0.48	0.85/0.72	0.91/0.91
	Recall	0.99/0.93	0.40/0.57	0.69/0.75	0.92/0.90
	F1-score	0.96/0.94	0.53/0.52	0.76/0.73	0.91/0.90
CLAM-based	Precision	0.93/0.94	0.61/0.32	0.77/0.63	0.89/0.88
	Recall	0.96/0.88	0.44/0.53	0.70/0.70	0.90/0.84
	F1-score	0.94/0.91	0.51/0.40	0.73/0.66	0.90/0.86

Confusion matrices (**Figure 16**) on Resnet-Transformer model show that most errors corresponded to missed dyskinesia episodes (false negatives), consistent with the relative scarcity and subtlety of these events. Importantly, the model maintained high specificity and rarely misclassified non-dyskinesia movements as dyskinesia.

Figure 16 Confusion matrix on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

5.3.2 dBM-DEV study (Validation Cohort)

Validation of the dyskinesia digital biomarker was performed using data from the dBM-DEV study, a prospective observational cohort collected under real-world conditions. The analysis focused on participants with complete accelerometer recordings and corresponding clinical dyskinesia assessments derived from the MDS-UPDRS Part IV.1 dyskinesia impact scale, which quantifies the percentage of awake hours affected by dyskinesia. The PD subgroup represented the primary population of interest, with 7 subjects exhibiting clinically reported dyskinesia during awake hours, while all RBD and healthy control participants were dyskinesia-free.

As summarised in **Table 30**, baseline ResNet-Transformer predictions showed a negligible, non-significant correlation with clinical dyskinesia severity (Spearman's $\rho = 0.08$, $p = 0.51$; Table 16), indicating that the aggregated daily scores did not consistently track higher versus lower MDS-UPDRS Part IV.1 dyskinesia impact ratings. In contrast, the ResNet-Transformer-CLAM model (trained on MJFF-LRS) demonstrated a weak but statistically significant positive association with clinical severity (Spearman's $\rho=0.21$, $p<0.05$), suggesting that its attention-based aggregation yielded daily scores that increased, on average, with higher clinician-rated dyskinesia impact.

Table 30 Performance metrics for dyskinesia duration classification on the dBM-DEV dataset.

Method	Spearman ρ	p-value
Resnet-Transformer	0.08	0.51
Resnet-Transformer-CLAM (MJFF-LRS-train)	0.21	<0.05

5.4 Discussion

5.4.1 Interpretation

The results on the MJFF-LRS dataset demonstrate that the deep learning dyskinesia frameworks can effectively identify episodes of involuntary movement from wrist-worn accelerometer data. Compared to the earlier feature-based approach reported in D3.1, which showed no significant correlation with dyskinesia presence due to weak temporal labeling in MJFF-LRS, the deep learning frameworks achieved substantially higher discriminative performance under the same data constraints. Despite the class imbalance, the models

achieved strong weighted performance, indicating robustness in clinical contexts where dyskinesia occurs relatively infrequently.

Validation on the dBM-DEV cohort highlights the inherent challenges of cross-paradigm generalisation. While correlations with clinical dyskinesia severity were modest, the observed statistically significant associations of the CLAM-based model indicate that the learned representations capture aspects of involuntary movement that remain informative under real-world conditions.

5.4.1.1 Innovation beyond state of the art

Dyskinesia tracking is implemented using the same ResNet-based foundation model pretrained on the UK Biobank dataset, combined with a Transformer encoder and a CLAM-based Multiple Instance Learning framework. Existing approaches typically rely on handcrafted signal features (e.g., motion strength or spectral entropy) and classical machine learning classifiers to distinguish dyskinetic movements from normal activity. However, available datasets usually provide only recording-level labels indicating the presence or absence of dyskinesia, without precise temporal annotations. The proposed CLAM-based framework enables learning directly from raw accelerometer signals while identifying the most informative temporal segments, allowing effective modelling despite weak annotations and representing the key methodological improvement over feature-based approaches.

5.4.2 Limitations and further insights

A primary limitation of dyskinesia validation is the mismatch between development and validation paradigms. The MJFF-LRS dataset provides task-level binary annotations of dyskinesia presence, whereas the dBM-DEV study relies on subject-level ordinal severity ratings reflecting the proportion of awake hours affected by dyskinesia. This difference inherently constrains achievable correlation and complicates direct comparison.

Additionally, dyskinesia severity in the dBM-DEV cohort was highly imbalanced, with only a small subset of PD participants exhibiting dyskinesia. This limits statistical power and reduces sensitivity to higher severity levels. Differences in wearable hardware and recording environments further contribute to variability and attenuated effect sizes.

Several aspects of the proposed dyskinesia framework help mitigate the structural limitations imposed by paradigm mismatch, class imbalance, and real-world variability. The use of architectures capable of capturing temporal dynamics provides robustness under weak task-level labels in MJFF-LRS, allowing the models to learn discriminative involuntary-movement signatures even when severe dyskinesia is sparsely represented. Cross-cohort validation on the clinically diverse dBM-DEV dataset further regularises against overfitting to the development paradigm and demonstrates that the learned representations retain clinical relevance despite differences in annotation granularity. Together, these methodological choices partially buffer the impact of imbalanced severity distributions and cross-paradigm discrepancies, supporting the reliability and generalisability of the dyskinesia digital biomarkers under real-world conditions. In this vein, these limitations are representative of broader challenges in real-world digital biomarker validation rather than shortcomings of the proposed modelling approach.

5.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

Despite these challenges, the dyskinesia digital biomarker demonstrates potential utility as a screening and longitudinal monitoring tool. Passive wrist-worn sensing enables continuous assessment of involuntary movement patterns without increasing patient burden,

complementing clinician-reported dyskinesia evaluations that are limited in temporal resolution.

With further refinement on larger real-world cohorts, such digital measures could support monitoring of treatment-related motor complications, aid in the assessment of medication response, and enable more granular tracking of dyskinesia dynamics in both clinical practice and decentralized trials.

5.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	Dyskinesia
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Digital score indicating the presence or absence of dyskinesia derived from three-axis wrist acceleration
Validation	<p>Type: In laboratory & in real-world settings.</p> <p>Primary measures of validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 of the digital score of the presence or absence of dyskinesia, averaged across each task for each subject, and then averaged across all subjects, compared with clinician-provided dyskinesia presence/absence score, based on clinical assessment. Correlation between aggregated daily dyskinesia predictions and patient self-reported dyskinesia severity on MDS-UPDRS Part IV.1 0–4 ordinal scale (corresponding to percentage awake hours). Evaluated using Spearman correlation and classification metrics (precision, recall, F1) on daily-aggregated data.
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires participants to wear wrist devices with accelerometers sampling at ≥ 25 Hz

6 Human activity recognition and physical activity tracking

6.1 Background and objectives

Physical activity is strongly associated with PD progression, with higher activity levels linked to lower disease risk and slower deterioration. These relationships and their implications were discussed in D3.1. This time, we again leveraged the Capture-24 dataset but utilized a labelling scheme from Walmsley et al. (2020) designed to better reflect physical activity

intensities relevant to health monitoring: sleep (excluded from the present analysis¹), moderate-vigorous, light, and sedentary. This refined labelling facilitates clearer classification and interpretation of overall health status through digital biomarkers.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Datasets

The Capture-24 dataset remains the primary dataset, consistent with D3.1, but here we employ a three-class labelling scheme (Walmsley, et al., 2020) without sleep, leading to moderate-vigorous, light, and sedentary categories. This scheme better suits the aim of differentiating activity intensity levels relevant to tracking overall health status.

6.2.2 Data Preprocessing

To assess the generalizability of derived dBMs in real-world clinical contexts, we additionally analysed data from the dBM-DEV study, the prospective observational study of the project (see Section 4.2.1 for detailed description). The study comprised 81 subjects distributed across three clinical cohorts. Participants wore the Garmin Vivoactive 5 smartwatch (25 Hz sampling rate) on their dominant hand. Three subjects were excluded from analysis: 1 person with RBD due to missing accelerometer data and two subjects (one with RBD and one with PD) with insufficient accelerometer data. The final cohort comprised 78 subjects with complete data: 27 individuals with RBD, 24 healthy controls (HC), and 27 PD patients.

Following D3.1, raw acceleration data were segmented into 5-second windows, non-numeric entries and missing values (NaN) were managed as described therein, and data resampling ensured consistent sampling frequencies. These steps are summarized here to avoid repetition, as details appear in D3.1.

In the current deliverable, the focus is shifted on the labelling scheme and data partitioning. The subject-independent, stratified (across sleep classes) train-validation-test split was applied to guarantee participants' data did not overlap between splits while maintaining balanced representation of the three activity classes across them. This approach preserves the validity of performance estimates by preventing data leakage and ensuring generalizability.

Though metabolic equivalent of task (MET) (Mendes et al., 2018) values per class were not used in modelling, they are detailed as descriptive statistics from the (Walmsley, et al., 2020)scheme, providing context to the physical activity intensities as follows: sedentary activities 1.49, light activity 2.46, and moderate-to-vigorous activity 3.80. **Table 31** Class distributions across splits **Table 31** summarizes the class distributions across splits, showing effective stratification.

Table 31 Class distributions across splits

Set	Sedentary (%)	Light (%)	Moderate-vigorous (%)
Train	63.2	28.6	8.2
Validation	71.6	23.3	5.1

¹ The sleep class was removed to focus on clinically relevant daytime activity intensities, as sleep constituted the majority class in Capture-24 and is better addressed through dedicated sleep detection modules in continuous monitoring pipelines.

Test	58.6	34.2	7.2
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6.2.3 Digital biomarkers

The primary dBM in this section is a quantified measure of human activity derived from a human activity recognition (HAR) model (Yuan et al., 2024) applied to wrist-worn accelerometer data. The HAR model classifies wrist-worn accelerometer signals into activity categories of varying intensity levels using probabilistic deep learning methods. The resulting digital score supports the tracking of subjects' physical activity patterns under free-living conditions. The development of the model follows the methodology presented in deliverable D3.1, which details the initial modelling steps, feature extraction, classifier training, and the broader biomarker architecture.

Additionally, to quantify daily step counts from raw accelerometer data, we integrated the step detection algorithm described in (Luu et al., 2022), which identifies characteristic gait patterns from wrist-worn acceleration signals. This method was integrated into our analysis pipeline to extract step-based physical activity metrics complementary to the HAR-derived activity intensity classifications, enabling comprehensive assessment of mobility patterns across free-living conditions.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers

Following the methodology laid out in D3.1, we evaluated the performance of the model on the Capture-24 test dataset using the refined three-class labelling scheme (moderate-vigorous, light, sedentary). The model achieved a balanced performance on the Capture-24 test set, with an overall accuracy of 78.36% and a mean F1-score of 0.70 across classes. Validation set results were consistent, with an accuracy of 84.05% and mean F1-score of 0.73. **Table 32** summarizes the classification metrics for both the validation and test sets.

Table 32 Classification metrics of the HAR model applied on the Capture-24 dataset.

Metric	Validation Set	Test Set
Accuracy	84.05%	78.36%
Precision	0.74	0.72
Recall	0.72	0.68
F1 score	0.73	0.70

Besides, the confusion matrix for this model on the test set is provided in **Figure 17**. The matrix highlights accurate identification of sedentary states, with some expected overlap between light and moderate-vigorous activities. This reflects the natural complexity and variability of free-living human behaviour. Overall, the confusion matrix demonstrates a robust classification ability across distinct physical activity intensities in realistic conditions.

6.3.2 Validation on Verily Study Watch Dataset

To verify the model's generalizability, we conducted validation on the Verily Study Watch dataset consistent with the procedure in D3.1. For this analysis, the active state comprises light and sedentary classes. The model demonstrated excellent discrimination, achieving 100% accuracy and an F1-score of 1.0 for this binary classification task. This result confirms the robustness and transportability of this digital biomarker in diverse real-world contexts.

6.3.3 Physical Activity Metrics in the dBM-DEV Study

To evaluate the applicability of derived activity metrics across clinically distinct populations, we analysed physical activity patterns in the dBM-DEV cohorts. Two complementary measurement approaches were employed: (1) step-based metrics, and (2) activity intensity levels classification based on the HAR model trained on Capture-24 data. A sleep detection module (Yuan, Plekhanova, et al., 2024) was applied to filter sleep periods from passive smartwatch data.

Figure 17 Confusion matrix on the Capture-24 test set.

Physical Activity Intensity Levels

Activity intensity distributions across the three cohorts were derived from the HAR model applied to waking hours only, classifying accelerometer data into sedentary, light, and moderate-to-vigorous categories. Healthy controls (HC, $n=24$) spent less time in sedentary behaviour compared to both patient cohorts, averaging $66.08\% \pm 8.84\%$ of waking hours, while RBD ($n=27$) and PD ($n=27$) patients exhibited higher sedentary levels with means of $69.78\% \pm 9.35\%$ and $70.11\% \pm 10.52\%$, respectively. Correspondingly, HC participants engaged in substantially more light-intensity activity ($31.36\% \pm 8.55\%$ of waking hours) compared to RBD ($27.74\% \pm 8.85\%$) and PD ($27.33\% \pm 10.03\%$) cohorts. Moderate-to-vigorous activity was similarly low across all groups, with HC averaging $1.94\% \pm 1.51\%$, RBD $1.86\% \pm 1.82\%$, and PD $2.18\% \pm 2.46\%$ of waking hours, indicating that high-intensity activity remains rare in all populations studied (**Figure 18**). To formally evaluate whether these descriptive trends were statistically meaningful, non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis tests were performed across the three groups. No statistically significant differences were observed for sedentary behaviour ($H = 3.29$, $p = 0.193$), light activity ($H = 3.48$, $p = 0.175$), or moderate-to-vigorous activity ($H = 0.31$, $p = 0.859$). Exploratory pairwise Mann–Whitney tests with

Bonferroni correction likewise did not reveal significant differences between cohorts for any activity intensity category. Effect sizes were small-to-moderate for HC vs PD comparisons in sedentary behaviour ($r = 0.26$) and light activity ($r = -0.28$), suggesting a potentially meaningful trend despite the absence of statistical significance. These results suggest that although descriptive trends indicate slightly higher sedentary behaviour and reduced light activity in the patient groups relative to healthy controls, variability within cohorts prevents these differences from reaching statistical significance.

However, cohort-level patterns differed notably: HC exhibited a median of 1.44% with mean $1.94\% \pm 1.51\%$, RBD a median of 1.43% with mean $1.86\% \pm 1.82\%$, and PD a median of 1.50% with mean $2.18\% \pm 2.46\%$. The lower median moderate-vigorous activity in PD compared to HC suggests that the typical PD patient engages in less high-intensity activity; however, the increased mean (driven by outliers reaching up to 11.64% of waking hours) indicates substantial inter-individual heterogeneity in the disease cohort, with some PD patients maintaining relatively high activity engagement despite disease.

Figure 18 Distribution of sedentary, light and moderate-vigorous activity (percentage of waking hours) across HC, RBD and PD cohorts (dBM-DEV study).

To investigate whether activity intensity patterns in PD patients relate to disease severity, we performed exploratory correlation analyses within the PD cohort ($n=27$) examining associations between moderate-to-vigorous activity time and clinical disease measures. Moderate-to-vigorous activity showed a weak negative correlation with Hoehn & Yahr stage ($\rho=-0.24$, $p=0.22$) and UPDRS total score ($\rho=-0.13$, $p=0.53$), both non-significant, suggesting a trend toward reduced high-intensity activity with increasing disease severity, though larger sample sizes would be required to establish statistical significance. Sedentary time demonstrated weak positive correlations with H&Y stage ($\rho=0.19$, $p=0.34$) and UPDRS total score ($\rho = 0.11$, $p = 0.60$), also non-significant.

6.3.4 Steps Counts

Mean daily step counts differed substantially across cohorts, reflecting varying levels of physical activity engagement. Healthy controls (HC, $n=24$) demonstrated the highest activity levels with a mean of $7,645.2 \pm 2,629.8$ steps/day, while both PD ($n=27$) and RBD ($n=27$) patients exhibited reduced daily activity, with means of $6,109.2 \pm 3,441.0$ and $6,260.7 \pm 2,976.2$ steps/day, respectively (**Figure 19**). The HC cohort exhibited lower variability in step counts, with a standard deviation of 2,629.8 steps/day, whereas PD patients demonstrated substantially greater inter-subject heterogeneity ($SD=3,441.0$), reflecting the wide range of symptom severity and functional impairment across the PD cohort. To assess cohort differences, a non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis test was conducted. This revealed a significant overall difference in mean daily step counts across cohorts ($H = 8.43$, $p = 0.015$). Post-hoc

pairwise comparisons using Mann–Whitney U tests with Bonferroni correction showed that healthy controls walked significantly more steps per day than PD patients ($U = 469$, $p = 0.019$, $r = -0.45$), representing a moderate-to-large effect size. Differences between HC and RBD ($p = 0.122$) and between PD and RBD ($p = 0.922$) were not statistically significant, indicating that the RBD cohort exhibited intermediate activity levels but did not differ significantly from either group.

Figure 19 Mean daily step counts across disease cohorts (dBM-DEV study).

Step variability, quantified as the coefficient of variation (CoV) across daily measurements within each subject, revealed distinct patterns of activity consistency across cohorts. Healthy controls exhibited the most stable daily activity patterns with a mean CoV of $45.9\% \pm 15.3\%$, indicating relatively consistent day-to-day step counts. In contrast, both PD ($68.0\% \pm 37.1\%$) and RBD ($51.5\% \pm 24.7\%$) cohorts demonstrated increased step variability, with PD patients showing the highest mean CoV. Notably, the PD group also exhibited the greatest variability in this metric itself ($SD = 37.1\%$), reflecting heterogeneous patterns of activity consistency within the disease cohort. The substantially increased CoV in PD patients suggests either greater day-to-day fluctuations in functional capacity (potentially linked to medication timing, or symptom fluctuations) or variable engagement in structured activities (**Figure 20**).

6.4 Discussion

The human activity recognition and physical activity tracking digital biomarker successfully discriminates between clinically relevant activity intensity states using wrist-worn accelerometer data. The use of the three-level labelling scheme offers a balanced granularity, enabling nuanced insights into patient activity patterns. The Capture-24 results demonstrate strong classification performance, while perfect validation on the Verily dataset attests to its applicability across varied populations and sensor deployments.

6.4.1 Interpretation

The human activity recognition digital biomarker demonstrated a strong ability to differentiate activity intensities that are clinically meaningful for monitoring PD progression. Its classification performance on the Capture-24 dataset, along with perfect validation results on the Verily Study Watch dataset, confirm the robustness and transportability of this approach for monitoring physical activity in free-living conditions. Despite the absence of ground truth

Figure 20 Step count variability across disease cohorts (dBM-DEV study). Coefficient of variation (%) in daily step counts for each subject, quantifying day-to-day activity consistency across cohorts.

annotations in the dBM-DEV study, the proposed dBM yielded clinically coherent patterns across disease cohorts. Healthy controls demonstrated lower sedentary engagement and correspondingly higher light-intensity activity compared to both PD and RBD patients, although these differences did not reach statistical significance. Step count patterns revealed clearer disease-related differences, with PD patients exhibiting significantly lower daily step counts than healthy controls, as well as substantially greater inter-individual variability in activity levels. This increased variability suggests heterogeneous patterns of day-to-day functional fluctuations within the PD cohort.

These findings, observed across activity intensity distributions, step counts and step consistency metrics, align with emerging evidence in the field showing that wrist-worn sensor data, when combined with advanced machine learning models, can provide reliable and objective measures of daily activity patterns that relate to disease status. The granularity afforded by the three-class labelling scheme supports nuanced behavioural insights, which are essential for personalizing disease management and therapeutic adjustments.

6.4.2 Innovation beyond state of the art

The human activity recognition and physical activity tracking digital biomarker is implemented using a ResNet-based foundation model pretrained on the large-scale UK Biobank accelerometer dataset. The pretrained model provides general motion representations learned from population-scale data and is subsequently fine-tuned on labelled datasets relevant to Parkinson's disease, including MJFF-LRS and Capture-24, to adapt the learned features to PD-specific activity patterns and mobility characteristics. This transfer-learning strategy improves robustness and generalization compared with models trained solely on small disease-specific datasets. While the component primarily builds upon established deep

learning and transfer learning methodologies for wearable activity recognition, its contribution lies in integrating large-scale pretrained motion representations within the AI-PROGNOSIS digital biomarker framework and validating their applicability for monitoring physical activity differences across Parkinson's disease, prodromal, and healthy populations in real-world settings.

6.4.3 Limitations and further insights

The approach maintains many strengths from the prior approach (D3.1), notably the use of a well-characterized wrist-worn sensor dataset and rigorous, subject-independent model evaluation to ensure generalizability. While distinguishing between light and moderate-vigorous activities reflects natural variability in real-world behaviours, the current three-class labelling provides a meaningful granularity, balancing clinical relevance with model feasibility. In the dBM-DEV study, no relevant ground-truth annotations were available; although the observed patterns were clinically coherent, the absence of direct ground truth does not allow full certainty regarding classification accuracy within this cohort. A complementary consideration concerns the inherent variability of free-living behaviour and the challenges it poses for model interpretability. Wrist-worn accelerometry captures composite movement patterns influenced by contextual factors, such as gait compensation strategies, tremor, or task-specific arm use, that may blur distinctions between adjacent intensity states. This can introduce uncertainty when extrapolating lab-validated thresholds to heterogeneous real-world settings. Nonetheless, the convergence of activity distributions across cohorts, the alignment with known disease-related mobility profiles, and the consistency of step-based metrics provide indirect validation that the model captures clinically meaningful behavioural signatures.

6.4.4 Usability of digital biomarkers in the context of current care

This dBM offers promising integration opportunities in clinical workflows for PD, enabling objective, continuous monitoring of physical activity with minimal burden on patients. Its validated accuracy and generalizability signify strong potential for real-world application, supporting early detection of deteriorations and monitoring of treatment responses. Beyond clinical settings, the biomarker could empower patients by providing personalized feedback on activity levels and lifestyle factors influencing disease trajectory.

6.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	Various aspects of physical activity
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Digital score indicating activity classes that categorise human action or type of physical activity.
Validation	<p>Type: In laboratory and in real world</p> <p>Primary measures of validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 of the digital score that corresponds to activity classes, averaged across all subjects, compared to the labelled activities.
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires participants to wear wrist devices with accelerometers sampling at ≥ 25 Hz

7 Slowness of fine movement tracking

7.1 Background and objectives

Rigidity and bradykinesia are cardinal PD motor symptoms that significantly affect the person's mobility and consequently their quality of life. Along with tremors, they form a collection of symptoms referred to as Parkinsonism, which constitutes the core of the clinical diagnostic criteria of PD (Postuma & et al, 2015). Sub-threshold Parkinsonism is further considered a prodromal marker of PD (Heinzel, et al., 2019). Conventional clinical assessments provide a standardised and detailed, yet imperfect way to assess these symptoms, as they are plagued by low resolution (patient snapshot) and lack of ecological validity.

There is an increasing popularity of smart sensor use for capturing the spatiotemporal properties of movement (for an extensive review see D2.3, section 2.3.7) in daily life. Recent research developed dBMs to unobtrusively assess rigidity and bradykinesia, based on either passive tracking of upper limb movements using wearable inertial measurement units (IMUs) (Mahadevan, et al., 2020) or keystroke dynamics during touchscreen typing (Iakovakis, et al., 2020), showing that both modalities have potential in assessing rigidity and bradykinesia.

Assuming that passive data collection from wrist-worn devices or during routine typing is well tolerated by users, in AI-PROGNOSIS, we are implementing dBMs of upper limb slowness of movement, using unobtrusively collected kinematic data from wearable sensors and keystroke dynamics data from touchscreen keyboards. In the former case, we target grosser movements, while in the latter, fine motor skills. Implementations are based on the works of (Iakovakis D. , et al., 2018), (Iakovakis, et al., 2018b) and (Mahadevan, et al., 2020).

The aim is dual, i.e., to develop a system for more accurate tracking of PD motor symptoms in daily life and to use the dBMs (or their constituent features) as input to the predictive models for PD risk assessment and prognosis that the project is developing. This section focuses on dBMs of slowness of fine movement derived from keystroke dynamics. More specifically, the best performing dBMs from D3.3 (Finger Tapping & Rigidity) were tested on data collected in the dBM-DEV study. Wrist accelerometry-based dBMs are detailed in Section 8.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Datasets

The keystroke dynamics dataset for this analysis was sourced from the finalised dBM-DEV study. For data descriptive purposes only, we adopted the dBM-DEV cohorts described in Section 2.2.1, namely Development RBD, Development Control, and Confirmation.

Data collection for the keystroke dynamics dataset was conducted using a custom virtual keyboard developed by Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) bundled with the dBM-DEV study app. The keyboard replaced the participants' default smartphone keyboard and participants used it for routine typing across apps. Each time a participant used the keyboard, a typing session was captured locally in JSON format and subsequently uploaded to the AI-PROGNOSIS cloud infrastructure. Each typing session consists of the data fields listed in

Table 33. All data captured in this study were in daily living conditions aiming for unobtrusive symptom assessment.

The keystroke dynamics dataset was extracted on December 3rd, 2025. Participation was voluntary, with 12 individuals opting to use the custom keyboard. In accordance with the study design, participants were followed for a variable amount of time depending on their respective cohort from 4 to 12 weeks.

Table 33 dBM-DEV keystroke dataset variables

Variable	Type	Description
recID	String	Recording identifier
userID	String	User identifier
endTime / startTime	Timestamp in ms	The time the typing session started/ended
currentLanguage	String	Keyboard language
distance	Integer for millimetres	Distance between keys tapped
downtime	Timestamp in ms	Timestamps corresponding to the moment keys were tapped down
uptime	Timestamp in ms	Timestamps corresponding to the moment keys were released
pressure	Float	Normalized (0-1) maximum pressure applied for each key tap
isLongPress	Boolean	Flag denoting whether a key was long pressed
isSoundOn / isVibrationOn	Boolean	Binary flag for vibration and sound
keyboardScale	Boolean	Landscape or portrait orientation of the keyboard
numDels/numSpace	Integer	Number of times the backspace/delete key was tapped
downtimeSpace	Timestamp in ms	Timestamps corresponding to the moment Space key was pressed
uptimeSpace	Timestamp in ms	Timestamps corresponding to the moment Space key was released
uptimeDelete	Timestamp in ms	Timestamps corresponding to the moment backspace/delete key was released

7.2.2 Data pre-processing

The pre-processing pipeline for the dBM-DEV dataset was similar to the one presented in D3.1 and is outlined in **Figure 21**. In brief the steps followed are:

1. For each session the *Hold Time (HT)* and *Flight Time (FT)* sequences are calculated. Hold time (HT) is defined as the time between a key press and release and flight time (FT) is the time between the release of a key and the press of the subsequent key (**Figure 22**). HT and FT are typical variables of keystroke (or key tap) dynamics.
2. Any HT_n in the *HT* sequence outside of the [0,300] ms interval was discarded. Similarly, any FT_n in the *FT* sequence outside the [0,3000] ms interval was also discarded.
3. The *Normalised Flight Time (NFT)* vector NFT is calculated as the typing session's detrended *FT* sequence, i.e., $NFT = FT - \overline{FT}$, where \overline{FT} is the typing session's mean FT value.
4. Only NFT values above the 1st percentile and below the 99th percentile of a real-life data distribution [-1270, 1700] ms (Iakovakis D. , et al., 2018) were kept.

5. Only typing sessions with more than 20 key taps, total time less than 10 minutes and only participants with more than 10 typing sessions were included in the analysis.
6. From the *HT* and *NFT* sequence of each eligible typing session, the mean and standard deviation of HT and the skewness of NFT are calculated and form the feature vector representing the typing session. These features were found to be the most informative by (Iakovakis D. , et al., 2018).

Figure 21 Feature vector estimation pipeline from keystroke timing data of a single typing session. HT: hold time; FT: flight time; NFT: normalised flight time; std: standard deviation; skew: skewness.

Figure 22 Representation of keystroke events and keystroke dynamics variables.

7.2.3 Digital biomarkers

In the previous version of this deliverable, we presented two models that were trained on the hold time and flight time features described in the previous section to predict UPDRS Part III Items 22 (Rigidity), 23 (Finger tapping) scores (see D3.1 for details). The models were trained on a keystroke dynamics dataset captured via a controlled typing experiment as part of the i-PROGNOSIS H2020 project² (referred to as the in-clinic dataset in D3.1). Here, we evaluate those two pre-trained models on the keystroke dynamics dataset of the dBM-DEV study.

dBM-DEV data were deduplicated to remove errors that occurred during the synchronisation with the AI-PROGNOSIS cloud infrastructure and the eligible typing sessions for analysis were identified for feature extraction. We then used the pre-trained models to predict scores of bradykinesia and rigidity for each typing session. We compared the results with the corresponding MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.3 (Rigidity) and Item 3.4 (Finger Tapping). Spearman's rank correlation was used to assess the association of the predicted digital score with the respective clinical scores. To assess the quality of the extracted features and their ability to discriminate between symptom impairment levels, we performed a Mann-Whitney U test for each feature comparing features from participants labelled as 0 and 1 for both MDS-UPDRS Part III items.

² Iakovakis, D., Hadjidimitriou, S., Charisis, V., Bostantzopoulou, S., Katsarou, Z., & Hadjileontiadis, L. (2019). Keystroke timing and pressure data captured during touchscreen typing by early Parkinson's disease patients and healthy controls (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571623>

For examining the consistency of the best-performing score across time, we performed Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) analysis using repeated measurements across weeks. For each participant, we aggregated their predicted score for the typing sessions by computing the median predicted value per week. Subsequently, we utilised a two-way mixed effects model for absolute agreement [ICC(3, k)] (Shrout & Fleiss, 1979) to compare the weekly measurements up to the sixth week. We limited the analysis to six weeks to keep the analysis reliable as after this point only two participants had datapoints.

Finally, for visualisation of the longitudinal evolution of the best-performing score we aggregated the predictions for the typing sessions up to the respective week of reference using their mean. This approach was selected to provide a robust digital score and remove fluctuations that could be attributed to a small number of weekly typing sessions and data variability.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Sample characteristics

Following the filtering and preprocessing described in Section 7.2.2, data from 12 participants were available for analysis, comprising a total of $n=2,147$ typing sessions. On average, each participant contributed 179 ± 177 typing sessions. Most participants were assigned zero scores for both MDS-UPDRS items, except for 2 participants and Item 3.4 (Finger tapping) and one participant and Item 3.3 (Rigidity). The timeline of the typing sessions per participant is illustrated in **Figure 23**, while the typing session activity per hour of the day for all participants in **Figure 24**. The clinico-demographic characteristics of the participants included in the analysis are described in **Table 34**.

Figure 23 demonstrates sufficient data continuity, and the activity heatmap confirms that samples were collected at various times throughout the day. This reinforces the unobtrusive nature of the data collection and indicates that the typing sessions reflect real-world behaviour across different states, such as varying levels of fatigue.

Table 34 Clinico-demographic characteristics of the dBM-DEV keystroke dataset. N/A: Not applicable

Cohort	Persons with RBD	Healthy controls	Persons with PD
n	6	4	2
Age (years)	70.3 ± 6.6	66 ± 5.0	65.0 ± 4.2
Sex Female (%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (100%)	2 (100%)
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	N/A	N/A	3 ± 0.0
MDS-UPDRS Part III Total	1.7 ± 3.2	0.0 ± 0.0	15.0 ± 12.7
MDS-UPDRS 3.4a (Finger Tapping)	0.2 ± 0.4	0.0 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.7
MDS-UPDRS 3.3b (Rigidity)	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.7

Figure 23 Timeline of eligible typing sessions per participant in the dBM-DEV keystroke dynamics dataset from study initiation.

Figure 24 Distribution of typing sessions of all participants across the study duration. On x-axis are days since study initiation, on y-axis is the hour of the day (UTC) the typing session was captured. Colour intensity represents session frequency.

7.3.2 Selection of digital biomarkers

The results from the Mann-Whitney U test for each feature grouped by symptom severity (Item score 0 and 1), are shown in the **Figure 25** for the MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4 (Finger tapping) and **Figure 26** for the MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.3 (Rigidity). For both MDS-UPDRS Items all tested keystroke dynamics features differed significantly between the two groups suggesting satisfactory discriminatory ability.

Figure 25 Keystroke dynamics distribution of Mean Hold Time, Standard Dev. of Hold Time and Skewness of Normalised Flight time grouped by the MDS-UPDRS Part III item 3.4 (Finger tapping) with Mann-Whitney U test comparisons. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$, ** $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$.

Figure 26 Keystroke dynamics distribution of Mean Hold Time, Standard Dev. of Hold Time and Skewness of Normalised Flight time grouped by the MDS-UPDRS Part III item 3.3 (Rigidity) with Mann-Whitney U test comparisons. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$, ns: non significant.

The Spearman’s rank correlation of the keystroke dynamics-derived scores of bradykinesia and rigidity with the associated clinical scores are presented in **Table 35**. While for MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4 (Finger tapping), the bradykinesia score achieved significant good positive correlation with the associated labels, the score corresponding to MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.3 (Rigidity) did not yield significant results. This could be attributed to the existence of only one participant with Item 3.3 scored as 1.

We hereby refer to the keystroke dynamics-derived score of finger-tapping bradykinesia as a slowness of finger (fine) movement score. **Figure 27** further depicts the association of the digital slowness of finger movement score with the respective clinical score (MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4 (Finger tapping)).

Table 35 Association of the keystroke derived digital score for the dBM-DEV dataset with the relevant MDS-UPDRS Part III items for each pre-trained model (i-PROGNOSIS dataset)

Slowness of movement estimator target	Spearman's ρ [95%CI]
MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4 (Finger tapping)	0.65 ($p < 0.05$) [0.48, 0.76]
MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.3 (Rigidity)	Non-significant $p > 0.50$

Figure 27 Association of the keystroke dynamics-derived digital slowness of finger movement score with the MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4 score (Finger tapping) in the dBM-DEV dataset.

For the ICC-based reliability analysis, we aggregated the predicted score for the typing sessions of each participant using the median predicted value per week. Each eligible dBM-DEV study participant had a mean of 24.97 ± 25 typing sessions per week. As shown in **Figure 28** the model demonstrated excellent short-term reliability (ICC = 0.928 for weeks 1-2) and maintained good reliability across extended periods (ICC = 0.762-0.886 for weeks 1-4 through 1-6). A temporary decrease in week 3 (ICC = 0.667) may reflect intrinsic variability in the data. All ICC estimates were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), with the number of complete cases decreasing from 12 to 6 participants across the 6-week observation window.

The longitudinal evolution of the digital slowness of finger movement score for each participant can be seen in the **Figure 29**. Most of the individual evolution trajectories appeared to be stable and robust with clear separation of participants assessed as 1 in the MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4 (Finger tapping).

Figure 28 Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) values across increasing weekly time windows for assessing model prediction consistency. The model used for predictions is the pre-trained model using the MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4 (Finger tapping). Each point represents the ICC(3,k) value (with 95% confidence intervals) for weeks 1 through 6; (*: $p < 0.05$).

Figure 29 Longitudinal evolution of the fine motor slowness of movement digital score calculated using keystroke dynamics on the dBM-DEV dataset

7.4 Discussion

7.4.1 Interpretation

In this study, we aimed to validate the keystroke-dynamics dBMs of slowness of fine movement, developed in the first period of the project and presented in D3.1, using data from the dBM-DEV study. We evaluated the performance of two keystroke dynamics-based models trained to predict rigidity and finger tapping clinical scores.

The digital slowness of finger movement score (corresponding to finger-tapping) demonstrated promising preliminary results as evidenced by the good correlation with the clinical labels (Spearman's $\rho = 0.65$, $p < 0.05$) and excellent short-term reliability with good reliability across larger time periods. We have also shown that the score demonstrates stable longitudinal evolution trajectories. The discriminatory ability of the input keystroke dynamics features was consistent with the original training set.

Conversely, the digital rigidity score failed to demonstrate a significant association with the clinical scores in the dBM-DEV study dataset. This is likely a compounded effect of the data sparsity and to the fact that only one participant of the study exhibited rigidity, a critical dataset limitation, precluding robust model validation.

7.4.2 Limitations and further insights

The results of this study must be interpreted with care as there are several limitations. First, and most critically, the available label distribution was severely constrained; the dataset contained only participants with scores of 0 or 1 on the relevant MDS-UPDRS items, missing the full spectrum of impairment (scores 2-3). This hinders a comprehensive validation of the models' performance across all severity levels and limits assessment of their generalizability to cases of moderate or severe motor impairment. Second, the overall sample size was small (N=12 participants, 179 ± 177 typing sessions per participant), which reduces the statistical power and stability of the findings. A larger cohort is required to confirm these preliminary results. A further consideration relates to the intrinsic complexity of mapping keystroke-based motor signatures onto clinical constructs that themselves exhibit variability across context, medication state, and examiner scoring. Keystroke dynamics capture a mixture of cognitive, motor, and behavioural influences, attention lapses, typing strategies, device familiarity, and hand-posture adaptations, which may dilute the specificity of the extracted features when the available clinical labels span only the mildest impairment levels. This makes it difficult to disentangle true motor slowness from contextual noise and limits the interpretability of null findings, particularly for rigidity, where the absence of moderate or severe cases prevents the model from learning the characteristic temporal irregularities associated with increased muscle tone. Nevertheless, the stability of the finger-tapping dBM, its consistent discriminatory patterns, and its coherent longitudinal trajectories suggest that the underlying signal is robust.

We aim address certain of the limitations by reevaluating our models with the full dataset of the AI-PMP study when completed. Using the advanced capabilities of the virtual keyboard used in AI-PROGNOSIS compared to the one used in the i-PROGNOSIS project (where the training dataset was captured), we aim to enhance our models with a wider array of features, such as the capturing of “delete”, whitespaces and distance between the keys tapped.

7.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

dBMs from unobtrusive user-smartphone interaction offer a way to complement PD care. The implemented keystroke dynamics dBM of slowness of finger movement can be used for continuous and unobtrusive monitoring of fine movement impairment in daily life. This can support earlier detection of symptom changes, accurate and robust assessment of treatment effectiveness and improved monitoring of disease progression. In the context of the AI-PROGNOSIS, the keystroke-dynamics digital slowness of movement digital score will be integrated with the mAI-Insights platform for healthcare professionals.

7.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility

Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Finger bradykinesia 2. Upper limb rigidity
Measurement technology	Touchscreen in combination with a custom virtual keyboard
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital score of finger bradykinesia severity derived from keystroke dynamics during touchscreen typing 2. Digital score of rigidity severity derived from keystroke dynamics during touchscreen typing
Validation	<p>Type: In laboratory and in real world</p> <p>Primary measures of validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spearman correlation of digital score of finger bradykinesia with UPDRS Part III item 23 score or MDS-UPDRS Item 3.4 (finger tapping) of dominant hand 2. Spearman correlation of digital score of rigidity with UPDRS Part III item 22 or MDS-UPDRS Item 3.3 (upper limb rigidity) score of dominant hand
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Touchscreens accurately capture finger tap timing events. • Relevant data collection in the background without interfering with natural typing is well tolerated by subjects. • Dominant hand is used either alone or in combination with the other hand during typing.
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated in unaffected controls and PD patients of Stage I and II with scores ≤ 2 in UPDRS items of interest (D3.1) • Tested in dBM-DEV unaffected controls, RBD patients and PD patients of Stage I and II with scores ≤ 2 in MDS-UPDRS item 3.5 (Finger Tapping). • Measurement takes place when the subject is typing >20 characters.

8 Upper limb slowness of movement tracking

8.1 Background and objectives

The background was briefly described in the previous section (Section 7.1). This section is centred on the implementation of dBMs of slowness of upper limb movement from wrist accelerometry data and extends the work of Mahadevan et al. (2020). dBMs are developed using the Verily Study Watch dataset and tested on the MJFF-LRS and dBM-DEV study datasets.

8.2 Methods

8.2.1 Datasets

The Verily Study Watch dataset, including, among others, all-day accelerometer (sampling rate 100Hz) data from PwPDs, persons at risk of PD, and HCs for almost two years, was the core dataset used to implement and validate the dBMs. The dataset is detailed in Section 5.2.1 of D3.1.

Table 36 presents the key clinico-demographic characteristics for the participants with digital measurements and at least one MDS-UPDRS Part III assessment that were used in the present analysis. While over one year of data are available on average for every participant, in this analysis we used six (6) days of data that were collected following each MDS-UPDRS clinical assessment.

The Michael J. Fox Foundation (MJFF) Levodopa Response Study (LRS) dataset was utilised as an independent dataset to validate the dBMs trained with the Verily Dataset. It contains accelerometer data collected from PwPD using two different smartwatches (sampling rate 50Hz), a GENEActiv and a Pebble, worn respectively on the most and least affected upper limb. Four days of data were available for each participant, including two MDS-UPDRS Part III assessments conducted in both ON and OFF medication states. **Table 37** presents the key clinico-demographic characteristics for the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Finally, we sourced data from the finalised dBM-DEV study to perform a validation of the dBMs. In this dataset participants wear the Garmin Vivoactive 5 smartwatch³ (sampling rate 25Hz) on their dominant hand. The dataset was exported on December 3rd, 2025. As described in Section the primary objective of the study was to identify a novel dBM for the detection of RBD using passive smartwatch-based recordings. For describing the dataset, we utilised the dBM-DEV cohorts described in **Table 1**, while for the analysis we separated the cohorts to PwPD, individuals with RBD only and healthy controls. **Table 1** contains the clinical and demographic information of the dBM-DEV study participants.

We also used the Capture-24 dataset, detailed in Section 5.2.4 of D3.1, to develop a gait-specific detector, which is a variation of the human action recognition model presented in Section 6, tailored to the needs of the present dBM implementation.

Table 36 Demographic and clinical characteristics of Verily Study Watch subset used for the development of the wrist accelerometry-based dBMs of slowness of movement. N.A.: not applicable.

Characteristics	PD	Persons at risk	Health Controls
n (total n = 314)	146	136	32
Demographics			
Females	58	87	14
Males	88	49	18
Age (yrs)			
<50	5	2	3
50-59	22	42	4
60-69	64	63	13
70-79	47	27	7
80-89	7	2	5
>90	1	0	0
Clinical characteristics			
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	5.78 ± 2.45	N.A.	N.A.

³ Garmin Vivoactive 5 - <https://www.garmin.com/en-IE/p/1057989>

Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III score (std)	27.9 ± 12.8	3.85 ± 6.4	3.16 ± 3.88
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Table 37 Demographic and clinical characteristics of MJFF Levodopa Response Study dataset used for the external validation of the wrist accelerometry-based dBM of slowness of movement. N.A.: not applicable

Characteristics	PD
n	16
Demographics	
Females	4
Males	12
Age (std)	64.62 ± 7.83
Clinical characteristics	
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	9.27 ± 3.75
Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III score (std)	44.25 ± 12.05

8.2.2 Data pre-processing

For the present dBM implementation only 3-axis wrist accelerometer data was used. Each 3-axis accelerometer signal was segmented into continuous non-overlapping 5-s windows with any possible gap between two samples being less than 5 s. Each 5-s segment was resampled to 25 Hz, a typical sampling rate of commercial smartwatches, including the smartwatch⁴ that is being used in the dBM-DEV and other AI-PROGNOSIS clinical studies.

8.2.3 Digital biomarkers

The implementation detailed here is an extension of the algorithm proposed by (Mahadevan, et al., 2020). **Figure 30** illustrates the high-level components of the algorithm. For a given accelerometer signal, pre-processed 5-s accelerometer segments were given as input to a hand movement classifier. If hand movement was detected, the segment was processed by a gait classifier. If gait was detected, the segment was further processed by an estimator of slowness of movement that output a quantitative digital score for slowness of movement. The subsequent sections detail the different blocks of the pipeline.

Figure 30 Pipeline for slowness of movement assessment from wrist accelerometry.

Hand movement classifier

A heuristic method proposed was used to detect hand movement. For each 5-s segment, the signal vector magnitude ($\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$) was computed to eliminate the dependence on device orientation. Then, the magnitude was filtered using a 6th-order low-pass Butterworth filter with a cut-off frequency of 3 Hz to reduce noise attributed to the hand tremor and a rolling

⁴ Garmin Vivoactive 5 - <https://www.garmin.com/en-IE/p/1057989>

coefficient of variation ($c_v = \mu/\sigma$ where μ : mean and σ : std.) was calculated by sliding a 1-s window. The segment was considered to contain hand movement if the coefficient was $c_v > 0.01$. From the resulting binary signal, the 5-s segment was considered to contain hand movement.

Gait classifier

For gait detection, two distinct models were trained and evaluated to classify gait and non-gait periods. A *magnitude-based model* that relies solely on signal vector magnitude-related features extracted from the 3-axis accelerometer signal, such as magnitude's higher-order (>2) statistics, signal autocorrelation and dominant frequency, and a *multi-axis model* that uses a combination of features derived from the individual three axes and signal vector magnitude features.

The labelled accelerometer data of the Capture-24 dataset (151 participants) were used for training the gait detection models. A LightGBM classifier was employed in both cases, and a nested cross-validation scheme was used to evaluate performance and perform hyperparameter tuning. For the outer fold of the nested cross-validation, we employed a Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) scheme, while for the inner fold, used for hyperparameter tuning, we adopted a 5-fold approach.

Figure 31 shows the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves and areas under the ROC curve (AUC) for the two models, derived with the LOSO scheme. Although the multi-axis model (AUC 0.83) slightly outperforms the magnitude-based model (AUC 0.79), we selected the latter since it is device orientation-agnostic. As the detection of non-gait periods is of interest in this pipeline, the decision threshold probability (gait versus non-gait period) was set to 0.70 for maximising specificity based on the ROC analysis.

Figure 31 ROC curves and AUCs of the two types of models developed for gait classification.

In the pipeline, continuous segments greater than 30-s with hand movement, were band-pass filtered (4th order, Butterworth filter) in the range of 0.25 – 3.00 Hz to isolate the frequency band associated with gait. Then, feature extraction was performed for every 5-s window of the resulting signal, and the extracted features were fed to the gait detector that classifies the segment as a gait or non-gait period.

Slowness of movement estimator

Wrist acceleration data from the Verily Study Watch dataset was used to train the slowness of movement estimator. Slowness of movement was estimated in 30-s intervals where hand movement a) was present and b) the interval does not correspond to gait periods. The presence of movement and lack of gait were based on the classification of the individual 5-s segments included in the interval, as illustrated in **Figure 32**. If the majority of the classified 5-s windows within a 30-s interval indicate hand movement and no gait, that 30-s interval is retained for slowness of movement estimation. For each retained 30-s interval, the features presented in **Table 38** are extracted for the 5-s windows classified as having hand movement and no gait. Features from the valid 5-s hand movement - non gait windows were aggregated over the entire day by calculating the standard deviation and the mean of the magnitude-based features. To avoid multicollinearity, metrics with high correlation (Pearson $|r| > 0.95$) were removed before the remaining features were ranked using gain importance under subject-aware cross-validation with hyperparameter tuning. The resulting final feature vector consisted of eleven features.

Figure 32 Time-wise classification of hand movement and gait presence over a 10-min period of slowness of movement estimation. Slowness of movement features are extracted only for 5-s windows classified as having hand movement and absence of gait in 30-s valid intervals (with hand movement and absence of gait based on majority voting on

Table 38 Features extracted in each 5-s window for the slowness of movement estimator

Feature Name	Description
Root mean square	Root mean square (RMS) of the signal data along the x, y, and z axes and the signal magnitude
Smoothness	Scaled mean squared jerk (smoothness) of the signal along the x, y, and z axes and the magnitude (Hogan & Sternanrd, 2012)
Peak Acceleration	Maximum absolute value along the x, y, and z axes and the magnitude
Range of Motion	$max - min$ along the x, y, and z axes, and the magnitude
Signal Entropy	Shannon entropy of the signal data along the x, y, and z axes and the magnitude

Mean absolute dynamic inclination rate	Average absolute angular velocity in the Y–Z plane
Standard deviation of dynamic inclination rate	Standard deviation of angular velocity in the Y–Z plane

classifications of constituent 5-s windows).

To develop a digital score indicative of slowness of movement severity, we trained Random Forest regressors using daily aggregated features to predict two clinical measurements:

1. a composite "slowness of movement" score, calculated as the sum of the averaged upper limb rigidity (items 3.3b, 3.3c), the averaged hand pronation-supination (items 3.6a, 3.6b), and the global spontaneity of movement (item 3.14) MDS-UPDRS item scores
2. the global spontaneity of movement score (item 3.14) alone.

These targets were selected as they are more likely to be captured by wrist acceleration. Averaged upper limb scores were used because the specific hand (left/right) wearing the accelerometer was not available. We refer to the output of the regressors as digital scores of slowness of movement.

The performance of the dBMs was first assessed on the Verily dataset by training and testing the models under a nested Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation scheme with hyperparameter optimization with Optuna⁵. For participants with multiple MDS-UPDRS Part III assessments, the slowness of movement features was labelled with the clinical scores from the temporally closest assessment. Spearman's rank correlation was used to evaluate the association between the estimated dBMs of slowness of movement and the corresponding clinical items and composite scores. To further assess the dBMs' diagnostic value, pairwise comparisons across the four emergent symptom severity levels were performed using the Mann-Whitney-U test with Bonferroni adjustment for multiple comparisons. We then assessed the effect of age on the predictions of the model and corrected for it using an Elastic Net regressor. To isolate the effect of aging from disease-related variance, the Elastic Net model was trained using age as the sole predictor of model output scores, fitted exclusively on the healthy control cohort. The estimated age effect was subsequently subtracted from the raw predictions of all participants

To assess the generalisability, we used the independent dataset from the MJFF-LRS and dBM-DEV study. Using the best parameters from the hyperparameter tuning process (number of estimators: 500, max depth: 9, min samples split: 5, min samples leaf: 6, max features: 0.5) we trained the model on the entire Verily dataset and used this model for inference with the independent datasets. Performance on the datasets was assessed with Spearman's correlation. Finally, as experimental analysis we calculated the mean diurnal and longitudinal trajectories from the participants of the dBM-DEV study.

⁵ <https://optuna.org/>
PU – Public

8.3 Results

8.3.1 Sample characteristics

In the case of the Verily Study Watch cohort, in line with the work presented in D3.1 and following the removal of participants who did not have any MDS-UPDRS assessment in the ON state (N=4), data from 314 participants (146 PwPDs, 32 HCs, and 136 individuals at risk) were used for training and validating the slowness of movement estimator. In total, 633 MDS-UPDRS assessments and their corresponding accelerometer signals (recorded for up to 6 days post-assessment) were utilized.

For the MJFF LRS dataset, all the participants were used in the analysis, while for the dBM-DEV, three participants were excluded due to incomplete accelerometer recordings or missing MDS-UPDRS Part III assessments, consistent with the exclusion criteria applied in the rest tremor analysis (see Section 4).

8.3.2 Selection of digital biomarkers

Table 39 presents the Spearman correlation coefficients between the estimated digital scores of slowness of movement and the associated clinical scores. The results from the nested Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation on the Verily Study Watch dataset (reported for both the Digital and the Digital with Age Correction model types) show moderate to strong, statistically significant associations.

Table 39 Internal Cross-Validation Results for the Models Trained to Estimate Bradykinesia

Slowness of movement estimator target	Model Type	Spearman coefficient (significance)
Slowness of movement composite score	Digital	0.68 ($p < 0.05$)
Global spontaneity of movement score	Digital	0.66 ($p < 0.05$)
Slowness of movement composite score	Digital with Age Correction	0.67 ($p < 0.05$)
Global spontaneity of movement score	Digital with Age Correction	0.65 ($p < 0.05$)

Figure 33 through **Figure 36** illustrate the distributions of the estimated digital scores, grouped by clinical severity. **Figure 33** and **Figure 34** present the results for the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement score, without and with age correction, respectively. Similarly, **Figure 35** and **Figure 36** present the results for the global spontaneity of movement score (Item 3.14), without and with age correction, respectively.

For composite score, pairwise comparisons showed that digital scores differed significantly between all severity groups: 0 vs 1–3 ($p < 0.001$, $U = 8.120e+03$), 1–3 vs 3–5 ($p < 0.001$, $U = 2.996e+03$), and 3–5 vs 5–8 ($p < 0.01$, $U = 1.790e+03$). For the global spontaneity of movement score, significant differences were observed for all pairwise comparisons (0 vs 1: $p < 0.001$, $U = 6.039e+03$; 1 vs 2: $p < 0.01$, $U = 3.668e+03$), except between severity scores 2 and 3 ($p = 0.12$, $U = 1.331e+03$).

Figure 33 Distributions of the estimated digital scores (without age correction) grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$; *** $0.0001 < p \leq 0.001$;

Figure 34 Distributions of the estimated digital scores (with age correction) grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$; *** $0.0001 < p \leq 0.001$; ns, not significant.

Figure 35 Distributions of the estimated digital scores (without age correction) grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the MDS-UPDRS Item 3.14 (Global spontaneity of movement) score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$; *** $0.0001 < p \leq 0.001$; ns, not significant.

Figure 36 Distributions of the estimated digital scores (with age correction) grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the MDS-UPDRS Item 3.14 (Global spontaneity of movement) score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$; *** $0.0001 < p \leq 0.001$; ns, not significant.

All models demonstrated comparable correlation performance. *We select the model trained with the composite score for the subsequent analyses due to its superior ability to discriminate between all disease severity levels. We refer to this model and its output as the digital slowness of movement model and score, respectively.*

Figure 37 illustrates the relationship between age and the estimated digital scores for slowness of movement, depicting this correlation both before and after an adjustment derived from the healthy control (HC) cohort. The analysis confirmed that slowness of movement was

positively correlated with age. Specifically, Spearman's rank correlation was $\rho = 0.35$ ($p < 0.001$) for the HC cohort and $\rho = 0.22$ ($p < 0.001$) for the combined cohort of persons at risk, individuals with PD, and HCs. Following age-correction, the correlation became non-significant for the HC cohort ($\rho \approx 0.05$, $p > 0.05$) and was substantially reduced in the combined cohort ($\rho = 0.10$, $p < 0.05$).

These results justified the use of a linear model to remove the age-related effect from the digital scores. This correction is critical for improving the generalizability of the models, as it ensures that the estimated slowness of movement reflects the underlying “PD symptoms” rather than the confounding influence of normal aging, thereby providing more accurate and clinically relevant measurements.

Figure 37 Correlation between Age and Estimated Digital Slowness of Movement Scores on the Verily Dataset. The top row displays the original digital slowness of movement scores, while the bottom row shows the age-corrected scores. The left-side plots focus on the HC cohort, and the right-side plots include the combined person at risk, PD, and HC cohorts.

Results from the external validation of the model (trained with the Verily Study Watch dataset) on the MJFF-LRS and dBM-DEV study datasets are presented in

Table 40. The table includes the resulting Spearman correlation coefficients between the estimated digital scores and the corresponding clinical scores.

For the MJFF LRS dataset, the results were consistent with the cross-validation performance on the Verily dataset, exhibiting strong associations ($\rho = 0.69$ to 0.84 , $p < 0.05$). **Figure 38** and **Figure 39** show the correlation between the individual predictions and the clinical scores for the most affected limb (GENEActiv) and the least affected limb (Pebble), respectively. The strong performance across two wearable devices ($p > 0.69$) demonstrates the generalisability and robustness of the slowness of movement model to an external cohort with similar clinical characteristics, albeit with higher average disease severity (Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III: 44.25 vs. 27.9).

The performance on the dBM-DEV dataset was comparable ($\rho = 0.60$, $p < 0.05$). **Figure 40** shows the individual predictions and the association with the clinical scores. Even though the average MDS-UPDRS Part III score of the dBM-DEV was relatively lower than the initial PwPD

cohort (20.54 ± 9.06 vs 27.9 ± 12.8), the model exhibited similar performance. Notably, even under different hardware, geographical location and observation period.

Table 40 Spearman correlation of digital slowness of movement score with the corresponding clinical score in the MJFF-LRS and dBM-DEV study datasets obtained by the slowness of movement models trained on the Verily Study Watch dataset.

Dataset	Slowness of movement estimator target	Model Type	Spearman correlation coefficient (significance)
MJFF LRS (Most affected limb)	Slowness of movement composite score	Digital	0.69 ($p < 0.05$)
MJFF LRS (Least affected limb)	Slowness of movement composite score	Digital	0.84 ($p < 0.05$)
dBM-DEV (dominant hand for HC or most affected limb for PwPD)	Slowness of movement composite score	Digital with Age Correction	0.61 ($p < 0.05$)

Figure 38 Association between digital and clinical slowness of movement scores in the MJFF-LRS dataset, for the wearable worn on the most affected limb (GENEActiv). This scatter plot illustrates the relationship between the estimated digital scores and the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement clinical scores. The solid line represents the linear regression fit, and the shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval.

Figure 39 Association between digital and clinical slowness of movement scores in the MJFF-LRS dataset, for the wearable worn on the least affected limb (Pebble). This scatter plot illustrates the relationship between the estimated digital scores and the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement clinical scores. The solid line represents the linear regression fit, and the shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval.

Figure 40 Correlation between digital and clinical slowness of movement scores in the dBM-DEV dataset. This scatter plot illustrates the relationship between the estimated digital scores and the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement clinical scores. The solid line represents the linear regression fit, and the shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval.

8.3.3 Test-Retest Reliability

We assessed the test-retest reliability of the extracted movement-based features used as input to the model, using the dBM-DEV dataset. The feature demonstrated excellent reliability (ICC ≥ 0.90) across all interval sizes, with stable performance observed even at the shortest 3-day window. These results indicate that the extracted movement-based metrics provide highly

consistent and reproducible measurements over time. The reliability trajectories of the features are shown in **Figure 41**, illustrating minimal variation across intervals and confirming the robustness of these features for longitudinal modelling.

Figure 41 Test-retest reliability of the slowness of movement score and its features used at the estimator across varying time intervals. Each panel displays the ICC reliability coefficients (y-axis) as a function of interval size in days (x-axis), calculated from non-overlapping consecutive windows. The dotted line connects reliability values across intervals, with shaded areas representing 95% confidence intervals. The number displayed in each panel represents the reliability coefficient at the maximum interval size evaluated.

8.3.4 Intraday profiling and longitudinal evolution

We conducted an exploratory analysis of intraday slowness of movement patterns in the dBM-DEV study dataset, by aggregating the predictions from the entire monitoring period into 10-minute intervals and calculating mean scores. We limited the time period from 07:00 to 22:00. **Figure 42** demonstrates distinct diurnal patterns across cohorts, with PD participants showing the highest movement slowness scores (2.5-3.2) and greatest variability throughout the day,

while HC participants maintained consistently lower scores (1.5-1.7). The RBD only cohort exhibited intermediate slowness patterns (1.7-2.0 range) with moderate daily fluctuation.

Figure 42 Intraday Digital Slowness of Movement. This figure displays the mean intraday digital slowness of movement scores from the dBM-DEV study dataset, stratified by cohort. The shaded areas represent the Standard Error of the Mean (SEM), for the Healthy Control (HC), Parkinson's Disease (PD), and REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD) only cohorts.

In addition to intraday patterns, we examined longitudinal evolution of slowness of movement scores following the methodology from Section 7.3.2 by predicting values using data up to the reference point. Due to data availability, individual trajectories were aggregated by cohort. **Figure 43** shows that PD participants maintained consistently higher slowness scores throughout the 30-day period compared to RBD only and HC cohorts, with all groups demonstrating relatively stable trajectories over time. The shaded confidence intervals indicate greater variability in the RBD only cohort compared to the more consistent patterns observed in HC and PD groups.

(HC), Parkinson's Disease (PD), and REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD) only cohorts.

8.4 Discussion

8.4.1 Interpretation

We implemented and evaluated a slowness of movement assessment pipeline based on wrist accelerometry by extending the work of (Mahadevan, et al., 2020). Two digital scores indicative of slowness of movement were investigated. Both scores demonstrated moderate to high correlation with the associated clinical scores, showing that they are indicative of symptom severity. Further analysis showed that the digital scores are well associated with different clinical severity levels. However, the slowness of movement estimator developed based on a composite clinical score led to scores that were statistically significant between all clinical severity levels. This slowness of movement score was subjected to further evaluation and external validation.

Figure 43 Longitudinal evolution of Digital Slowness of Movement. This plot illustrates the mean digital slowness of movement scores for the different cohorts in the dBM-DEV study dataset over a 30-day period following enrolment. The shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval (CI), demonstrating the overall longitudinal progression and uncertainty in scores for the Healthy Control

The strong correlation of the digital slowness of movement score with the corresponding clinical score was replicated in the MJFF dataset and the dBM-DEV dataset, pointing to both hardware-agnostic and region-agnostic validity. It must be highlighted that the Verily Study Watch dataset was collected in the US using the Verily Study watch, the MJFF-LRS was captured in the US using the GENEActiv and Pebble wearables, while dBM-DEV was collected in France, Germany and Spain, using the Garming Vivoactive 5 smartwatch.

Further analysis in the dBM-DEV study dataset, showed good test-retest reliability of both the digital slowness of movement score and of the input acceleration features, while intraday and longitudinal patterns of the score demonstrated plausible relationships between the three groups of the dBM-DEV study, i.e., healthy controls, persons with RBD, and persons with PD, with the latter exhibiting higher overall scores.

8.4.2 Innovation beyond state of the art

Slowness of movement tracking using wrist accelerometry is implemented through a multi-stage pipeline that detects relevant motor contexts and estimates digital bradykinesia scores from wearable accelerometer data collected in free-living conditions. The approach first identifies hand movement and filters out gait-related segments to isolate upper-limb activity, after which motion features are extracted from short temporal windows and used to estimate a composite clinical score reflecting bradykinesia and rigidity. The resulting digital score demonstrated strong correlations with clinical MDS-UPDRS motor scores across multiple datasets, including correlations of up to $r = 0.69$ in the MJFF Levodopa Response Study and $r = 0.60$ in the AI-PROGNOSIS dBM-DEV dataset. Beyond reproducing clinical motor scores, the framework introduces a context-aware estimation strategy that separates different motor states (gait vs. upper-limb movement), enabling more accurate estimation of bradykinesia during natural daily activities. This represents an important step toward continuous and ecologically valid monitoring of motor slowing in Parkinson's disease using unobtrusive wearable sensors.

8.4.3 Limitations and further insights

A key limitation of the analysis is the use of averaged upper limb clinical scores as targets due to the lack of information regarding the hand wearing the accelerometer device in the Verily Study Watch cohort. Additionally, the impact of medication and the intra-day fluctuations of the score have not been fully scrutinized. The small sample size and limited duration of the external datasets hindered the ability to thoroughly evaluate the pipeline's discriminatory performance for symptom severity and longitudinal symptom tracking. Furthermore, the lack of information regarding the side at which the accelerometer was worn did not allow for a more detailed analysis with respect to the unilateral nature of PD. A broader issue arises from the fact that wrist-based movement signals capture a wide spectrum of everyday behaviours that do not always map cleanly onto the clinical notion of "slowness." Daily activities vary in rhythm, amplitude, and purpose, and these contextual fluctuations can influence the acceleration patterns used to derive the digital score. The short observation windows available in the external datasets also limit the ability to examine how the score behaves across different parts of the day, during periods of fatigue, or around medication cycles, factors known to shape movement quality in real-world settings. Even so, the consistency of the associations across devices, countries, and study cohorts suggests that the signal is capturing a stable behavioural signature. We aim to address certain of those limitations by testing the slowness of movement dBM on the long-term and enriched data of the AI-PMP study of the project.

8.4.4 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

dBMs from wrist worn sensors offer a way to complement PD care. Such biomarkers can capture slowness of movement in real word settings. In general, the implemented wrist-accelerometry dBM of slowness of movement can be used for continuous and unobtrusive monitoring in daily life. This can support earlier detection of symptom changes, accurate and robust assessment of treatment effectiveness and improved monitoring of disease progression. In the context of AI-PROGNOSIS, the digital score and/or its constituent features are planned to be used as input to the PD risk and progression predictive models, while the score will also be included in the monitoring capabilities of the mAI-Insights platform for healthcare professionals.

8.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Slowness of upper limb movement 2. Global spontaneity of movement (slowness, hesitancy, small amplitude, and poverty of movement in general)
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital score of the severity of slowness of movement derived from three-axis wrist acceleration 2. Digital score of the severity of slowness and lack of spontaneity of movement derived from three-axis wrist acceleration
Validation	Type: Real world Primary measures of validation: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spearman correlation of digital score of slowness of movement with composite score computed as the sum of averaged upper limb rigidity (MDS-UPDRS items 3.3b, 3.3c), averaged hand pronation-supination (MDS-UPDRS items 3.6a, 3.6b), and

	<p>global spontaneity of movement (MDS-UPDRS item 3.14) clinical scores</p> <p>2. Spearman correlation of digital score of spontaneity of movement with global spontaneity of movement (MDS-UPDRS item 3.14) clinical score</p>
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough • Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated in unaffected controls and PD patients with an average (std) MDS-UPDRS Part III score of 27.9 (12.8) and average (std) disease onset of 5.78 (2.45) years. • Uses three-axis accelerometer data sampled at ≥ 25 Hz. • Measurement takes place when the subject is wearing the device, moves their hands, and is not walking.

9 Comprehensive motor function active assessment

9.1 Background and objectives

PD, as a neurodegenerative condition, is characterized by a progression that leads to increasing challenges with motor skills, including, but not limited to, issues with posture, balance, leg agility, and gait. The advent of digital tools for PD assessment contributes to the growing body of research that looks at how technology might monitor these challenges and improve the management of the condition. A systematic review of the use of digital tools to assess posture and balance can be found in “Section 2.3.8 Digital assessments of posture and balance” of Deliverable D2.3 “Initial report on domain review and datasets”.

Inexpensive sensors, such as cameras and smartphones hold promise for home-based monitoring, as highlighted by (Dias et al., 2020a), (Dias et al., 2020b). Recent advancements include the development of intelligent motor assessment tools and depth camera-based systems (e.g., Microsoft Kinect) for differentiating PD stages and to capture body motion (Dias et al., 2020a), (Dias et al., 2020b), (Dias et al., 2020c), (Dranca et al., 2018). Additionally, smartphone-based depth sensors and skeleton tracking in three-dimensional space, have shown promise, offering enhanced precision and accuracy in motion analysis (Abe et al., 2022). Video recording, coupled with pose estimation tools, such as AlphaPose (Fang et al., 2017), has also been utilized to extract human joint coordinates (Abe et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2021). However, to fully realize the potential of digital health solutions for PD management, continued research and collaboration in this sector are needed.

Building upon these technical developments, we aim to investigate and validate an approach for active balance and posture digital assessment in individuals with PD. The ultimate goal is to define new dBMs of posture and balance, by combining camera-based body tracking and a motor function test that is simple to set up and easy to use. For designing the test, we focused on relevant MDS-UPDRS (Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale) Part III items that are essential for assessing gross motor function, such as leg agility, rising from a chair, walking, and posture. These clinical assessment items are standardised markers of posture and balance that constitute key motor aspects of PD (Jankovic, 2008). By designing a Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT), that makes use of modified MDS-UPDRS-

related motor tasks, and combining it with continuous video-based pose tracking, we aim to obtain deeper, yet clinically relevant, insights into the motor aspects assessed by these items.

The CMFT was designed with two primary goals in mind: a) to ensure it can be easily set up in a home, work, or hospital environment using only a smartphone, a stand, and a chair, and b) to make it acceptable and easy for persons with PD to perform (or with the recommended support of caregiver).

The CMFT was developed with data collected from a small cohort of persons with PD and will be further refined and validated in the dBM-DEV study of the project.

9.2 Methods

The CMFT focuses on the automated assessment of specific items of the MDS-UPDRS Part III, namely “item 3.8” (leg agility), “item 3.9” (arising from chair), “item 3.13” (posture) and “item 3.10” (gait), shown in **Figure 44**, leveraging smartphone camera-based pose tracking.

Figure 44 Camera recordings from CMFT corresponding to four MDS-UPDRS items for assessing motor skills: (a) item 3.8 (Leg agility), (b) item 3.9 (Arising from chair), (c) item 3.13 (Posture), (d) item 3.10 (Gait).

To simplify the capturing procedure and facilitate the execution of the test, users are instructed to perform the movements underlying the MDS-UPDRS items of interest in a sequence, one after the other. The MDS-UPDRS guidelines were followed as closely as possible; however, some minor changes were inevitably required, as in the self-test case, the user may have to capture the video alone, without support from a carer or physician. The following outline the four movements encompassed in the CMFT:

- Leg agility (item 3.8): Initially, the patient should sit in a straight-backed chair with arms and have both feet comfortably on the floor. The patient should then raise and stomp each foot (first the right foot and then the left) on the ground 10 times as high and as fast as possible.
- Arising from chair (item 3.9): Then the user should cross their arms across the chest and try to stand up. If the user does not succeed, they should attempt again up to two times, and if they are still unsuccessful, they can try to push off using their hands on the arms of the chair.

- Posture (item 3.13): After standing up, the patient is asked to stand still for 5 seconds, so that their posture can be assessed.
- Gait (item 3.10): After completing the posture task, the patient should take 3 steps away from the chair, then turn around and return towards the chair, taking again 3 steps. Although the original MDS-UPDRS test requires the patient to walk for at least 10m, this test was adapted due to the limited field of view of the camera in the test set-up.

9.2.1 Datasets

As mentioned in deliverable D3.1, a cohort of 32 PD patients were recruited in the Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki (Thessaloniki, Greece) and in the Northern Greece Parkinson's Disease Association (Thessaloniki, Greece) in the first phase of the Papanikolaou-CMFT study, which was approved by the scientific board of the Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki (Thessaloniki, Greece). All participants provided written informed consent and voluntarily participated in the study. Each participant performed the CMFT, while being recorded by a smartphone, either in the hospital or in the facilities of the association.

In the second phase of the study (January-June 2024), 22 additional PD patients were recruited under the same conditions as in the first phase and performed the CMFT test (most of them multiple times), yielding 53 video recordings. Twenty (20) of these recordings were discarded for various reasons, e.g., patient moving outside the field of view, patient experiencing freezing of gait during the recording (since the CMFT protocol requires patients to take exactly 3 steps forward/back-also freezing of gait is assessed as a different item 3.11), and/or errors in skeleton tracking by the pose tracking algorithm used, i.e., the MediaPipe Pose Landmarker, (e.g., due to the entrance/presence of other subjects in the field of view). Thus, 33 recordings were added to the 17 recordings from the first phase, yielding 50 recordings in total. As in the first phase, each movement in the video recordings was rated/annotated by two independent neurologists of the Papanikolaou hospital based on the MDS-UPDRS items of interest (a 0-4 score for each item). Annotations ranged between 0-3 per item; no movement was rated as 4 (severe). Demographics and scoring distributions for each item are presented in **Table 41**.

Table 41 Demographics and clinical characteristics of the participants in the CMFT development study (Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset)

Demographics	Data
Patients # (Recordings #)	PD: 39 (50)
Women # (%)	10 (26%)
Avg. age in years (std)	69.70 (5.52)
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	13.30 (7.96)
Men # (%)	29 (74%)
Avg. age in years (std)	69.03 (10.82)
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	8,86 (4.49)
Clinical scoring characteristics	Histograms of scores (0/1/2/3)
Item 3.8L	5/13/18/14
Item 3.8R	7/17/13/13

Item 3.9	29/14/7/0
Item 3.13	2/24/22/2
Item 3.10F	24/15/7/4
Item 3.10B	23/14/8/5

We further evaluated the CMFT algorithms on the recordings (sequences of 3D Pose landmarks) collected by participants of the dBM-DEV study that performed the test through the app of the study (mAI-Health). Sixty-nine 69 CMFT sessions have been performed in total by 29 participants. In methodology and results presented below, manual segmentation of motor items from the landmark sequences and extraction of angle-based features was mainly used, resulting to 47 valid tests by 21 participants from all three groups (persons with RBD, healthy controls (HC) and persons with PD). On the other hand, automated segmentation resulted to 28 valid tests by 15 participants, for which “clinically meaningful” displacement-based features could be obtained for motor items 3.8R and 3.8L. Demographics are presented in **Table 42**.

Table 42 Demographics and clinical characteristics of the participants in the dBM-DEV study. RBD: person with RBD; HC: healthy control; PD: person with PD.

Demographics	Manual segmentation	Automated segmentation (only for items 3.8R, 3.8L)
Patients # (Recordings #)	RBD: 4(7), HC: 5(6), PD: 12(34)	RBD: 2(4), HC: 3(5), PD: 10(19)
Women # (%)	9 (43%)	6 (40%)
Avg. age in years (std)	62.11 (10.39)	67.50 (6.22)
Men # (%)	12 (67%)	9 (60%)
Avg. age in years (std)	66.00 (7.83)	64.78 (7.14)
Clinical scoring characteristics	Histograms of scores (0/1/2/3)	Histograms of scores (0/1/2/3)
Item 3.8R	28/18/0/0	15/13/0/0
Item 3.8L	31/16/0/0	22/5/1/0
Item 3.9	44/3/0/0	-
Item 3.13	31/14/0/0	-
Item 3.10F	23/23/1/0	
Item 3.10B	23/23/1/0	-

9.2.2 Data preprocessing

CMFT combines the associated movements of the aforementioned MDS-UPDRS items in a sequence with the following order: right foot stomping (item 3.8R), left foot stomping (item 3.8L), arising from a chair (item 3.9), standing still for 5 s (item 3.13), 3 steps forward (adjusted item 3.10F), turn (item 3.10T), take 3 steps returning to the chair (adjusted item 3.10B). The same data processing pipeline (**Figure 45**), described in Deliverable D3.1 was used for training and validation using the video recordings of patients from Papanikolaou-CMFT study assessment, captured at a rate of 30 frames per second (fps).

The video recording of each participant was split into frames and the 3-D body pose landmarks in each frame were detected using the MediaPipe Pose Landmarker (**Figure 45**). Landmarks

were then used to compute time series for a set of joint angles that are relevant to each motor item, as shown in **Table 43**.

These time series for each motor item are then pre-processed and used to compute a set of movement features that potentially correlate with the corresponding clinical score. Specifically, to reduce noise effects (e.g., MediaPipe pose detection errors), each time series was filtered using a Butterworth low-pass filter to remove high frequencies. An 8Hz cut-off value was selected, followed by the subtraction of the mean value (DC term) for normalisation purposes.

Figure 45 Data processing pipeline for training and validation of the CMFT using video recordings of patients from Papanikolaou-CMFT study.

Figure 46 Mediapipe body landmark locations

Table 43 Joint angles that are relevant to each MDS-UPDRS item included in CMFT.

Item	Relevant joint angle(s)
Right foot stomping (3.8R)	KNEE_R (landmark 26)
Left foot stomping (3.8L)	KNEE_L (landmark 25)
Arising from chair (3.9)	HIP_C (angle formed at midpoint between hips (landmarks 23,24) with respect to a) the midpoint of shoulders (landmarks 11,12) and b) midpoint of knees (landmarks (25,26)
Posture (3.13)	
Walking forward (3.10F), walking back (3.10B)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BETWEEN_LEGS (angle formed at midpoint between hips (landmarks 23,24) with respect to: a) right knee (landmark 26) and b) left knee (landmarks 25)),

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SHOULDER_L (landmark 11): angle formed with respect to: a) left elbow (landmark 13) and b) left hip point (landmark 23), • SHOULDER_R (landmark 12): angle formed with respect to: a) right elbow (landmark 14) and b) right hip point (landmark 24)
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Regarding the data recorded from patients performing the CMFT during the dBM-DEV study using the mAI-Health app, a slightly modified data processing pipeline, illustrated in **Figure 47** was used. In this case, a database query was used to retrieve the sequence of the 3D Pose Landmarks recorded by the app during a specific CMFT performance by a patient. These sequences - in contrast to video recordings from the Papanikolaou CMFT study - were recorded at lower frame rates than 30 fps and sampling was non-uniform for practical reasons. For this reason, we used 1-D cubic spline interpolation to resample the dBM-DEV study sequences at 30fps using uniform sampling, before applying the subsequent processing steps, which are common in both pipelines, namely feature selection and ML classification to predict each clinical motor item score.

Figure 47 Data processing pipeline of the CMFT for validation using the dBM-DEV study.

9.2.3 Digital biomarkers

Movement segmentation

CMFT combines the associated movements of multiple MDS-UPDRS items in a sequence with the following order: right foot stomping (item 3.8R), left foot stomping (item 3.8L), arising from a chair (item 3.9), standing still for 5 s (item 3.13), take 3 steps forward (adjusted item 3.10F), turn (back towards the chair) and take 3 steps returning to the chair (adjusted item 3.10B). The detected 33 MediaPipe Pose Landmarks are shown in **Figure 46**.

In D3.1 (Section 10.2.3), an automated segmentation methodology was introduced to identify each movement's first and last frame from the continuous sequence of detected body landmarks. However, significant modifications were required to improve efficiency and robustness as well as to resolve certain issues raised when processing the additional recordings (from the second phase of CMFT study as well as the validation using data from dBM-DEV study). Such issues include: a) depending on the camera and chair setup, participants may appear in the camera to walk towards the chair either from left to right or from right to left, b) some people may start stomping with the left foot (3.8L) and others with the right foot (3.8R). This modified algorithm (based on the x and y coordinates of the detected landmarks) is briefly described below (an indicative final result for a recording is illustrated in **Figure 48**):

- a) In order to properly deal with both possible camera-chair configurations (chair located at the left or the right of each frame), we measure the average feet orientation $d=(d_R+d_L)/2$, where $d_R=x_{32}-x_{30}$ for right foot and $d_L=x_{31}-x_{29}$ for left foot (see **Figure 46**). As the sign of d normally changes when the user turns, we expect that the first change point corresponds to the frame when the user turns after taking 3 steps forward (T_{turn}). Similarly, the second change point should correspond to the frame when the user turns again preparing to sit at the chair, marking the end of the sequence to be analysed (T_{end}). Hence, to detect these important time instants (frames), we detect the first two zero-crossings of d . However, in some cases additional zero-crossings may occur, e.g., if the patient changes the direction of his feet when sitting or due to MediaPipe pose landmark detection errors. To deal with this issue, we calculate the distance between consecutive zero-crossings and cluster together points that are close to each other. In this way, T_{turn} and T_{end} are robustly detected in all dataset samples, while, in addition, the patient movement direction (left-to-right or right-to-left) is also identified based in the sign before the first turning point.
- b) As some time is required for the user to complete the first turn, we can obtain estimates of $T_{end_gait_forward}$ (end time of forward gait item) and $T_{start_gait_back}$ (start time of backward gait item) as follows: a) we compute the mean value m_i of each of the two parts $i=1,2$ (before and after T_{turn}) (b) starting from T_{turn} , we iterate over each previous (next) frame, computing the difference $d-m_0$ ($d-m_1$) until its sign changes, identifying $T_{end_gait_forward}$ ($T_{start_gait_backward}$), respectively. The “gait backward” period ($T_{start_gait_backward}$, T_{end}) corresponds to **3.10B**(backward) item.
- c) Split the time period (T_{start} , T_{turn}) of the y-coordinate of the midpoint between hips: $c_y=(y_{24}+y_{23})/2$ time series into two phases (sitting, standing) by applying binary segmentation (Fryzlewicz, 2014), implemented in the raptures Python library (Truong, 2020).
- d) The transition period (T_{start_rising} , T_{end_rising}) corresponds to motor item **3.9** (arising from the chair) and is estimated using a similar procedure as (b): we first compute the mean value m_i of each of the two parts $i=1,2$ and then starting from the identified change point we iterate over each previous (next) frame, computing the difference c_y-m_0 (c_y-m_1) until its sign changes, identifying T_{start_rising} (T_{end_rising}), respectively.
- e) Detect stomping of the left foot within the sitting phase (up to T_{start_rising}), by estimating prominent peaks in the y-coordinate of right ankle (y_{28}) time series. Specifically, we sort peaks by their prominence and select the first 10 peaks, which typically correspond to the maximum foot raise in each of the 10 stomps that the patient is instructed to perform. This approach is seen to robustly identify most of the stomps in the dataset. To deal with specific cases where some stomps are missed or other foot movements are detected, we calculate the difference between consecutive peaks, define clusters based on these differences and keep only the cluster with the most members. This cluster corresponds to the motor item **3.8R** (right foot stomping), while it provides clinically meaningful features (e.g. max/min/mean/std of maximum foot raise time series or max/min/mean/std of time difference between consecutive stomps).
- f) Similarly, detect stomping of the left foot within the sitting phase (up to T_{start_rising}), by estimating prominent peaks in the y-coordinate of left ankle (y_{27}) time series. The stomping part corresponds to motor item **3.8L** (left foot stomping), while clinically meaningful features can be estimated as in (e) above. Notably, by analysing the left and right stomping independently, we a) allow the patient to start with either foot and b) we can even efficiently filter-out involuntary smaller movements of one foot during stomping with the other foot (observed in some recordings).

- g) Split the standing phase (T_{end_rising} , $T_{end_gait_forward}$) into two phases a) “stand still”, corresponding to motor item **3.13** (Posture), and b) “gait forward”, corresponding to motor item **3.10F** (gait), based on the x -coordinate of the midpoint between hips $c_x=(y_{24}+y_{23})/2$ time series. Again, we apply binary segmentation to identify the change point $T_{start_gait_forward}$. The “stand still” period (T_{end_rising} , $T_{start_gait_forward}$) corresponds to motion item **3.13**(posture), while the “gait forward” period ($T_{start_gait_forward}$, $T_{end_gait_forward}$) corresponds to **3.10F**(forward).

The performance of the above algorithm was tested with recordings made both from Papanikolaou-CMFT and dBM-DEV study and was seen to be very satisfactory in most cases. As seen in an example from Papanikolaou-CMFT recordings (**Figure 48**), manual annotation (dotted lines) coincides with automated segmentation (solid lines), especially for items **3.8L** (red) and **3.8R** (green), while for **3.9**, **3.13** and the two gait items (**3.10F**, **3.10B**), automated segmentation seems much more accurate (and consistent) than manual segmentation.

Figure 48 Time series of x and y coordinates of the detected landmarks of a user (with ID=8 and clinical UPDRS scores for the six items of CMFT 1,2,0,2,2,2, respectively) that performed the CMFT movement sequence; ($center_x$, $center_y$) are the coordinates of the midpoint between hips (landmarks 23 and 24). Dotted vertical lines indicate manual annotation into the motor items shown in the labels, while solid lines indicate the results of automatic annotation, based on the proposed algorithm. Red/Green crosses indicate the peaks in y -coordinate of right/left ankles.

Feature extraction

As already mentioned, we opted for features based exclusively on joint angles (instead of displacements), to reduce the dependency on factors, such as a) camera angle, b) distance of patient from the camera, and c) human body size/shape variations. Hence, for each movement segment (corresponding to an MDS-UPDRS item), a set of relevant joint angles was identified and measured. Further details can be found in deliverable D3.1 (Section 10.2.3 – Digital biomarkers).

As an alternative, we exploited the approach described in “Movement segmentation” subsection above to obtain “clinically meaningful” displacement-based features (according to MDS-UPDRS guidelines for each item) for items 3.8L, 3.8R. Specifically, we have used eight (8) features based on the detected peaks (location and height), aiming to align with the rating guidelines for the particular items: a) min/max/mean/variance of (peak height-floor_level) (to

identify amplitude decrements) and b) min/max/mean/variance of consecutive peak distances (to identify slow or irregular rhythm). Floor level can be estimated as the minimum of the ankle time series within the peaks. In order to compensate with different camera setups, we have normalized the distances with the estimated knee-ankle Euclidean distances (as estimated by MediaPipe). Notably, the peak selection and clustering approach was designed (and verified in all our results) so as to do “minimal harm”, as only valid peaks are being selected, while rare cases of “missed valid peaks” do not affect the feature values significantly. Future work may include defining other similar “clinically meaningful” features for other motor items.

As an alternative feature extraction approach, we have also obtained results using the same time series of relevant joint angles using tsfresh (Time Series Feature Extraction based on Scalable Hypothesis tests) (Christ et al, 2018), a Python library used for automated feature extraction from time series data. In this way, we can efficiently calculate several statistical features, such as mean, variance, autocorrelation, and entropy. In addition, as in certain items certain features could not properly be computed, due to the limited number of frames, tsfresh supports imputation to deal with these missing values. Finally, it can select only those features that are statistically relevant to the target variable.

Machine learning and MDS-UPDRS item score classification

We trained ML models to predict the MDS-UPDRS item scores based on the feature vectors computed for each associated movement. Five classifiers were employed, i.e., K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), principal component analysis (PCA) in combination with KNN, and supervised PCA (sPCA) (Ghojogh, 2019) in combination with KNN.

Following the proposed methodology, an additional feature selection step was used to further improve performance. Specifically, for each item, we measured the correlation of each extracted feature with the corresponding clinical score. We sorted the results to define a subset of $N < F$ features with the largest correlations. The hyperparameter N was experimentally selected to maximise performance: $N=6$ for items 3.8, 3.9 and 3.13 and $N=9$ for gait items (3.10F and 3.10B).

Validation of ML classifiers was performed using the Leave-One-Subject-Out cross-validation approach, and relevant metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 scores) were computed.

Furthermore, as the final model should be available for further validation using results from both studies, we opted to use an 80/20 stratified train/test split of the Papanikolaou-CMFT study, so that each set contains balanced numbers of patients from each class. Finally, we used all data from dBM-DEV study for additional validation of the models.

For each classifier, we optimized a few important parameters using k-fold validation using grid search based on the training set: i) KNN: `n_neighbors(1-5)`, `weights(distance/uniform)`, ii) SVM: `C(1/10/100)` and `kernel (rbf/linear)`, `degree(2/3)`, iii) RF: `n_estimators (100/200)`, `max_depth(None/10)`, `min_samples_split (2/5)`, `min_samples_leaf (1/2)` iv) PCA+KNN/sPCA+KNN: `n_components (2/3)`, `n_neighbors(1-5)`, `weights(distance/uniform)`. For detailed descriptions for these hyperparameters we refer the reader to the python implementations of the ML classifiers⁶.

⁶ <https://scikit-learn.org>

As an alternative deep learning classification approach based exclusively on skeleton dynamics, we have also tested the approach of (Yan et al., 2018). This approach, previously proposed for action recognition, exploits the fact that human skeletons can naturally be represented as graphs (where the pose landmarks are the nodes and connections between them are edges) that evolves over time (temporal dimension). In order to jointly capture spatial and temporal dependencies, a *Spatial-Temporal Graph Convolutional Network (ST-GCN)* is used, where a graph of body joints connected by “spatial edges” is computed in each frame and “Temporal edges” connect the same joint across consecutive frames, forming a temporal dimension in the graph. Graph convolution is then applied on this graph to jointly capture spatial and temporal patterns, based on spatial and temporal neighbours of each node.

To apply this approach for CMFT, we create spatial graphs using either the entire skeleton (33 Pose Landmarks) for **3.9** and **3.13** or only the lower part of Mediapipe (10 Pose Landmarks including hips, knees and ankles) for **3.8R**, **3.8L** and **3.10**, setting as target variable the score for each item.

9.3 Results

9.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers

Initially, a feature correlation analysis was conducted to examine the association between the selected kinematic features and clinical scores. Specifically, Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient (ρ) along with corresponding significance were computed for each feature. Features were then ranked according to each index and three features with very high correlations in both indices were identified for each motor item. Corresponding boxplots are presented in **Figure 49**, providing a graphical representation of the distribution of each feature’s values across clinical scores, which may lead to useful insights regarding their suitability for estimating the score using machine learning methods. First, we observe monotonical trends for most features, however in many cases overlaps in feature values exist which are expected to impact negatively the classification performance. Also in some cases, e.g. **3.8R**, selected features that are indeed clinically relevant, such as “angle_min” (the minimum angle corresponds to the knee angle at the highest knee position as the starting angle is the reference) and “angle_range” (“angle_max”-“angle_min”), violate this monotonicity (class 0 boxplot). This is expected to negatively impact classification, which is also confirmed by the LOSO validation results presented below.

Figure 49 Boxplots of selected features having highest correlation with clinical scores for each item.

Results from training and validating the models are presented below. As in D3.1, the feature selection step was seen to improve performance in all cases, so we only present detailed results using the selected features. Features kept after the feature selection step for each item along with the corresponding Spearman correlation and significance, are presented in **Table 44**.

Table 44 Features with maximum correlation kept for each motion item

Item	Feature	Spearman Correlation	Significance
3.8R	angle_min	0.53	6.72e-05
	angle_range	-0.51	1.84e-04
	speed_quartile_range	-0.49	3.34e-04
	speed_stdev	-0.48	4.78 e-04
	accel_median	0.46	7.13 e-04
	accel_max	-0.46	7.39 e-04
3.8L	speed_quartile_range	-0.72	4.39 e-09
	speed_stdev	-0.70	1.13 e-08
	accel_stdev	-0.66	1.59 e-07
	speed_range	-0.62	1.70 e-06
	speed_max	-0.61	2.20 e-06
	accel_max	-0.6	3.30 e-06
3.9	angle_filtered_dom_freq_value	-0.63	1.20 e-06
	speed_min	0.58	1.06 e-05
	speed_mean	0.54	5.77 e-05
	speed_stdev	-0.53	8.74 e-05
	speed_quartile_range	-0.52	9.29 e-05
	angle_filtered_mean_cross_rate	-0.52	1.11 e-04
3.13	accel_min	-0.46	1.32 e-03
	accel_range	0.45	1.68 e-03
	accel_stdev	0.44	2.39 e-03
	accel_max	0.43	3.14 e-03
	speed_median	0.42	3.76 e-03
	speed_max	0.42	4.10 e-03
3.10F	thigh_angle_range	-0.51	1.39 e-04
	thigh_speed_stdev	-0.50	2.17 e-04
	armR_angle_filtered_dom_freq_ratio	0.49	2.71 e-04
	thigh_angle_filtered_rms	-0.48	4.54 e-04
	thigh_angle_stdev	-0.48	4.54 e-04
	thigh_accel_max	-0.47	5.73 e-04
	thigh_angle_min	0.47	6.10 e-04
	thigh_speed_quartile_range	-0.44	1.24 e-03
	thigh_angle_quartile_range	-0.44	1.33 e-03
3.10B	thigh_speed_stdev	-0.64	5.62 e-07
	thigh_angle_range	-0.64	6.84 e-07
	thigh_speed_quartile_range	-0.63	1.04 e-06

Item	Feature	Spearman Correlation	Significance
	thigh_angle_filtered_rms	-0.62	1.40 e-06
	thigh_angle_stdev	-0.62	1.40 e-06
	thigh_speed_min	0.62	1.42 e-06
	thigh_angle_min	0.61	2.65 e-06
	thigh_angle_quartile_range	-0.59	7.62 e-06
	thigh_speed_range	-0.53	7.58 e-05

As seen, feature selection is in most cases in line with corresponding clinical assessment criteria, e.g., in the case of **3.8** (leg agility), speed or acceleration variations are important features used by physicians for the clinical assessment.

In the following subsections, results are presented from baseline approach (angle-based features) as well as from the three alternative approaches described in Section 9.2 (displacement-based features, angle-based features using tsfresh and the ST-GCN skeleton-based approach).

Angle-based features (baseline approach)

Table 45 presents the accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for all assessment items and ML classifiers obtained using the LOSO cross-validation scheme. Best results for most items are obtained using the SVM or RF (Random Forest) approaches. Based on these validation results we can conclude that angular features yield moderate results for most items. For motor items 3.9 and 3.13, the improved performance may be partly attributed to the fact that the training set scores belong mainly on (three) classes (0-2), instead of four (0-3) classes for the other motor items (**Table 41**).

Table 45 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers derived from LOSO validation using SELECTED features. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold.

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.36	0.35	0.36	0.35
SVM	0.42	0.43	0.42	0.42
RF	0.48	0.42	0.48	0.45
PCA+KNN	0.4	0.39	0.4	0.39
sPCA+KNN	0.42	0.35	0.42	0.38
3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.52	0.54	0.52	0.53
SVM	0.48	0.47	0.48	0.47
RF	0.52	0.53	0.52	0.52
PCA+KNN	0.48	0.52	0.48	0.49
sPCA+KNN	0.48	0.5	0.48	0.49
3.9	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.68	0.64	0.68	0.65

SVM	0.74	0.72	0.74	0.73
RF	0.6	0.58	0.6	0.59
PCA+KNN	0.64	0.6	0.64	0.61
sPCA+KNN	0.64	0.59	0.64	0.6
3.13	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.65	0.59	0.65	0.62
SVM	0.67	0.62	0.67	0.64
RF	0.61	0.56	0.61	0.58
PCA+KNN	0.59	0.54	0.59	0.56
sPCA+KNN	0.61	0.59	0.61	0.6
3.10F	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.46	0.39	0.46	0.42
SVM	0.46	0.42	0.46	0.43
RF	0.46	0.41	0.46	0.44
PCA+KNN	0.46	0.37	0.46	0.41
sPCA+KNN	0.54	0.42	0.54	0.47
3.10B	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.42	0.39	0.42	0.4
SVM	0.46	0.43	0.46	0.44
RF	0.52	0.47	0.52	0.49
PCA+KNN	0.44	0.39	0.44	0.41
sPCA+KNN	0.38	0.34	0.38	0.36

The results generally follow the same pattern as the LOSO validation results; however, we can observe cases where specific classifiers perform much better than others, probably due to improved hyperparameter tuning.

Table 46 presents the accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for all assessment items and ML classifiers obtained for the held-out Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset. The results generally follow the same pattern as the LOSO validation results; however, we can observe cases where specific classifiers perform much better than others, probably due to improved hyperparameter tuning.

Table 46 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers obtained for the held-out Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset using SELECTED features. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold.

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
NN	0.5	0.47	0.5	0.47
SVM	0.8	0.88	0.8	0.78
RF	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.33
PCA+KNN	0.4	0.38	0.4	0.39
sPCA+KNN	0.4	0.35	0.4	0.37

3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.5	0.69	0.5	0.5
SVM	0.4	0.45	0.4	0.4
RF	0.4	0.43	0.4	0.37
PCA+KNN	0.4	0.43	0.4	0.37
sPCA+KNN	0.4	0.65	0.4	0.43
3.9	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.8	0.78	0.8	0.77
SVM	0.8	0.72	0.8	0.76
RF	0.5	0.47	0.5	0.49
PCA+KNN	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
sPCA+KNN	0.5	0.44	0.5	0.47
3.13	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.6	0.62	0.6	0.58
SVM	0.7	0.71	0.7	0.7
RF	0.6	0.62	0.6	0.58
PCA+KNN	0.7	0.71	0.7	0.7
sPCA+KNN	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
3.10F	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.6	0.58	0.6	0.51
SVM	0.6	0.46	0.6	0.5
RF	0.5	0.28	0.5	0.36
PCA+KNN	0.6	0.46	0.6	0.5
sPCA+KNN	0.5	0.28	0.5	0.36
3.10B	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.8	0.87	0.8	0.8
SVM	0.8	0.82	0.8	0.79
RF	0.9	0.95	0.9	0.9
PCA+KNN	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
sPCA+KNN	0.7	0.83	0.7	0.73

Table 47 presents the accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for all assessment items and ML classifiers obtained for the dBM-DEV study dataset. As seen, performance in 3.8L, 3.8R and 3.13 is extremely poor, but this can be largely explained by the fact that the score distributions in the training and dBM-DEV datasets are very different, e.g. notice the lack of samples with score 0 in **Table 41**, in contrast to **Table 42**, where class 0 is clearly the dominant class. Indeed, the Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset currently contains only PD patients (no HCs), in contrast to dBM-DEV dataset which contains a large number of HCs.

On the contrary, results for **3.9**, **3.10F** and **3.10B** are very satisfactory, as score distributions for these items are consistent for both datasets.

Table 47 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers obtained for the dBM-DEV study dataset using SELECTED features. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold.

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.20	0.36	0.20	0.20
SVM	0.17	0.39	0.17	0.21
RF	0.17	0.58	0.17	0.23
PCA+KNN	0.20	0.15	0.20	0.17
sPCA+KNN	0.26	0.42	0.26	0.31
3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.17	0.59	0.17	0.22
SVM	0.15	0.75	0.15	0.15
RF	0.15	0.09	0.15	0.11
PCA+KNN	0.19	0.58	0.19	0.22
sPCA+KNN	0.21	0.57	0.21	0.28
3.9	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.77	0.92	0.77	0.83
SVM	0.55	0.87	0.55	0.67
RF	0.60	0.91	0.60	0.70
PCA+KNN	0.53	0.90	0.53	0.65
sPCA+KNN	0.70	0.86	0.70	0.77
3.13	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.07	0.05	0.07	0.06
SVM	0.09	0.07	0.09	0.08
RF	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.08
PCA+KNN	0.07	0.05	0.07	0.05
sPCA+KNN	0.13	0.10	0.13	0.11
3.10F	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.62	0.64	0.62	0.61
SVM	0.70	0.69	0.70	0.69
RF	0.66	0.68	0.66	0.67
PCA+KNN	0.68	0.69	0.68	0.67
sPCA+KNN	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.71
3.10B	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.45	0.63	0.45	0.45

SVM	0.68	0.76	0.68	0.71
RF	0.66	0.72	0.66	0.68
PCA+KNN	0.51	0.61	0.51	0.55
sPCA+KNN	0.49	0.65	0.49	0.55

A plot presenting the contributions and importance of different features for the prediction of the held-out Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset (item **3.8R, SVM, F1=0.7**) is illustrated in **Figure 50**. As seen, the ranking of features with high importance is generally in line with the ranking of correlations with the clinical score (**Table 44**), with the exception of “accel_median”, which in the specific case seems to contribute significantly to the improved classification performance. As expected, larger acceleration values (changes in rhythm) tend to increase the model output (i.e., increase the predicted UPDRS value).

Figure 50 Relative importance of different features for the held-out set

Note that in all results presented above, features were obtained by manual movement segmentation. We used this approach as, unfortunately, many dBM-DEV recordings had issues (e.g., shaky recordings by handheld smartphones, CMFT protocol deviations such as skipping a motor item), which caused the automated movement segmentation (Section 9.2.3) algorithm to fail.

Displacement-based features

In order to evaluate the displacement-based features for motor items 3.8R and 3.8L, we first extracted features by automated movement segmentation using the Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset, where no automated movement segmentation errors were observed. We then performed a similar correlation analysis as for angle-based features and found that foot amplitude features (minh, maxh, meanh, varh) exhibit the highest Spearman correlations (0.5-0.6) with clinical scores **Table 46** presents the corresponding boxplots for the features with highest correlation for each motor item. We can observe that monotonicity trends are violated in some cases (esp. for class 0) and there are some overlaps in feature values between different classes, which are expected to affect the classification performance.

Figure 51 Boxplots of selected features having highest correlation with clinical scores for each item. Y axis – Score of item [0-3]

LOSO validation results using the displacement-based features are presented in **Table 48**. We can see that the performance is generally similar to angle-based features, as they both suffer from lack of training samples for class 0, as previously discussed. Displacement-based features are clinically meaningful as they directly measure the actual features to be assessed by clinicians (amplitude, rhythm) for the leg agility item. At the same time, they more prone to errors than angle-based features, especially when there is smartphone movement during recording that may cause errors in estimating the floor level and/or the peaks corresponding to highest foot locations.

Table 48 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores obtained from LOSO validation using clinically meaningful displacement-based features for items (3.8R, 3.8L) obtained from the Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset using automated motion segmentation.

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.34	0.37	0.34	0.35
SVM	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.48
RF	0.48	0.50	0.48	0.49
PCA+KNN	0.34	0.39	0.34	0.36
sPCA+KNN	0.42	0.46	0.42	0.42
3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.42
SVM	0.44	0.40	0.44	0.42
RF	0.38	0.36	0.38	0.37
PCA+KNN	0.34	0.30	0.34	0.32
sPCA+KNN	0.50	0.49	0.50	0.49

Table 49 presents the accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for all assessment items and ML classifiers obtained for the held-out Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset. As seen, the performance is similar as in the case of angle-based features.

Table 49 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers obtained for the held-out Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset using clinically meaningful displacement-based features. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold.

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.48
SVM	0.70	0.78	0.70	0.68
RF	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.59
PCA+KNN	0.60	0.53	0.60	0.53
sPCA+KNN	0.50	0.42	0.50	0.45
3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.30	0.28	0.30	0.29
SVM	0.50	0.53	0.50	0.50
RF	0.50	0.46	0.50	0.48
PCA+KNN	0.50	0.56	0.50	0.52
sPCA+KNN	0.50	0.56	0.50	0.52

Table 50 presents the accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for leg agility items using clinically meaningful displacement-based features and ML classifiers for the dBM-DEV study dataset. As in the case of angle-based features, performance is not satisfactory due to the large discrepancy between the score distribution in training and validation samples (especially for class 0).

Table 50 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers obtained for the dBM-DEV dataset using clinically meaningful displacement-based features. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold.

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.14	0.39	0.14	0.18
SVM	0.14	0.66	0.14	0.18
RF	0.18	0.70	0.18	0.22
PCA+KNN	0.18	0.15	0.18	0.17
sPCA+KNN	0.18	0.59	0.18	0.27
3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.05
SVM	0.18	0.79	0.18	0.25
RF	0.07	0.02	0.07	0.03
PCA+KNN	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.00
sPCA+KNN	0.11	0.79	0.11	0.13

Tsfresh-based features

Results using LOSO validation using tsfresh feature extraction, imputation and feature selection are presented in **Table 51**. These results are similar and/or inferior to the corresponding results of the adopted approach (**Table 45**), justifying our feature selection.

Table 51 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers derived from LOSO validation using tsfresh feature extraction, imputation and feature selection. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.32	0.25	0.32	0.28
SVM	0.40	0.35	0.40	0.37
RF	0.44	0.39	0.44	0.41
PCA+KNN	0.34	0.33	0.34	0.33
sPCA+KNN	0.34	0.32	0.34	0.32
3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.54
SVM	0.56	0.54	0.56	0.55
RF	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.59
PCA+KNN	0.54	0.55	0.54	0.55
sPCA+KNN	0.60	0.62	0.60	0.61
3.9	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62
SVM	0.58	0.45	0.58	0.50
RF	0.74	0.73	0.74	0.74
PCA+KNN	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68
sPCA+KNN	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.66
3.13	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.70	0.64	0.70	0.66
SVM	0.57	0.52	0.57	0.54
RF	0.63	0.59	0.63	0.61
PCA+KNN	0.72	0.66	0.72	0.68
sPCA+KNN	0.65	0.60	0.65	0.62
3.10F	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.32	0.26	0.32	0.29
SVM	0.40	0.36	0.40	0.37
RF	0.38	0.34	0.38	0.36
PCA+KNN	0.34	0.32	0.34	0.33
sPCA+KNN	0.34	0.28	0.34	0.31

3.10B	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.32	0.29	0.32	0.30
SVM	0.46	0.43	0.46	0.44
RF	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52
PCA+KNN	0.46	0.41	0.46	0.43
sPCA+KNN	0.42	0.37	0.42	0.39

ST-GCN skeleton-based approach

Results obtained using ST-GCN approach for the different items from the held-out test Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset are presented in **Table 52**. Despite that convergence for all motor items is observed (both training and testing errors decrease up to a certain iteration), the results are clearly not satisfactory. As ST-GCN was originally proposed for action recognition, this fact may indicate inability of this approach to accurately identify more subtle variations, such as those assessed by the CMFT motor items. In addition, we note that the training set (40 samples) may be insufficient to be used for training of deep learning models.

Table 52 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers obtained for the held-out Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset using the ST-GCN approach.

Item	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
3.8R	0.40	0.16	0.40	0.23
3.8L	0.40	0.21	0,40	0.26
3.9	0.50	0.25	0.50	0.33
3.13	0.80	0.85	0.80	0.78
3,10F	0.20	0.13	0.20	0.16
3,10B	0.40	0.16	0.40	0.22

9.3.2 Patient and public involvement

To support the development of the mobile version of the Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) for integration into the AI-PROGNOSIS applications, a co-creation workshop was conducted, as detailed in D3.1. The CMFT is designed to be a user-friendly digital tool for assessing motor symptoms in PD, with a focus on perceived usefulness and ease of use for both PwP and healthcare professionals. The workshop aimed to gather early feedback from PwP on usability, engagement, accessibility, and areas for improvement, ensuring the tool aligns with user needs and expectations. The session followed a structured format, including project overview, mock-up presentations, and a panel discussion guided by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

During the workshop, participants reviewed a CMFT prototype composed of five interactive screens: a main menu, setup instructions, motor test guidance, a countdown screen, and a motor test recording interface. These components were designed to guide users through the motor assessment process in a clear and accessible manner.

Participants were selected through purposive sampling, targeting individuals aged 18 or older with a confirmed PD diagnosis and English proficiency. The session included 15 participants:

6 PwP, 5 researchers, 1 clinical expert, and 3 technical experts from the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium. The 70-minute online session, held in April 2024 via Microsoft Teams, concluded with a satisfaction questionnaire. Audio recordings were transcribed and pseudonymised, and a structured guide with seven questions focused on CMFT design, particularly posture and balance.

Data analysis was conducted by two independent researchers using thematic analysis, with educational backgrounds classified according to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) and inter-rater reliability assessed via Cohen's kappa. Direct quotations from participants were used to support the findings.

Overall, 91% of participants expressed high satisfaction with the session and a willingness to engage in future activities. PwP participants appreciated the CMFT's simplicity and its potential to improve motor assessments. Suggestions for improvement included extending session duration for deeper discussion, clarifying the app's intended purpose, enhancing instructional clarity and visual design, and incorporating interactive demo materials. These insights guided the final refinements of the CMFT's design and development, helping align it with user needs and supporting its integration into the dBM-DEV study.

9.4 Discussion

9.4.1 Interpretation

The proposed CMFT approach involves utilising smartphone-based video analysis to assess motor skills, in PwP. It aims to offer insights into key motor symptoms of PD, while being easy to perform for both PD patients and healthcare professionals. In order to design and validate the proposed approach, we organized a clinical study in Papanikolaou Hospital of Thessaloniki using a cohort of 39 volunteer PD patients and captured 50 videos of them performing a sequence of four items from the MDS-UPDRS motor tests (Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset). Additional validation was possible using recordings from the dBM-DEV study, which were recorded using mAI-Health app. The main findings can be summarized as follows:

- Despite a few random errors, extraction of body landmarks using the Google MediaPipe Pose Landmarker tool was seen to be highly efficient, when the input is either video recordings from smartphones are used (e.g., Papanikolaou-CMFT study) or recorded data from mAI-Health app. However, in the latter, conversion of the frame rate to 30fps is required as, depending on the smartphone computational efficiency, the frame rate is irregular and may vary between 10-20fps. Notably, a custom player was developed for visualizing the estimated recordings (body landmark sequences), which is very useful for evaluating each individual recording and may even be useful for clinical assessment of CMFT motor items in the future.
- A set of representative angle, angular speed and angular acceleration features was selected for each motor item. Correlation analysis revealed that many of these features have significant Spearman correlations with the corresponding clinical scores. For each individual item, a feature selection approach was used to identify features that exhibit the highest correlation with the clinical scores. This approach was seen to result in performance gains, against the case where all candidate features are used. The adopted feature extraction and selection approach was also seen to perform favourably compared to the tsfresh feature extraction and selection approach.
- The movement segmentation approach to identify each individual item that was initially designed in D3.1 was further modified and optimized, leading to outstanding performance for all 50 entries of Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset. Notably, peak detection based on

maximum prominence within the automatically segmented 3.8R and 3.8L time series demonstrated robust performance for leg agility items (3.8R and 3.8L) and led to the computation of “clinically meaningful” displacement features, which we consider as an important outcome of this work, as these features correspond to rhythm and amplitude, which are the actual features to be assessed by clinicians, according to the MDS-UPDRS guidelines for these motor items. Future work may further extend this approach for other items.

- Different ML classifiers were tested and optimised and results indicate strong correlations with clinical scores in both held-out and dBM-DEV datasets for motor items 3.9 (posture) and 3.10F/B (gait). The SVM and RF classifiers seem to yield satisfactory results for most items.
- Unfortunately, the validation with dBM-DEV study data was not satisfactory for motor items 3.8R, 3.8L and 3.13, which may be due to several reasons:
 - Many recordings were not usable for analysis. Most of these issues were due to movements of the smartphone camera (e.g., handheld smartphone instead of tripod use as instructed) which is not in line with the CMFT execution protocol. Other errors include: a) smartphone camera in portrait, instead of the recommended landscape mode, b) errors in properly following the CMFT protocol, such as incomplete short recordings or setting the chair to facing the camera (instead of 45 degrees, which increases MediaPipe errors, moving both feet during 3.8R or 3.8L, etc. CMFT UI improvements are considered to address these issues.
 - The Papanikolaou-CMFT study used only PD patients (no HCs), thus lacking enough recordings for training class 0. This problem can also be observed in the feature value distributions of displacement-based features (Figure 49).

Finally, a co-creation session was held to gather feedback from PD patients and healthcare professionals regarding specific aspects of the CMFT, such as usability, engagement, accessibility, and suggestions for improvement. The findings of this session were taken into account for optimizing the CMFT tool.

9.4.2 Innovation beyond state of the art

The Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) introduces an active digital assessment framework that evaluates posture, balance, gait, and coordination using camera-based motion tracking. Video recordings of patients performing standardized motor tasks are processed using pose estimation algorithms to extract joint trajectories, displacement-based features, and biomechanical indicators of motor performance. Machine-learning models trained on these features achieved F1 scores of up to 0.90 for several MDS-UPDRS motor items, demonstrating strong alignment with clinical assessments. The innovation of this approach lies in transforming traditional in-clinic neurological examinations into automated digital assessments that can be objectively quantified and potentially performed remotely. By combining pose estimation, automated movement segmentation, and machine learning-based scoring, the CMFT framework enables scalable and reproducible evaluation of complex motor tasks while preserving the clinical interpretability of established UPDRS motor items.

9.4.3 Limitations and further insights

The final version of the Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset includes 50 recordings by 33 PD patients in total, selected in the context of the data collection study approved by the Papanikolaou General Hospital. The number of recordings in the dataset, which was used for CMFT

development is considered satisfactory, but additional recordings (especially the addition of HCs) is expected to further increase robustness.

Data collected with the CMFT mobile implementation within the dBM-DEV study (69 recordings by 29 distinct participants) were used for validation but many of these recordings were not usable due to different reasons e.g., recordings performed by handheld smartphone, in portrait mode or when the CMFT protocol is not properly followed by the patient. The CMFT approach (both movement segmentation and item score prediction) was trained using recordings from fixed cameras and is not able to cope well with handheld recordings.

Clinically meaningful displacement-based features associated with the clinical evaluation, e.g., monitor amplitude and frequency changes during the leg agility tests (items **3.8R** and **3.8L**) have been robustly estimated. In the future, similar angle-based features may be computed for motor items **3.9** and **3.13**, however the available 33 MediaPipe body landmarks may be insufficient to properly assess axial motor dysfunctions at trunk and neck. Regarding gait items (**3.10F** and **3.10B**), the robust estimation of additional clinically meaningful features, such as step duration or swing phase duration (Di Biase, 2020), seems to be hard, as the identification of prominent peaks corresponding to the three steps towards each direction is complicated by landmark detection noise, especially during the additional steps needed as the patient turns.

A further aspect worth considering is the way the CMFT protocol itself shapes the behaviour being recorded. Performing motor tasks in front of a smartphone can subtly alter posture, pacing, or movement amplitude, especially for individuals who are unfamiliar with being filmed or who adjust their performance to “fit” within the camera frame. These behavioural adaptations may introduce systematic differences between CMFT-captured movements and those observed during in-person clinical examinations, where the spatial setup, clinician prompts, and environmental cues are different. In addition, pose-estimation models such as MediaPipe translate complex three-dimensional movements into a simplified two-dimensional skeletal representation, which may not fully capture nuances that clinicians rely on, such as hesitations, compensatory trunk shifts, or the quality of movement initiation. This creates an interpretive gap between what the algorithm measures and what clinicians score. Further work towards improving the CMFT is planned to be conducted within WP4 and WP5.

9.4.4 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

As mentioned above and supported by the findings of the dedicated co-creation session for the CMFT (detailed in D3.1), the test has the potential to offer several advancements to PD patient care, facilitating regular and objective symptom tracking and allowing patients to conduct assessments at home. The co-creation session for the CMFT showcased extensive patient and public involvement, integrating valuable feedback from PwPD to refine this digital assessment tool. The session's primary goals were to make the CMFT user-friendly for PwPD and to ensure it provided clinically relevant insights into key motor symptoms such as balance and posture. Usability, accessibility, and engagement were evaluated using the TAM framework, focusing on perceived ease of use and usefulness. Feedback emphasized the importance of clear instructions and the option for both written and video guidance, which many PwPD participants found helpful in reducing ambiguity. Discussions highlighted accessibility improvements, such as proper smartphone positioning and accommodations for advanced PD stages, including potential caregiver support. A thematic analysis identified three primary areas for enhancement: usability, ease of use and accessibility, and user engagement. PwPD participants valued the CMFT's feasibility, efficiency, and convenience for at-home use, emphasizing its practical benefits for routine assessments. They also preferred feedback on symptom progression, which could boost engagement and adherence. Ethical considerations regarding data protection were addressed, clarifying that only motion-

tracking data (not personal video data) would be stored in alignment with EU data protection guidelines. This approach, supported by the WHO's guidance on ethical AI in health⁴, upholds user privacy and informed consent. In summary, the co-creation session provided essential insights, highlighting the value of early PwPD involvement to enhance the CMFT's relevance, usability, and patient-centeredness. This approach not only aligns with patient-centred design principles but also reinforces the CMFT's potential as a practical tool for PwPD, healthcare professionals, and caregivers within the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem.

In the long term, the proposed approach can also be further generalised for other MDS-UPDRS Part III: Motor Examination motion items, such as hand/finger movements (3.4-3.6), possibly using MediaPipe Hand landmark detection instead of Pose landmark detection.

9.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Posture/Balance
Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MDS-UPDRS item 3.8 (Leg agility) 2. MDS-UPDRS item 3.9 (Arising from chair) 3. MDS-UPDRS item 3.13 (Posture) 4. MDS-UPDRS item 3.10 (Gait)
Measurement technology	A Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) is implemented that makes use of four modified MDS-UPDRS-related motor tasks, combining it with continuous video-based human body tracking.
Type of measurement	Active
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital score for each item obtained by training ML models using angular, speed, acceleration features related to the joints involved in the item. 2. Digital score for leg agility items (3.8R /3.8L) obtained by training ML models using clinically meaningful displacement-based features (amplitude, rhythm).
Validation	<p>Type: Real world</p> <p>Primary measures of validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. F1 scores (along with accuracy, precision, recall) for the classification of the digital scores of MDS-UPDRS items 3.8R, 3.8L, 3.9, 3.13, 3.10 <p>Test cohorts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Held-out test-set from Papanikolaou-CMFT dataset (50 recordings from 39 volunteer PD patients from Papanikolaou Hospital in Thessaloniki capturing videos of them as they executed the CMFT. • dBM-DEV study CMFT recordings (69 recordings from 29 distinct participants made using the mAI-Health AI-PROGNOSIS app).
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The smartphone video capturing the data is reliable, with minimal noise or distortions affecting the quality of the video-based human body tracking. • The Mediapipe pose landmark detection algorithm functions consistently and accurately, identifying joint positions and movements without significant errors.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients adhere to the CMFT protocol, maintaining proper positioning within the camera's field of view and performing the tasks as instructed. • The smartphone used for recordings has adequate computational power to process the video data and store landmarks without interruptions or lag. • Environmental factors such as lighting, clothing and room setup are optimized to ensure clear visibility and accurate video-based human body tracking.
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients must adhere to the CMFT protocol to ensure accurate data capture, such as staying within the camera's field of view during all tasks. The camera should be correctly positioned in a well-lit room, ideally with a chair placed appropriately for tasks that require sitting or standing. The smartphone used for recording must have adequate computational power and storage capacity to support the seamless execution of the test, particularly for running Mediapipe pose landmark detection without interruptions or delays. Proper environmental setup and device readiness are crucial to maintaining the integrity of the assessment.

10 Cognitive function active assessment

10.1 Background and objectives

Cognitive impairment in patients with PD is a very common non-motor manifestation and includes subjective cognitive decline (SCD), mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and PD dementia (PDD) (Degirmenci, 2023). Approximately 10% to 20% of people with PD develop mild cognitive impairment, and approximately 46% develop PD dementia (PDD) within 10 years after diagnosis (Hähnel, 2023). Given the high prevalence and clinical relevance of cognitive impairment in PD, it is important to establish reliable dBMs of cognition that allow early detection of cognitive deficits and their monitoring over time. In addition, psychiatric symptoms such as impulsivity can occur as a side effect of dopaminergic medication. Such symptoms can also be assessed by cognitive tests.

Digital assessments of cognition, grounded in neuropsychophysical research, enable the capture of high-resolution cognitive performance metrics that extend beyond the scope of conventional paper-and-pencil neuropsychological testing. Digital assessments allow more fine-grained temporal assessment and better resolution of behavioural features such as impulsivity. In deliverable D2.3 "Initial report on domain review and datasets", a detailed description of recent studies on digital assessments of cognitive decline in PD is provided. AI-PROGNOSIS aims to establish cognitive dBMs derived both from active cognitive tests, and passively, through the interaction of users with their smartphone. This section focuses on the dBMs derived from the active cognitive tests.

Three cognitive tests were implemented in the dBM-DEV smartphone application and administered to participants enrolled in the dBM-DEV study. The implementation code for all three tests was derived from an open-source tablet-based cognitive test battery designed and previously rolled out by partner TUD in a research study in 97 PD patients (henceforth referred to as the training cohort). The selected tests (the N-back task assessing working memory, the

Stop-Signal task measuring response inhibition, and the Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART) evaluating risk-taking and impulsivity) are well-established computerized neuropsychological paradigms involving well-defined features that constitute cognitive dBMs. These paradigms and their underlying features have been widely applied across clinical populations with cognitive impairment, including PD, and are supported by an extensive and longstanding body of literature (e.g. N-Back test⁷, SST⁸, BART⁹).

As described in Deliverable D3.1, the selection of features of interest to be used henceforth as cognitive dBMs was first verified in the training cohort. In this deliverable we report some minor modifications in the features extracted in dBM-DEV. Moreover, we present here an exploratory approach, developed in the training cohort, which aimed to identify dBMs most strongly linked to cognitive status as defined by the MoCA. Although this approach was not decisive for the selection, nor for the validation of the cognitive dBMs, it is presented in the current deliverable as complementary work addressing the epistemological consideration as to whether precise, mechanism-based digital measures align with global cognitive performance measured by a classical paper-and-pencil test widely used in the clinic in PD. Results are discussed, including the full potential of digital biomarkers beyond their association with overall cognitive status.

10.2 Methods

10.2.1 Datasets

Training cohort

As reported in deliverable D3.1, an open-source tablet-based cognitive test battery (Feige et al., 2024) guided the implementation of the AI-PROGNOSIS active cognitive tests. A dataset with 97 entries, corresponding to 97 PD patients that completed three cognitive Tasks (N-Back, Bart and Stop Signal) was used for the development of the dBMs. Demographics for this cohort were presented in Deliverable D3.1. Each entry contains values for: a) features from the three cognitive Tasks (performed once) and b) the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA; Nasreddine et al., 2005) total score of the patient.

dBM-DEV cohorts

Across all dBM-DEV cohorts, participants were instructed to complete each of the three tests every two weeks. Accordingly, the two development cohorts had a maximum expected number of 2 completed test sets per participant, whereas the confirmation cohort had a maximum of 6. In total, 46 participants enrolled in dBM-DEV performed 128 completed cognitive task sessions. Their demographics are presented in **Table 53**.

Table 53 Demographics of the dBM-DEV participants included in the dataset of active cognitive tests

Demographics	Values
Number (#) of Patients (# recordings)	RBD group: 12 (22) HC group: 12 (20) PD group: 22 (86)
Women # (%)	18 (39%)

⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18545772/>

⁸ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37669861/>

⁹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36894682/>

Avg. age in years (std)	63.28 (9.99)
Men # (%)	28 (61%)
Avg. age in years (std)	63.96 (8.11)
MoCA score class distribution of sessions (# in L:0-21/M:22-25/H:26-30)	0/11/117
Avg. Disease Duration, years (std)	6.4 (4.7)
Avg. Age at onset in years (std)	56.3 (10.5)
Avg. DA Dose, mg (std)	243.8 (141.6)
Avg. Levodopa Dose, mg (std)	418.4 (197.7)
Avg. LEDD, mg (std)	672.3 (338.8)
Avg. MoCA Score (std)	26.4 (2.8)
Avg. UPDRS III Score (std)	62.8 (10.1)
Avg. FAB Score (std)	6.4 (4.7)
Avg. SCD, positive/total (std)	56.3 (10.5)

10.2.2 Digital biomarkers

Stop-Signal task

The Stop-Signal task aims to measure how well the brain controls **inhibitory control**, i.e. the ability to cancel an already-initiated action. Participants respond to arrows by pressing the matching left or right button ("go" trials) but must withhold their response if a red cross appears shortly after ("stop" trials), with the stop-signal delay adapting to their performance across four blocks of 50 trials each.

For the dBM-DEV study, the Stop-Signal features listed in **Table 54** were used. The "StopSignal_max_value_delay_low" feature previously used in Deliverable D3.1) was removed to reduce test duration.

Table 54 Features extracted from the Stop-Signal task.

Variable Name	Description
StopSignal_totalCorrect	Total number of correct responses across all trials.
StopSignal_correct_go	Number of correct responses in "go" trials.
StopSignal_correct_stop	Number of correct suppressions in "stop" trials.
StopSignal_max_value_delay_high	Maximum time delay value for the stop signal (red cross) in the High condition.
StopSignal_StopSignal_RT_mean_go	Average reaction time for "go" trials.
StopSignal_StopSignal_RT_std_go	Standard deviation of reaction time for "go" trials.

Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART)

The Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART) aims to measure **risk-taking behaviour**. Participants inflate a virtual balloon to earn points with each pump but risk losing them if the

balloon flies away at a random limit; they can secure points anytime by pressing “Collect Points,” across 20 trials after practice.

For the dBM-DEV study, the BART features listed in **Table 55** were used (same as in Deliverable D3.1).

Table 55 Features extracted from the Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART).

Variable Name	Description
bart_correctedPumps	Number of pumps per trial adjusted for average number of pumps before the balloon would have flown away.
bart_changeAfterBurst	Changes in participant behaviour following a balloon flying away. This is the differences in pumps between the trial the balloon flew away and the following one.
bart_didBurst	Indicator of whether the balloon flew away in a trial.
bart_correctedTotal	Total adjusted score adjusted for average number of pumps before the balloon would have flown away.

N-Back task

The N-Back task aims to measure **executive function and memory**. Participants see an image along with a green and a red button and are instructed to tap the green button if the displayed image is the same as the one shown 1 to n images before or the red button if this is not the case. After a practice round, there are two test rounds ($n=1,2$), each with 50 trials without feedback.

In the dBM-DEV study, for the N-Back task, only features from the first test round (level) were used, as the analysis of feature contributions from the second test round (for the original TUD dataset) did not yield any meaningful results. Thus, only three features from the first round were used as shown in **Table 56**.

Table 56 Features extracted from the N-Back task.

Variable Name	Description
NBack_correct_sum_load_1.0	Total number of correct responses for n-back level 1.
NBack_rt_mean_load_1.0	Average reaction time for correct responses at n-back level 1.
NBack_rt_std_load_1.0	Standard deviation of reaction time for n-back level 1.

Features were clipped at ± 3 *interquartile range (IQR) to minimize the influence of extreme outliers.

10.2.3 Feasibility (completion of repeated assessments).

Feasibility was quantified using adherence to the intended repeated-measures schedule. For each participant, we summarized the number of completed assessments relative to the maximum expected number in the respective cohort (development cohorts vs. confirmation cohort). Completion was treated as a pragmatic indicator of usability and acceptability of the digital test battery under real-world conditions. Results are reported descriptively (e.g., completed sessions per participant and overall completion rates per cohort/task) to document whether repeated at-home measurements can be obtained at sufficient frequency for downstream analyses.

10.2.4 ANCOVA models (exploratory cohort comparisons).

To explore cohort differences in task-derived features, we fitted separate analysis-of-covariance (ANCOVA) models for each outcome using ordinary least squares regression. Cohort was entered as a categorical factor with DEV-control (healthy controls) as the

reference group [DEV-RBD (persons with RBD) and Confirmation (persons with PD) estimated as contrasts vs. DEV-Control). To account for demographic and clinical heterogeneity, age (centered) was included as a covariate. In addition, PD disease duration (centered) \times PD status was included as an interaction term to model an effect of disease duration restricted to PD participants (0 for controls). For each model, coefficients, standard errors, t-statistics, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are reported. Analyses were exploratory and intended to support feasibility and plausibility assessment rather than confirmatory inference; accompanying plots summarize covariate-adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable (partial regression) relationships for continuous predictors.

10.2.5 MoCA-Based Patient Stratification and Correlation-Driven Feature Selection

In order to determine the association of features derived from these tests with the MoCA, we first grouped the PD patients in the training set with respect to their MoCA scores (ranging between 18-30) into 3 balanced classes/groups: Class 0: 18-22, Class 1: 23-25, and Class 2: 26-30.

A feature correlation analysis was then conducted to examine the association between the 13 features from the tasks and MoCA scores. Specifically, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) and significance (p) were computed for each feature. Features were then ranked according to the rank coefficient and three features with largest correlation were identified (**Table 57**). Corresponding boxplots are presented in **Figure 52**, providing a graphical representation of the distribution of each feature's values across the three MoCA score classes. As seen, monotonical trends can be observed in all three features, indicating that the values for these features may be used for predicting the corresponding MoCA class.

Table 57 Features with highest Spearman correlation with respect to the corresponding clinical MoCA score.

Features	Spearman rho	Spearman p
NBack_rt_std_load_1.0	-0.517	5.86e-08
NBack_correct_sum_load_1.0	0.483	5.48e-07
StopSignal_correct_go	0.329	0.00099

Figure 52 Boxplots showing feature distributions per MoCA class (0/1/2) of the three features having highest correlation with clinical MoCA scores.

As described in the previous subsections, there were changes (with respect to the approach used in D3.1) in the features used in two of the three cognitive tests, hence, we re-trained ML models for predicting the MoCA score groups using the training cohort, based on the available features from all tasks. Specifically, we trained five ML classifiers for this task, i.e., i) KNN, ii) SVM, iii) RF, iv) combination of PCA and KNN, and v) combination of supervised PCA (sPCA) (Ghojogh, 2019)) and KNN. We have also implemented an additional feature selection step by identifying a subset of N features (N=3) that have the largest correlation with the

corresponding target (MoCA group) and then using only these features for prediction. As the final model should be available for further validation using results from the dBM-DEV study, we decided to use an 80/20 stratified train/test split, so that each set contains balanced numbers of patients from each class. For each classifier, we optimized a few important parameters during training using grid search: i) KNN: $n_neighbors(2/3/4)$, weights (distance/uniform), ii) SVM: $C(1/3/5)$ and kernel (rbf/linear), iii) RF: $n_estimators(100/200/1000)$ and $max_features(\log3/sqrt)$, iv) PCA+KNN: $n_components(2/3)$ and $n_neighbors(2/3)$, v) sPCA+KNN: $n_components(2/3)$ and $n_neighbors(2/3)$. For detailed descriptions for these hyperparameters we refer the reader to the python implementations of the ML classifiers in <https://scikit-learn.org/>.

Finally, we also attempted to correlate specific cognitive sub-domains measured by the MoCA with selected test-derived features. More specifically, as the N-back test is associated with executive function and memory, we associated it with the short-term memory recall component of MoCA, and b) as the Stop signal task is associated with attention in addition to response inhibition, we associated it with the attention component of MoCA.

10.3 Results

10.3.1 Feasibility

In each cohort, the majority of participants completed at least one session (Dev-RBD: 19/30, 63.3%; Dev-Control: 17/24, 70.8%; Confirmation: 22/28, 78.6%) (**Table 58**), demonstrating that obtaining usable cognitive data with the app was achievable across study groups. In the confirmation cohort, repeated participation was also substantial: 21/28 (75.0%) completed at least two sessions, 17/28 (60.7%) at least three, and 15/28 (53.6%) at least four sessions, indicating that longitudinal data collection was feasible for a meaningful proportion of participants. Overall, these figures show that the study setup enabled both initial data acquisition and – particularly in the confirmation cohort – repeated measurements over multiple time points.

Table 58 Adherence to cognitive testing by cohort (≥ 1 to ≥ 6 completed sessions), n (%)
Note that the study duration for the first two cohorts was shorter than for the confirmation cohort.

Completed Sessions	≥ 1	≥ 2	≥ 3	≥ 4	≥ 5	≥ 6
dBM-DEV study cohort						
Development-RBD (DEV-RBD)	19 (63.3%)	12 (40.0%)	-	-	-	-
Development-control (DEV-Control)	17 (70.8%)	13 (54.2%)	-	-	-	-
Confirmation	22 (78.6%)	21 (75.0%)	17 (60.7%)	15 (53.6%)	7 (25.0%)	5 (17.9%)

10.3.2 Exploratory group comparisons

10.3.2.1 NBack

For *NBack_rt_mean_load_1.0*, cohort contrasts relative to DEV-Control were -5.81 ms for DEV-RBD ($p = .942$; 95% CI $[-165.52, 153.89]$) and 71.92 ms for the Confirmation cohort ($p = .336$; 95% CI $[-76.32, 220.16]$) (**Table 59**). Age (centred) was associated with higher reaction times ($\beta = 12.11$ ms, $p = .001$; 95% CI $[4.86, 19.36]$). The PD years (centred) \times PD interaction term was 16.20 ms ($p = .156$; 95% CI $[-6.38, 38.78]$). The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in **Figure 53**.

Table 59 Analysis-of-covariance results for NBack_rt_mean_load_1.0. Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) × PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	1014.56	56.21	18.05	<.001	902.09	1127.04
RBD (vs. Control)	-5.81	79.81	-.07	.942	-165.52	153.89
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	71.92	74.08	.97	.336	-76.32	220.16
Age (centred)	12.11	3.62	3.34	.001	4.86	19.36
PD years (centred) × PD	16.20	11.28	1.44	.156	-6.38	38.78

Figure 53 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for NBack_rt_mean_load_1.0. Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years×PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

For *NBack_rt_std_load_1.0*, cohort contrasts relative to DEV-Control were 46.22 for DEV-RBD ($p = .206$; 95% CI [-26.16, 118.60]) and 62.06 for the Confirmation cohort ($p = .070$; 95% CI [-5.13, 129.24]) (**Table 60**), indicating an ordered pattern with higher values in DEV-RBD and Confirmation compared with DEV-Control, with the Confirmation vs. DEV-Control contrast narrowly missing conventional significance. Age (centered) had an estimated coefficient of 3.23 ($p = .054$; 95% CI [-0.06, 6.51]). The PD years (centered) × PD interaction term was 11.91 ($p = .023$; 95% CI [1.67, 22.14]). The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in **Figure 54**.

Table 60 Analysis-of-covariance results results for NBack_rt_std_load_1.0. Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) × PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	248.21	25.47	9.74	<.001	197.24	299.19
RBD (vs. Control)	46.22	36.17	1.28	.206	-26.16	118.60
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	62.06	33.58	1.85	.070	-5.13	129.24
Age (centred)	3.23	1.64	1.96	.054	-.06	6.51
PD years (centred) × PD	11.91	5.11	2.33	.023	1.67	22.14

Figure 54 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for NBack_rt_std_load_1.0. Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years×PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

For *NBack_correct_sum_load_1.0* (higher values indicate better performance; negative coefficients reflect fewer correct responses), the DEV-RBD cohort differed from DEV-Control ($\beta = -8.19$, $p = .047$; 95% CI $[-16.28, -0.10]$) (**Table 61**), whereas the Confirmation cohort did not show a clear difference relative to DEV-Control ($\beta = -4.20$, $p = .268$; 95% CI $[-11.71, 3.31]$). Age (centered) was -0.24 ($p = .195$; 95% CI $[-0.61, 0.13]$), and the PD years (centered) × PD interaction term was -0.46 ($p = .422$; 95% CI $[-1.61, 0.68]$). The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in **Figure 55**.

Table 61 Analysis-of-covariance results results for NBack_correct_sum_load_1.0. Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) × PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	45.30	2.85	15.91	<.001	39.60	51.00
RBD (vs. Control)	-8.19	4.04	-2.03	.047	-16.28	-.10
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	-4.20	3.75	-1.12	.268	-11.71	3.31
Age (centred)	-.24	.18	-1.31	.195	-.61	.13
PD years (centred) × PD	-.46	.57	-.81	.422	-1.61	.68

Figure 55 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for NBack_correct_sum_load_1.0. Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years×PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

10.3.2.2 Stop Signal

For *Stop Signal Correct go*, cohort contrasts relative to DEV-Control were 6.53 for DEV-RBD ($p = .548$; 95% CI [-15.17, 28.22]) and -14.90 for the Confirmation cohort ($p = .149$; 95% CI [-35.34, 5.54]) (Table 62). Age (centered) had an estimated coefficient of -0.77 ($p = .149$; 95% CI [-1.83, 0.29]). The PD years (centered) \times PD interaction term was -0.18 ($p = .923$; 95% CI [-3.79, 3.44]). The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in Figure 56.

Table 62 Analysis-of-covariance results results for the Correct go feature of the Stop Signal task. Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) \times PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	105.40	7.37	14.30	<.001	90.60	120.19
RBD (vs. Control)	6.53	10.81	.60	.548	-15.17	28.22
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	-14.90	10.18	-1.46	.149	-35.34	5.54
Age (centred)	-.77	.53	-1.47	.149	-1.83	.29
PD years (centred) \times PD	-.18	1.80	-.10	.923	-3.79	3.44

Figure 56 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for Stop Signal Correct go. Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years \times PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

For *Stop Signal Correct Stop %* ($p_{stop_success}$), no cohort differences were observed relative to DEV-Control (DEV-RBD: $\beta = 0.02$, $p = .612$; 95% CI [-0.06, 0.10]; Confirmation: $\beta = 0.01$, $p = .693$; 95% CI [-0.06, 0.09]) (Table 63). Age (centered) and the PD years (centered) \times PD interaction term were also close to zero (age: $p = .638$; PD years \times PD: $p = .911$). Overall, stop accuracy was comparable across cohorts, indicating that the Stop-Signal paradigm performed similarly in all groups. The intercept estimate corresponded to an average stop success probability of ~ 0.58 ($\approx 58\%$), i.e., a stop failure (“false positive”) rate of approximately 42% – close to the targeted 50% level of the adaptive staircase procedure. The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in Figure 57.

Table 63 Analysis-of-covariance results results for the feature “correct Stop” of the Stop Signal task. Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) \times PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
------	------	---------	---	------	--------	--------

Intercept	.58	.03	21.72	<.001	.53	.64
RBD (vs. Control)	.02	.04	.51	.612	-.06	.10
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	.01	.04	.40	.693	-.06	.09
Age (centred)	.00	.00	.47	.638	-.00	.00
PD years (centred) × PD	.00	.01	.11	.911	-.01	.01

Figure 57 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for Stop Signal Correct Stop (%). Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years×PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

For *Stop Signal Reaction Time (SSRT)*, cohort contrasts relative to DEV-Control were -9.04 for DEV-RBD ($p = .680$; 95% CI $[-52.83, 34.74]$) and 23.53 for the Confirmation cohort ($p = .257$; 95% CI $[-17.72, 64.77]$) (**Table 64**). Age (centered) had an estimated coefficient of 0.31 ($p = .775$; 95% CI $[-1.83, 2.44]$). The PD years (centered) × PD interaction term was -0.22 ($p = .951$; 95% CI $[-7.51, 7.07]$). The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in **Figure 58**.

Table 64 Analysis-of-covariance results results for Stop Signal Reaction Time (SSRT). Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) × PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	378.27	14.87	25.44	<.001	348.41	408.13
RBD (vs. Control)	-9.04	21.81	-.41	.680	-52.83	34.74
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	23.53	20.54	1.15	.257	-17.72	64.77
Age (centred)	.31	1.06	.29	.775	-1.83	2.44
PD years (centred) × PD	-.22	3.63	-.06	.951	-7.51	7.07

Figure 58 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for *Stop Signal Reaction Time* (SSRT). Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years×PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

10.3.2.3 BART

For BART pumps (non-burst trials), cohort contrasts relative to DEV-Control were -1.44 for DEV-RBD ($p = .419$; 95% CI $[-4.98, 2.10]$) and 1.50 for the Confirmation cohort ($p = .368$; 95% CI $[-1.81, 4.81]$) (**Table 65**). Age (centred) had an estimated coefficient of 0.10 ($p = .231$; 95% CI $[-0.06, 0.26]$). The PD years (centred) × PD interaction term was -0.49 ($p = .060$; 95% CI $[-1.00, 0.02]$), indicating a negative association with pumps within PD participants that did not reach conventional significance. The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in **Figure 59**.

Table 65 Analysis-of-covariance results results for Bart Pumps. Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) × PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	11.62	1.24	9.36	<.001	9.13	14.10
RBD (vs. Control)	-1.44	1.77	-.81	.419	-4.98	2.10
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	1.50	1.65	.91	.368	-1.81	4.81
Age (centred)	.10	.08	1.21	.231	-.06	.26
PD years (centred) × PD	-.49	.26	-1.92	.060	-1.00	.02

Figure 59 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for BART Pumps. Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years×PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

For BART burst rate, cohort contrasts relative to DEV-Control were -0.01 for DEV-RBD ($p = .737$; 95% CI $[-0.10, 0.07]$) and 0.03 for the Confirmation cohort ($p = .484$; 95% CI $[-0.05, 0.11]$) (**Table 66**). Age (centered) had an estimated coefficient close to zero ($p = .476$; 95% CI $[-0.00, 0.01]$). The PD years (centered) × PD interaction term was -0.02 ($p = .006$; 95% CI $[-0.03, -0.01]$), indicating a negative association between PD disease duration and burst rate within PD participants. The corresponding adjusted cohort distributions and added-variable plots are shown in **Figure 60**.

Table 66 Analysis-of-covariance results results for BART Burst Rate. Estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals are shown for cohort contrasts (reference: DEV-Control), age (centered), and the PD years (centered) × PD interaction.

Term	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	.30	.03	9.86	<.001	.24	.36
RBD (vs. Control)	-.01	.04	-.34	.737	-.10	.07
PD Cohort (vs. Control)	.03	.04	.70	.484	-.05	.11
Age (centred)	.00	.00	.72	.476	-.00	.01
PD years (centred) × PD	-.02	.01	-2.84	.006	-.03	-.01

10.3.3 Exploratory study of feature correlations with cognitive status (MoCA scores)

In the following, results are presented from the exploratory study of re-training and validation of ML models for predicting the MoCA score groups based on the specific cognitive features. First, after hyperparameter optimization, results using Leave One Sample Out validation based on cognitive test battery data (97 patients) are presented **Table 67** (with or without feature selection). As seen, moderate performance is achieved, either with or without feature selection.

Figure 60 Covariate-adjusted cohort comparison and partial effects for BART Burst Rate. Boxplots show adjusted outcome values by cohort (DEV-Control reference). Scatterplots show partial relationships for age and PD-years×PD; colors indicate cohort membership.

Table 67 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for ML classifiers after hyperparameter tuning (with or without using feature selection) using Leave One Out cross-validation. Best performing ML classifiers are shown in bold.

With feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.62
SVM	0.68	0.64	0.68	0.66
RF	0.63	0.61	0.63	0.62
PCA+KNN	0.61	0.62	0.61	0.61
sPCA+KNN	0.61	0.62	0.61	0.61
Without feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.64
SVM	0.66	0.64	0.66	0.64
RF	0.64	0.60	0.63	0.62
PCA+KNN	0.59	0.65	0.59	0.59
sPCA+KNN	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.59

Regarding the estimation of MoCA components from features of “related” tasks, results from the prediction of MoCA memory (delayed recall) component (clinical score range 0-5) based on the three NBack Task features are presented in **Table 68**. The three MoCA groups were defined as 1(severe): 0-1, 2(moderate): 2-3, 3(normal): 4-5. These results indicate that there is no strong correlation between the MoCA memory component and NBack Task features, which measure primarily executive control and working memory.

Table 68 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for ML classifiers after hyperparameter tuning using Leave One Out cross-validation for MoCA memory component. Best performing ML classifiers are shown in bold.

Without feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
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KNN	0.49	0.47	0.49	0.48
SVM	0.58	0.33	0.58	0.42
RF	0.52	0.43	0.52	0.46
PCA+KNN	0.42	0.41	0.42	0.41
sPCA+KNN	0.42	0.41	0.42	0.41

Similarly, results from the prediction of MoCA attention component (clinical score range 0-6) based on the six Stop-Signal Task features are presented in **Table 69**. The three MoCA groups were defined (to ensure balance) as 1 (severe): 0-4, 2 (moderate): 5, 3 (normal): 6, Corresponding results using feature selection were similar and are omitted. Again, these results indicate that there is no strong correlation between the MoCA attention component and Stop Signal Task features, which only measure inhibitory control.

Table 69 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for ML classifiers after hyperparameter tuning using Leave One Out cross-validation for MoCA attention component. Best performing ML classifiers are shown in bold.

Without feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.44	0.40	0.44	0.42
SVM	0.56	0.43	0.56	0.47
RF	0.52	0.44	0.52	0.47
PCA+KNN	0.38	0.38	0.38	0.38
sPCA+KNN	0.39	0.40	0.39	0.40

Regarding the dBM-DEV data, results from the same correlation analysis for all features from the three Tasks are presented in **Table 70**, while boxplots are presented in **Figure 61**. As seen, in this case no significant correlation is found for any feature, while the boxplots for the three previously selected features from the training set show that they cannot properly discriminate between the MoCA groups. This may be partially attributed to the significant differences between the two cohorts: dBM-DEV study also contains healthy controls and MoCA scores of participants are much higher (see also **Table 69**).

Table 70 The feature with highest absolute Spearman statistically significant correlation with respect to the corresponding clinical MoCA score.

Features	Spearman rho	Spearman p
StopSignal_StopSignal_RT_mean_go	-0.212	0.016

Figure 61 Boxplots showing feature distributions per MoCA class of the three previously selected features from the training set (as having highest correlation with clinical MoCA scores).

Furthermore, results from the validation of a model to predict MoCA scores from selected features based on a) a held-out test set (20%) of the training cohort, selected using stratification and b) the dBM-DEV study are presented in **Table 71** and **Table 72** respectively. As seen, most classifiers achieve satisfactory results, particularly regarding dBM-DEV data, whose MoCA group distribution (0/11/117 sessions from MoCA groups 0/1/2, respectively) is very different than the train set (8/23/46) and the (balanced) held-out test set (2/6/12).

Table 71 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for ML classifiers after hypertuning using validation based on the held-out test. Best performing ML classifiers are shown in bold.

Without feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.70	0.72	0.70	0.69
SVM	0.80	0.76	0.80	0.78
RF	0.60	0.57	0.60	0.58
PCA+KNN	0.70	0.66	0.70	0.68
sPCA+KNN	0.75	0.70	0.75	0.72

Table 72 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for ML classifiers after hypertuning using validation based on dBM-DEV study. Best performing ML classifiers are shown in bold.

Without feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.37	0.75	0.37	0.49
SVM	0.55	0.81	0.55	0.65
RF	0.63	0.82	0.63	0.71
PCA+KNN	0.58	0.83	0.58	0.67
sPCA+KNN	0.59	0.84	0.59	0.68

A SHAP summary plot presenting the contributions and importance of different features for the prediction of MoCA class from the held-out test set using SVN without feature selection is illustrated in **Figure 62**. As in the correlation analysis, reaction time variance for N-Back task is the most important feature, with low reaction time variance having positive impact on model output (higher MoCA class/score). Similarly, as expected, higher number of correctedPumps in the BART task also result in higher MoCA class/scores.

Similarly, a SHAP summary plot presenting the contributions and importance of different features for the prediction of MoCA class from the dBM-DEV set using KNN without feature selection is illustrated in **Figure 63**. Although some minor differences with respect to **Figure 62** can be identified, the impact of the different features to the model output is similar in both cases.

Figure 62 Relative importance of different features for the held-out set.

10.4 Discussion

10.4.1 Interpretation

Across cohorts, a substantial number of repeated task observations could be collected, providing an important feasibility signal for the digital assessment approach. In particular, the availability of multiple measurements per participant indicates that the procedures can be implemented in a repeated-measures setting, and that participants are generally able to complete the tests as intended. This breadth of collected data supports the practical viability of the battery for longitudinal or high-frequency sampling.

Across the three tasks, the analyses support feasibility and yield largely plausible patterns while showing only selective cohort-related differences. For the NBack, reaction-time outcomes were primarily driven by age, whereas cohort contrasts in RT were small and imprecise; in contrast, the accuracy outcome indicated reduced performance in the RBD group relative to controls, consistent with the possibility that subtle vulnerability may be more detectable in error-based metrics than in mean RT in this sample. For the Stop-Signal task, go accuracy and stop success rates were comparable across cohorts, suggesting that the paradigm operated similarly in all groups; stop accuracy was reasonably close to the intended operating point of the adaptive staircase (slightly above the nominal 50% target). SSRT did not show clear cohort or covariate effects in this exploratory dataset. For the BART, cohort differences were again limited, but within the PD participants disease duration showed negative associations with pumps (non-burst trials) and burst rate, indicating that risk-taking–

Figure 63 Relative importance of different features for dBM-DEV set.

related behaviour may vary with PD progression. Overall, the pattern of results is compatible with adequate task functioning and clinically plausible trends; the predominance of non-significant cohort contrasts likely reflects limited power and substantial inter-individual variability that could attenuate group-level effects in cross-sectional comparisons.

10.4.2 Limitations and further insights

The MoCA test is a screening test that is well established in clinical routine and clinical research. The dBM s validated here aim to complement the MoCA in two aspects. First, the MoCA was designed to detect dementia, and not for detection of subtle changes in cognition that might occur early in the disease or even before a diagnosis is made. Longitudinal digital measures might be better suited for this purpose, and the dBM s tested here could be used for this purpose. Furthermore, psychiatric complications such as disturbed impulse control can result from dopaminergic medication. The MoCA was not designed to detect these symptoms. In contrast, the stop signal task and the BART have been developed to assess impulsivity. Longitudinal dBM s might therefore help early detection of impulse control disorder.

Both considerations also indicate that a correlation of cognitive dBM s with the MoCA scores is not necessarily expected. In addition, the narrow range of MoCA scores in the dBM-DEV study of cognitively unimpaired individuals did not allow for meaningful correlations of cognitive dBM with the MoCA score. Specifically, correlations between the N-back and Stop-Signal tasks and their corresponding MoCA subdomains were only moderate to low. This likely reflects differences in the cognitive constructs measured: the N-back measures executive control and working memory, whereas the MoCA memory subscore reflects delayed episodic verbal recall; similarly, the Stop-Signal Task measures inhibitory control rather than the

broader attentional processes captured by the MoCA. Moreover, the cognitive tests are known to target highly specific, mechanism-based constructs: the BART test engages reward-related brain circuits, the SST involves inhibitory control networks, and the N-back test recruits executive and working memory circuits. By comparison, the MoCA provides an approximate measure of global cognitive function across multiple domains and is primarily intended for dementia screening in the clinic. While some overlap is expected, these findings support the notion that mechanism-specific digital tasks provide complementary, higher-resolution information and are better suited to detecting subtle changes over time within their targeted cognitive domains.

10.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

The dBM-DEV data demonstrate that remote cognitive assessment via digitised tests is feasible and yields interpretable results. The three selected active tests have been implemented in the ongoing AI-PMP study via the mAI-Care app. This will allow validation whether cognitive dBM derived from these tests can predict disease progression and treatment response, including occurrence of side effects. Consequently, dBM of cognitive performance could potentially enhance the accuracy of the predictive models.

10.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Cognitive function
Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Working memory and executive function (N-Back Task), 2. Risk-taking behaviour (BART Task) 3. Response inhibition (Stop Signal Task)
Measurement technology	Cognitive test battery administered via a smartphone application.
Type of measurement	Active
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	Task completion times, accuracy rates, and derived metrics such as reaction time variability and task-specific scores. The full list of selected features are described in Tables 52, 53 and 54 for the Stop-Signal Test, the BART and the N-Back test, respectively.
Validation	<p>Features of interest validated in the literature.</p> <p>Feasibility of remote cognitive testing via a smartwatch application and interpretability of the data confirmed in dBM-DEV, to be further examined in relation to clinical data in AI-PMP (N=100 PD patients) for the elucidation of their context of use.</p>
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participant is motivated and performs the task to the best of their ability, without intentional underperformance or disengagement. • The participant fully understands the task requirements and interface before and during testing. • The assessment is completed in a relatively quiet, stable environment without interruptions, multitasking, or external cognitive load.
Context of use considerations	Their context of use in PD will be elucidated in the appropriately powered AI-PMP study. Cognitive dBM are expected to provide fine-grained insights into disease progression and treatment response, potentially enhancing the accuracy of the predictive models (both the PD progression and the treatment response prediction models).

11 Open science

The AI-PROGNOSIS project fully embraces the principles of Open Science to promote transparency, accessibility, and reproducibility in research. This approach aligns with global efforts to make scientific outputs more accessible to the public, including stakeholders, such as clinicians, patients, and policymakers. Our open science practices are particularly informed by the CTTI, which emphasizes responsible data sharing and collaborative research.

11.1 Data sharing and accessibility

A core principle of CTTI is the ethical and secure sharing of clinical study data. The AI-PROGNOSIS project adheres to these guidelines by ensuring that all raw data collected within the project, including extracted features and indicators, are anonymized and shared in accordance with data protection regulations (such as GDPR). Our data will be deposited in the Zenodo repository, ensuring broad access for the research community and, in general, safety and adherence to FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) data sharing principles - details will be provided in the data management plan of the project (D1.6). Opening datasets will allow for independent validation and meta-analyses, contributing to more robust scientific findings.

11.2 Collaborative Research and Multi-Stakeholder Engagement

CTTI encourages the involvement of multiple stakeholders in clinical research. AI-PROGNOSIS is built on a foundation of collaboration between academic institutions, clinical researchers, patient advocacy groups, and industry partners. By making both data and tools open and accessible, the project fosters a collaborative research environment where stakeholders can participate in the evaluation and application of dBMs in real-world settings.

11.3 Publication and reporting standards

AI-PROGNOSIS follows open access publishing standards, ensuring that all findings related to the project are available in fully open-access journals per the Horizon Europe framework requirements. This aligns with CTTI's emphasis on transparent reporting and reduces the barriers for clinicians, patients, and the broader public to access crucial scientific knowledge. In addition to sharing final results, preprints and intermediate reports will be made available to ensure ongoing knowledge transfer during the lifecycle of the project. By aligning with CTTI's guidelines on data sharing, multi-stakeholder collaboration, and transparency, AI-PROGNOSIS ensures that its research not only advances scientific understanding but also supports the broader community working toward improved patient outcomes.

12 Ethical and Personal Data Protection Compliance (GDPR)

The development, validation and evaluation of digital biomarkers (dBMs) within AI-PROGNOSIS were conducted in compliance with the applicable European data protection framework, including Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) and in alignment with the approved Study Protocol governing the respective datasets used in this deliverable.

The digital biomarkers rely on the processing of personal data, including special categories of personal data, namely health-related data derived from wearable devices, smartphone-based interaction, active digital tests and clinical assessments. Such processing was carried out exclusively for scientific research purposes and on the basis of appropriate legal grounds, including explicit informed consent where required.

With regard to the data originating from the dBM-DEV Study, all processing activities were performed strictly in accordance with the approved Study Protocol and the corresponding informed consent forms signed by the participants. No processing activities were carried out beyond the agreed research purposes defined in the Study documentation. Participants were duly informed about the scope of data collection, the nature of the digital assessments, and the use of their data for the development and validation of digital biomarkers.

Data collection through wearables, smartphone interaction and digital active tests were implemented subject to predefined technical and organisational safeguards, including encrypted data transmission, controlled storage environments and restricted access based on role-specific authorisation. Also, secure storage and processing were performed on a trusted cloud provider (Hetzner), with access limited to specifically authorised personnel under role-based access control mechanisms. Pseudonymisation measures were systematically applied prior to data analysis and direct identifiers remained under the responsibility of the respective clinical sites, where applicable. All the above safeguards and processing operations are comprehensively described in the Data Processing Agreement (DPA) signed by all involved partners.

In addition to study-specific data, certain digital biomarker models were trained and/or validated using third-party datasets. The use of such third-party datasets was conducted strictly in accordance with their respective data use agreements and terms of use. No processing was undertaken beyond the contractually agreed scope and permitted research purposes.

Throughout the development and validation activities reported in this deliverable, no deviations from the applicable regulatory framework, the approved Study Protocol or the governing data use conditions of third-party datasets were identified.

Overall, the activities described in this report demonstrate alignment with EU data protection standards and ethical requirements applicable to digital health research and the development of AI-based clinical monitoring tools.

13 Conclusions

This deliverable reports on the final stages and outputs of developing and validating dBM for PD based on existing datasets. Based on data from wrist-wearable, user-smartphone interaction, and active digital tests, we investigated and identified, in certain cases, promising dBM of motor and cognitive function, RBD, and daytime somnolence. In **Table 73**, a summary of the Objectives, Key Features, Results and Challenges for all dBM included in this deliverable is presented.

Table 73 Summary table with Objectives, Key Features, Results and Challenges for all dBM

Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD)
Objective: Early detection of RBD using actigraphy data; focus on distinguishing RBD from other conditions.

Key Features: Activity rate, movement episodes, episode duration, skewness metrics, and sleep period boundaries were evaluated as key differentiators.

Results: Machine learning models like Random Forest achieved balanced accuracy up to 89.2% with SMOTE augmentation. Statistical features demonstrated clear separation between RBD and non-RBD groups.

Challenges:

- Lack of nightly ground truth data for RBD occurrence.
- Small dataset sizes and label inconsistencies (e.g., nightly vs subject-level labels).
- Variability in data due to sporadic RBD episodes.

Daytime Somnolence

Objective: Detect and quantify daytime sleep episodes using actigraphy and clustering-based methods.

Key Features: Gaussian mixture models utilized features from sliding time windows of actigraphy data; segment-based clustering identified nap episodes.

Results: 90% overlap between clustering results and Philips Actiware algorithm; detected naps were validated manually or via diaries with 99% accuracy.

Challenges:

- High noise levels in actigraphy data.
- Participant diaries underreported naps compared to automated detection.
- Sensitivity differences between clustering and existing algorithms.

Rest Tremor

Objective: Detect and classify tremor severity using wearable accelerometer data.

Key Features: Hand-movement detection pipeline followed by a deep-learning framework based on a ResNet encoder and Transformer module trained on raw triaxial signals, combined with attention-based multiple-instance learning to capture intermittent tremor episodes.

Results: On the MJFF-LRS dataset, rest tremor detection achieved weighted F1-scores of 0.90 (validation) and 0.87 (test). Tremor amplitude estimation showed significant correlations with MDS-UPDRS item 3.17 ($\rho = 0.77$, $p < 0.05$ for validation; $\rho = 0.68$, $p < 0.05$ for test). On the Verily Study Watch dataset, detection achieved an F1-score of 0.76, with amplitude estimation correlating at $\rho = 0.58$ ($p < 0.05$). Validation on the dBM-DEV study data demonstrated good alignment with clinical scores (MDS-UPDRS item 3.17), with tremor amplitude correlating at $\rho = 0.62$ ($p < 0.05$) and tremor constancy at $\rho = 0.42$ ($p < 0.05$), supporting robustness under real-world, free-living conditions.

Challenges:

- Pronounced class imbalance across tremor severity levels
- Potential confounding effects from voluntary and involuntary movements.
- Variability in wearable hardware, sensor placement, and recording conditions introduces noise in real-world validation.

Dyskinesia

Objective: Detect dyskinesia presence using accelerometer data for real-time monitoring.

Key Features: Sleep-detection pipeline to isolate waking hours, followed by a ResNet–Transformer framework enhanced with attention-based multiple-instance learning to selectively aggregate dyskinesia-relevant temporal segments.

Results: On the MJFF-LRS dataset, the model achieved weighted F1-scores of 0.90 (validation) and 0.86 (test), with recall for dyskinesia episodes of 0.44 (validation) and 0.53 (test). Validation on the dBM-DEV study data showed a weak but statistically significant correlation with MDS-UPDRS item 4.1 (Spearman $\rho = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$).

Challenges:

- Distinguishing dyskinesia from other voluntary and involuntary movements.
- Lack of annotated datasets for rigorous training and testing.

- Strong data class imbalance.

Human Activity Recognition and Physical Activity

Objective: Quantify overall mobility and physical activity to contextualize symptom fluctuations.

Key Features: Step-count pipeline followed by a deep-learning-based human activity recognition framework that classifies activity intensity levels.

Results: On the Capture-24 dataset, the activity recognition model achieved F1-scores of 0.73 (validation) and 0.70 (test). Application to the dBM-DEV study data revealed clinically meaningful differences across groups, with PD participants exhibiting reduced daily step counts and increased day-to-day activity variability compared to healthy controls.

Challenges:

- Individual variability in activity levels and patterns.
- Limited datasets representing diverse PD symptom severities.
- Noise and inconsistencies in real-world wearable data.

Slowness of Movement (Keystroke Dynamics)

Objective: Assess finger and hand bradykinesia and rigidity through typing patterns on touchscreens.

Key Features: Statistical features of key hold time and between-keys flight time sequences during natural typing.

Results: A regression model was trained on in-clinic-collected typing data to predict the finger tapping item (Item 23) of UPDRS Part III. The model was tested the dBM-DEV dataset with data collected in daily-living and the digital score exhibited good correlation with the associated clinical score (MDS-UPDRS Part III Item 3.4) ($r = 0.61$, $p < 0.05$). Test-retest reliability on data aggregated per week showed excellent short-term ($ICC(3,k) > 0.9$) and good long-term reliability ($ICC(3,k) > 0.75$). Longitudinal trajectories when aggregated weekly appear stable.

Challenges:

- Small sample size of the in-clinic and dBM-DEV training dataset
- Use of right hand as dominant hand on the training dataset
- Effect of medication (ON-OFF) periods and covariates of keystroke dynamics
- Data sparsity and variability in MDS-UPDRS Items

Slowness of Movement (Wrist Accelerometry)

Objective: Assess slowness of gross upper limb movement through a wrist-worn accelerometer.

Key Features: Features extracted from time-windowed 3-axis accelerometer signals during hand movement and no gait periods.

Results: The pipeline with the hand movement detector, gait detector, and the slowness of movement estimator was refined. For the slowness of movement estimator, a regressor was re-trained with acceleration features derived from the Verily Study Watch dataset to predict a composite clinical score of MDS-UPDRS Part III items related to bradykinesia and rigidity. After applying age correction the digital score exhibited a correlation of $r = 0.67$ ($p < 0.05$) with the clinical composite score and differed significantly between severity categories. We tested the model trained on the Verily Study Watch dataset two independent dataset containing data captured in free-living. For the MJFF Levodopa Response Study dataset the digital score yielded correlation $r = 0.69$ ($p < 0.05$), while for the data from the dBM-DEV study correlation $r = 0.60$ ($p < 0.05$).

Challenges:

- Lack of information regarding the hand wearing the accelerometer
- Effect of covariates of acceleration (sex, body-mass index) other than age
- Lack of information regarding medication to capture intra-day fluctuations
- Small sample size of external datasets.

Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT)

Objective: Evaluate posture, balance, and motor coordination through active camera-based motion tracking assessments.

Key Features: Joint angles, posture symmetry, and movement time series were captured and analysed with motion-tracking pipelines.

Results: Models effectively correlated movement features with clinical scores for motor impairment (e.g., UPDRS Part III). High precision in detecting abnormalities in gait, posture, and transitions.

Challenges:

- Limited datasets for validating complex multi-movement assessments.
- Variability in patient engagement during active assessments.
- Dependency on controlled environments for reliable data capture.

Cognitive Function Active Assessment

Objective: Assess cognitive performance through cognitive tasks (Stop-Signal, Balloon Analogue Risk Task and N-Back tests) administered via a smartphone application.

Key Features: Task completion times, accuracy rates, and derived metrics such as reaction time variability and task-specific scores.

Results:

Selected features indicative of cognitive performance were defined as dBMs of interest according to the literature, for all three active cognitive tests. The features extracted in dBM-DEV demonstrate that remote cognitive assessment via the smartphone app is feasible and yields interpretable results. Consequently, all three tests have been implemented in the ongoing AI-PMP study (N=100 PD patients) via the mAI-Care app. It is expected that their features will provide fine-grained insights into PD disease progression and treatment response, potentially enhancing the accuracy of the predictive models.

Challenges:

- Variability in task performance due to patient familiarity and engagement, and potentially environmental distractors that are not accounted for.
- Balancing task complexity with usability for diverse patient groups.

Taken together, the work presented in this deliverable demonstrates that a diverse portfolio of digital biomarkers, spanning passive sensing, active assessments, and smartphone-based interaction, can capture meaningful aspects of motor, behavioural, and cognitive function in PD. Across modalities, several dBMs showed encouraging validity, reliability, and coherence with clinical expectations, while others highlighted important methodological and practical challenges that must be addressed as the project advances. The insights gained from these analyses, combined with the limitations identified, provide a clear roadmap for refining the algorithms, strengthening validation pipelines, and enhancing data collection protocols in the ongoing AI-PMP study.

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